

Landscape of no-fee open access publishing in Africa

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1. Executive summary

This study provides an overview of open access (OA) journals in Africa that do not charge fees for either authors or readers (often referred to as Diamond OA journals). It is based on survey responses from 199 journals, 21 institutional, national and continental platforms that host Diamond OA journals, and 25 country reports with information about current funding and financial sustainability approaches and challenges, institutional in-kind support, incentives and collaborations among Diamond OA journals, needs and strategies to advance Diamond OA publishing.

This landscape study was conducted as a part of the three-year [‘Collaboration for sustainable open access publishing in Africa’](#) project (November 2023- October 2026), implemented by EIFL, AJOL (African Journals Online) and WACREN (the West and Central African Research and Education Network) with support from Wellcome. The study informed and guided us in our planning for developing and delivering a participatory funding approach to strengthen the quality and sustainability of African Diamond OA publishing while maintaining its diversity. The project will also strengthen national and regional collaboration on Diamond OA publishing and seek to secure funding commitments from African governments and institutions by embedding support for Diamond OA publishing in open science policies.

Most journals that responded to our survey are relatively small in terms of output: 64.8% of the responding journals published up to 20 articles and 31.7% published 11–20 articles in 2023.

About 60% of the respondents rely on volunteer work fully or partially. More than half of the respondents who do have a dedicated unit responsible for publishing with employed staff (30.2%), still rely on volunteer work. Interestingly, a comparison with data relating to staff size shows that those with 2–5 team members (38 of 61) and those who have more than 30 team members (10 of 18) mostly rely on volunteer work, either fully or partially.

Institutional funding: 45.7% of the respondents have institutional funding provided either through permanent (24.6%) or periodically negotiated subsidies (21.1%) from the journal’s primary institution’s base.

The study outlines other sources of funding for Diamond OA journals that could be aspirational, e.g. donations, membership and partner support, training income or, (depressingly) personal money.

Sustainability: Almost equal numbers of respondents see their funding sources as stable or very stable (40.1%) and unstable or very unstable (39.2%). Most journals (71.4%) do not have an annual approved budget. The majority of the respondents (56.8%) have a journal sustainability plan. The study describes major financial sustainability challenges that also include global reach and visibility challenges, human resources and volunteer work challenges, administrative and organizational challenges, lack of strategic and sustainability planning skills, technical challenges and training needs.

Institutional in-kind support: The most common types of support from journal host organizations include general IT services (used by 52.3% respondents), service-specific IT services – publishing platforms, websites and other tools (45.7%), and facilities and premises (45.7%). The majority of journals (57.8%) rely on multiple forms of support provided by the host organization, while 7% report receiving no support.

Institutional incentives: Almost a quarter of the responding journals reported that their institutions provided incentives for journal personnel, e.g. additional points during evaluation/promotion, allowances, bonuses and honoraria, and reduction in regular work and working hours (including teaching load and institutional administrative work).

Collaborations: More than three quarters of the respondents (77.4%) would consider collaborating with other organizations, with the most popular areas for collaboration being training, support and/or advice on publishing policies and best practices, IT services, production, communications and editorial services.

Peer review and editorial boards: 96.7% of the respondents have some form of anonymous peer review. Double-anonymized peer review prevails among 83.9% of the respondents. 85.9% of the respondents have specific policies/guidelines/instructions on editorial quality (with definition of quality criteria, compliance, peer review process and editorial independence commitment) and research integrity/publication ethics. A vast majority of the surveyed journals have manageable editorial boards: 79.9% of respondents have up to 20 members in their editorial boards or other editorial bodies, with almost equal shares of those having up to ten board members (40.2%) and those with 11–20 members (39.7%). Approximately one quarter of the respondents (24.6%) have more than 50% of editorial board members from outside of the journal's country and nearly half (48.7%) of the respondents have more than half of editorial board members from outside their institutions.

Technical service efficiency: Nearly half (49.2%) of the respondents rely solely on in-house infrastructure, almost one-third use outsourced services (31.2%), while about 10.1% combine various in-house and outsourced resources. For more than half of the respondents (56.3%), the publishing infrastructure supports all publishing workflows online (e.g. a journal's online platform is used to submit manuscripts, review them and make them openly available after approval for publication). Public Knowledge Project's open-source software Open Journal Systems (OJS) is by far the most popular publishing software used in the surveyed sample (68.3%). Almost three

quarters (74.4%) of the respondents assign unique persistent identifiers. The most commonly used is Crossref DOI: more than half of the surveyed journals (56.8%) use Crossref DOI. ORCID is used by 25.6%.

Visibility and discoverability (including indexation): More than half of the respondents (53.3%) have said that their journals are indexed in African Journals Online (AJOL) and half of them are discoverable via Google Scholar. Those indexed in the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) account for nearly one third (32.7%), while the share of those indexed in the Web of Science and Scopus is considerably smaller – 10.1% and 13.1%, respectively. The most common challenges faced by journals when applying for indexing include meeting the technical criteria and membership fees (21.11%), followed by satisfying the metadata requirements (17.1%) and non-technical participation criteria (15.1%). Although insufficiently detailed, free-text responses provide more information about the challenging non-technical requirements: some journals are rejected because of their local, i.e. African focus, low citation rates in citation databases, authors coming from limited geographic areas and endogeneity (too many papers authored by editorial board members or the reviewers working for the journal). A few respondents also mentioned the unresponsiveness of the indexing services, who have never provided feedback about their applications.

Overall challenges: Financial constraints are by far the most pressing challenge that affects three quarters (74.87%) of the respondents, while nearly half of them (45.2%) are struggling with the lack of human resources. Infrastructure-related and administrative challenges affect more than 30% of the respondents. Additional challenges include recruiting reviewers and the slow pace of their work, low submission rates, registration in journal databases, marketing, geographic diversity of authors, but also the fact that African journals are expected to adopt ethical principles and guidelines coming from the West, though these are not necessarily relevant in the African context.

Unmet funding needs: We grouped unmet funding needs in the topics of editorial quality challenges, administrative constraints, funding, collaboration and partnerships challenges, technology challenges, visibility and indexation challenges and interoperability challenges.

Support required: Human resources and technical support ensuring interoperability would make Diamond OA journals more sustainable and would strive to solve the visibility challenges. Advocacy for Diamond OA publishing and knowledge sharing and training support have also been requested by respondents.

This study also provides some information on institutional, national and continental platforms that host Diamond OA journals, their unmet funding needs and support required to make these platforms more sustainable. Platforms differ in size measured by the number of hosted journals (ten platforms host 1–5 journals; seven - 21–30 journals, one - 100–200 journals, while one hosts more than 500 journals) and the number of published articles (seven platforms have up to 1,000 articles, six - 1,000–5,000, two - 5,000–10,000, two - 10,000–50,000, and two - 100,000–500,000 articles). While nine platforms host only Diamond OA journals,

others also host journals that charge author fees. Altogether, the surveyed platforms host 302 Diamond OA journals. Although the stability of funding sources also varies, the majority of the respondents see their funding sources as either stable or very stable. Platform host organizations provide facilities and premises, salaries, general and service-specific IT services. Most platforms rely on multiple types of support. Platforms are open to different types of collaborations on training, production services and communication services. Ten respondents have a platform sustainability plan. In most cases the platform's technical infrastructure is maintained and updated in-house. And in most cases (16) the platform supports all publishing workflows online. Financial and human resources are the main challenges faced.

Country reports provide more context to the diverse Diamond OA publishing landscape and describe the operations of major national and institutional Diamond OA publishing initiatives and Diamond OA journals, their challenges and funding needs. Recommendations are made in the areas of funding, training and capacity building, infrastructure and technology, advocacy and awareness raising, recognition and incentives, quality assurance, inclusivity, diversity and international collaboration.

2. Introduction and methodology

The research comprised three parts:

1. Community consultation, through a survey, to identify the potential of African Diamond OA journals and platforms, challenges faced by them and their funding needs in order to plan our grant funding calls for projects accordingly. The survey tool used drew on the [“Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication” \(DIAMAS\)](#) Institutional Publishing in the European Research Area Landscape Survey¹ questionnaire adapted to our needs.
2. Expert reports that include qualitative analysis of Diamond OA journals and institutional and national Diamond OA publishing initiatives in 22 countries, their challenges, needs, gaps and opportunities, as well as suggested support actions on the journal, institutional and national levels.
3. Desk research in three countries building on previous OA publishing projects results.

The survey for Diamond OA journals (in English and French) and the survey for OA publishing platforms (English) hosting Diamond OA journals included the following six sections with a total of 37 questions for journals and 39 questions for the platforms:

1. General features
2. Funding, incentives, institutional support, sustainability and collaborations
3. Editorial quality and research integrity/publication ethics
4. Technical service efficiency
5. Visibility and discoverability (including indexation)
6. Challenges, funding needs and support required to make Diamond OA publishing more sustainable

Questionnaires are available in

[Appendix 1](#). “Collaboration for sustainable open access publishing in Africa” journals survey

[Appendix 2](#). Enquête: Aidez-nous à comprendre l'accès ouvert selon la voie diamant en Afrique

[Appendix 3](#). “Collaboration for sustainable open access publishing in Africa” portals survey

The survey results are presented in sections 3. Diamond OA journals and 4. Continental, national and institutional platforms for Diamond OA journals.

¹ [Full survey analysis](#), [full country reports](#), [complete country reports](#), and the entire [survey dataset](#). The key findings are also presented in a synopsis [available here](#).

To create a more comprehensive picture of Diamond OA publishing in Africa, we collaborated with experts in OA publishing in 22 countries (Algeria, Benin, Botswana, Burkina Faso, Côte d'Ivoire, Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), Ethiopia, Ghana, Kenya, Lesotho, Malawi, Mali, Morocco, Mozambique, Namibia, Nigeria, South Africa, Tanzania, Togo, Tunisia, Zambia and Zimbabwe) to conduct qualitative analysis mapping the national Diamond OA publishing landscape. While writing their country reports, the experts engaged their national networks – e.g. university and library consortia – in qualitative data collection. We asked the experts to answer the following questions:

- **Who/Which** are the significant Diamond OA journals, institutional and national Diamond OA publishing initiatives (journal platforms, etc.) in their countries.
- **What** are the challenges of Diamond OA publishing, needs, gaps and opportunities of Diamond OA publishing support in their countries.
- **How** to improve quality Diamond OA publishing in their countries: suggested support actions on the journal, institutional and national levels.

Highlights from experts' reports are included in section 5. Country overviews and recommendations.

Desk research was conducted in Angola, Senegal and Uganda. For Angola, we reviewed "[OA for Angola Collaborative Project](#)" results from UNESCO, the Ministério do Ensino Superior, Ciência, Tecnologia e Inovação, Redalyc of the Autonomous University of the State of Mexico, AmeliCA and the Universidade Óscar Ribas. For Senegal and Uganda, we build on our previous OA publishing project results: [OA in Senegal](#) and [OA and open science in Uganda](#).

However, because Diamond OA publishing varies from country to country, and information about these topics was limited or unavailable in some countries, information across countries is uneven.

3. Diamond OA journals

We are grateful for 206 responses received from 199 journals from 27 countries (Algeria, Angola, Benin, Cameroon, Central African Republic, Côte d'Ivoire, DRC, Egypt, Ethiopia, Gambia, Ghana, Kenya, Libya, Madagascar, Malawi, Mali, Morocco, Mozambique, Nigeria, Rwanda, Somalia, South Africa, Tanzania, Togo, Tunisia, Uganda and Zimbabwe) submitted in English, French and Portuguese.

In a few instances, more than one person responded from a particular journal. In these cases, we retained the more complete responses and removed duplicates. A total of seven duplicates were removed, and the analysis was conducted on 199 responses.

About a dozen responses came from journals that charge Article Processing Charges (APCs). In some cases, the responses from journals charging APCs were the only responses received from their countries and they provided some insights into the current OA publishing landscape. Furthermore, funding schemes used by OA journals are complex. Journals often rely on multiple funding sources, and APCs, as with print sales, may be used only marginally and not as the main revenue stream. Such journals have the potential to flip to a fully Diamond OA publishing model. The fact that APC-based journals responded to a survey targeting Diamond OA journals may reflect an interest to move in this direction. As the survey is not motivated by statistical considerations, we have adopted a more inclusive approach that offers broader insights, while taking into account the diversity of OA publishing and forthcoming project work on the strategies for flipping APC-based journals to Diamond OA.

Table 1. The distribution of the journal survey responses by country

Country, where your Diamond OA journal is registered/based	# journals	% journals
Algeria	18	9.05%
Angola	1	0.50%
Benin	1	0.50%
Cameroon	4	2.01%
Central African Republic	1	0.50%
Congo (The Democratic Republic of the Congo)	1	0.50%

Country, where your Diamond OA journal is registered/based	# journals	% journals
Côte d'Ivoire	2	1.01%
Egypt	3	1.51%
Ethiopia	14	7.04%
Gambia	1	0.50%
Ghana	30	15.08%
Kenya	13	6.53%
Libya	2	1.01%
Madagascar	1	0.50%
Malawi	2	1.01%
Mali	2	1.01%
Morocco	19	9.55%
Mozambique	4	2.01%
Nigeria	21	10.55%
Rwanda	2	1.01%
Somalia	1	0.50%
South Africa	34	17.09%
Tanzania	8	4.02%
Togo	1	0.50%
Tunisia	7	3.52%
Uganda	3	1.51%
Zimbabwe	3	1.51%
Total	199	100.00%

3.1 Overview of Diamond OA journals

199 journals completed the survey, most of which are relatively small in terms of the output: most journals (129; 64.8%) published up to 20 articles and over one third (63; 31.7%) published 11–20 articles in 2023.

# articles published in 2023	# journals	% journals
0	7	3.5%
1-5	29	14.6%
6-10	37	18.6%
11-20	63	31.7%
21-30	17	8.5%
31-50	15	7.5%
51-100	19	9.5%
100-300	9	4.5%
more than 300	3	1.5%
Total	199	100.0%

Note: Most respondents provided absolute numbers, which were coded into ranges to make it easier to read the data.

Figure 1. The size of journals measured by the number of articles published in 2023

199 respondents represent/cover all disciplines. Most journals are either multidisciplinary or cover more than one discipline (55.3%). Medical and health sciences (14.6%) and Social sciences (15.1%) journals are the most numerous among single-discipline journals. The distribution of the respondents across major disciplinary clusters shows that Social sciences and Humanities (SSH; 31.7%) journals are slightly better represented in the sample than STEM

(Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics; 28.1%). The remaining 40.2%, grouped under the ‘multidisciplinary’ label include journals that cover both SSH and STEM topics.

Figure 2. The distribution of journals across major disciplinary clusters

Table 2. The distribution of journals across disciplines

Disciplines	# journals	%
Multidisciplinary or multiple disciplines	110	55.3%
Natural sciences	4	2.0%
Engineering and technology	7	3.5%
Medical and health sciences	29	14.6%
Agricultural sciences	4	2.0%
Social sciences	30	15.1%
Humanities	15	7.5%
Total	199	100.0%

More than 40% of the respondents have small editorial teams (excluding Editorial boards) comprising one to five people (groups less than 2 and 2–5), while 5% do not have any editorial team members. More than one fifth (22.1%) have 6–10 people and the share of those having 11–20 people is still not insignificant (15.6%). The journals with more than 20 team members (groups 21–30 and more than 30) account for 13.3%.²

² The ‘unclear’ group includes those journals that submitted duplicate responses providing inconsistent information.

Figure 3. The number of people working for a journal in any capacity (excluding the Editorial boards)

About 60% of the respondents rely on volunteer work fully or partially. Although 30.2% of them have a dedicated unit responsible for publishing with employed staff, 16.6% still rely on volunteer work.

How does your journal's personnel work?	# journals	%
Dedicated unit with personnel fully or partially employed to work for the journal	27	13.6%
No dedicated unit and everyone is working as volunteers	87	43.7%
Dedicated unit responsible for the journal with some personnel employed and some volunteers	33	16.6%
No dedicated unit, but personnel employed by the institution is sharing their time	41	20.6%
Unclear	11	5.5%
Total	199	100.0%

Figure 4. The reliance of journals on the employed personnel and volunteers

Interestingly, a comparison with data relating to staff size shows that those with 2–5 team members (38 of 61) and those with more than 30 team members (10 of 18) predominantly rely on volunteer work, either fully or partially.

Table 3. The relationship between the personnel size and the reliance on employed personnel and/or volunteers

Personnel size	U/E	V	U/E,V	E	Unclear	Total	
						#	%
None	0	7	1	2	0	10	5.0%
Less than 2	3	8	3	7	1	22	11.1%
2–5	9	30	8	10	4	61	30.7%
6–10	9	14	9	7	5	44	22.1%
11–20	0	12	8	11	0	31	15.6%
21–30	1	4	1	3	0	9	4.5%
More than 30	5	10	2	1	0	18	9.0%
Unclear	0	2	1	0	1	4	2.0%
Total	27	87	33	41	11	199	100.0%
%	13.6%	43.7%	16.6%	20.6%	5.5%	100.0%	

U/E Dedicated unit with personnel fully or partially employed to work for the journal

V No dedicated unit and everyone is working as volunteers

U/E,V Dedicated unit responsible for the journal with some personnel employed and some volunteers

E No dedicated unit, but personnel employed by the institution is sharing their time

3.2 Funding and sustainability, institutional support and incentives, collaborations among Diamond OA journals

3.2.1 Funding

The majority of the respondents (91; 45.7%) have institutional funding provided either through permanent (49; 24.6%) or periodically negotiated subsidies (21.1%) from the journal's primary institution. For a significant number of journals institutional subsidies are the only funding source. Those relying solely on permanent subsidies provided by the journal's primary institution account for 25% (35 journals) of the total sample, while 21.43% (30 journals) receive only periodically negotiated institutional subsidies.

Table 4. Funding sources

Funding sources	# journals using this funding source	# journals using only this funding source
Fixed and permanent subsidy from your journal's primary institution's base	49	35
Periodically negotiated subsidy from your journal's primary institution's base	42	30
Time-limited grants or subsidies, either private or public from outside your journal's primary institution's base	20	12
Permanent public/government funding (international, national, local)	12	7
Collective funding (e.g. crowdfunding, membership fees, etc.)	23	16
Print sales	22	10
Other	45	22

Other sources of funding mentioned by respondents include (in alphabetical order):

- **Advertising**, although not always reliable: "At the initial stage the journal was mainly relying on advertisements from pharmaceutical companies, but this has now dwindled down and is no longer a reliable source of income. The journal would do with reliable financial support as currently it is entirely supported by the two associations, and they are getting overstretched as the journal is not their core business."
- **Events**: "Book launch during annual conferences of the Society"
- **Departmental funding**
- **Donations**: e.g. "research project donation" / "goodwill donations from colleagues or Associations" / "volunteer donations"
- **Support provided from another journal that charges publication fees**
- **Grants**
- **Membership support**
- **Optional publication fee**

- **Personal money:** “Chief Editor's own pocket funding” / “personal research funds” / “personal research funds from Advisory and Editorial board or other members”
- **Print on demand**
- **Seed funding for the initial volume**
- **Sponsorship**
- **Training earnings:** “The Journal is produced by the Think tank of the University. Being the Think tank of the University as well as for the country, there are efforts to sustain the Journal through partnership with key security players in the country and regionally. The Think tank conducts research and paid short courses and sensitization workshops. Part of the earnings of the training go towards the production of the journal.”
- **Support from the partners:** e.g. [African Journals Partnership \(AJPP\)](#), through a once-off grant from KU Select secured by a publisher.

3.2.2 Sustainability

Almost equal shares of respondents see their funding sources as stable or very stable (40.1%) and unstable or very unstable (39.2%) in the last three years.

Table 5. The stability of funding sources

Stability of funding sources	# journals	%
Very stable	14	7.0%
Stable	64	32.2%
Neither stable not unstable	27	13.6%
Unstable	46	23.1%
Very unstable	34	17.1%
Don't know	14	7.0%
Total	199	100.0%

Unstable funding offers a risk of switching a journal's business model from Diamond OA to a fee-based publishing model: “Unstable funding sources. We plan to charge a submission fee as soon as the journal is indexed in Medline/Pubmed.”

The majority (149; 74.9%) of those who consider their funding sources stable do not rely on permanent institutional subsidies. The majority (38 of 49) of those who have access to this type of funding consider their funding sources either stable or very stable, which, expectedly, is not the case with other funding sources.

The majority of journals (71.4%) don't have an annual approved budget.

Table 6. The presence of an annual approved budget

Have a budget	# journals	%
No	142	71.4%
Yes	57	28.6%
Total	199	100.0%

The majority of the respondents (113; 56.8%) have a journal sustainability plan.

Table 7. The presence of a sustainability plan

Have a sustainability plan	# journals	%
No	86	43.2%
Yes	113	56.8%
Total	199	100.0%

Financial sustainability challenges mentioned by the respondents include the following:

Financial challenges

- “Inflation; unstable finance base.
- “Lack of foreign currency resources.”
- “Lack of stable/permanent source of funding/ subsidy from the journal's primary institution's base and also collaborating organizations.”
- “Limited funding”
- “Reliance on government funding, little increase in funding for growth and development needs for journal and human capacity”
- “The budget set for a journal is inadequate and sometimes the money is not available when requested. We usually pay for English editing and sometimes it takes a long time to pay, which is likely to jeopardize the commitment of these editors. We usually have physical meetings to deliberate on the issues before the decision to publish; some editorial members have to travel to attend; they are forced to use their resources and we delay in reimbursing them. This is likely to reduce the commitment of some members.”
- “The financial coverage of the journal depends on the project funding grant obtained by the journal's publisher. No dedicated stable finding for the journal.”
- “The KU Select funding has run out. We have some bridging finances saved, but are looking to transition to a subscribe to open model as suggested by our publisher, Berghahn books.”
- “The lack of funding and the high cost of hosting should we use commercial publishers or journal hosting sites. We also find people unwilling to volunteer their services. Reintroducing APC would deny many of our colleagues an opportunity to publish. To address the funding issue we are looking at applying for institutional support as well as financial support from the host society subscription fees.”
- “The main challenge is that the journal is funded through grants. Other options for more sustainable funding are not entirely clear at this point.”

- “The main challenges related to the financial sustainability of our journal include: Over reliance on the editor-in-chief as the sole funder, which may not be sustainable in the long term. Lack of external funding sources, limiting financial resources for editorial tasks, and maintaining quality standards. To address these challenges, we could consider the following strategies:
 - Diversifying funding sources by seeking grants, sponsorships, or partnerships with academic institutions or organizations aligned with the journal's mission.
 - Developing a comprehensive sustainability plan that outlines financial goals, revenue generation strategies, and operational efficiency and cost management measures.
 - Exploring alternative revenue streams such as advertising, conference sponsorship, etc.”
- “The only source of funding annually is through sponsorship from Institutions. The majority of the infrastructure was destroyed during the war. At present, the managing editorial board members are carrying out their duties with limited resources, relying on a few outdated computers. We are actively seeking sponsors to provide essential infrastructure such as computers, printers, furniture, and other necessary equipment. Furthermore, it is essential to allocate paid professionals to manage copy editing, production tasks, maintenance of a website and indexing processes in various databases.”
- “The main challenge is having one source of funding. We hope we can secure other sources of funds to continue with our Diamond OA.”
- “The major challenge for our journal is it has no budget. We believe that collaboration mitigates the problem.”
- “Uncertainty of funding source; limited nature of existing financial support (grant)”
- “We are missing the stable funding, we are collecting the journal's funds from the founders (persons) to support OA publishing.”
- “We are reliant on donor funding. We are getting a lot of goodwill support from AJPP and partners.”

Global reach and visibility as a challenge:

- “Competition from global publishers”
- “Lack of diversified manuscripts from different parts of the world.” / “The main challenge is getting foreign institutions’ researchers to publish their research articles with the journal”
- “Low visibility: building readership and impact in a crowded market can be challenging. These challenges can be addressed by diversifying funding sources: exploring grants, partnerships with international institutions, or alternative funding models like micro-donations; improving quality and visibility: implementing rigorous peer review, publishing high-quality research, and actively promoting the journal through conferences, social media, and other channels; developing strategic partnerships: collaborating with other journals, libraries, or research institutions for resource sharing and promotion.”
- “The main challenge is related to the facilities that enable the journal to be accessed by a large audience (visibility).”

- “The viability of our journal may face several major challenges. Here are some of these challenges and suggestions on how to address them:
 - Increased competition: In our country, the competition among journals to attract quality contributions is intense. That is why we have chosen the field of research in African management, an efficient and transparent peer-review process, and thus, to build a strong editorial reputation.”
- “There is competition for funding from grants, sponsorships, or institutional support, especially in niche research areas or during economic downturns. It can be addressed by actively seeking out partnerships with funding agencies, collaborating with academic institutions or professional societies, or launching fundraising campaigns among their readership base.”

Human resources challenges

- “Additional pay as incentive for journal chief editor, deputies, editors and associate editors”
- “Admin and publishing services (copy editing, proofing, typesetting) are the biggest challenges.”
- “Financial sustainability is needed in order to engage the services of permanent staff for the journal.”
- “High reviewer attrition rate” / “Lack of reviewers because of lack of incentives.” / “Slow feedback from reviewers”
- “Human resources are very scarce – new skilled people need to be involved but the university is facing the limitation to contract new people.”
- “Lack of motivation for journal personnel”
- “Limitation of the finance budgets and proper reviewers and an editor in our cause to publish the journal by the given time.”
- “Motivation for the editor and the editorial office. It can be addressed through alternative funding among many others.”
- “No reliable financial support to enable peer review process.”
- “Pay the salary of a full time administrative support person. Provide editing services.”
- “Since there is no monetary advantage, getting people to participate in our publication in various capacities takes much work. Even if we have not yet succeeded, we are still looking for partners.”
- “The editorial boards are not well constituted.”
- “The journal faces challenges due to the absence of Associate Editors, causing significant workload for the Editor-in-Chief, deputy Editor-in-Chief, and Managing Editor and affecting the timeliness of the journal. Finding reviewers is difficult due to lack of review incentive. The journal's lack of financial resources is causing staff discouragement.”
- “The journal is relatively young and recently accredited through DOAJ and Scopus. Since accreditation, the volume of work has increased significantly. The journal does not incur much by way of costs but does need to pay an annual fee to the publisher. At present, this is self-funded through the editor's own research funds. The main challenge therefore is that the sustainability of the journal would be jeopardized if the editor were to

leave the role for any reason. Because the journal does not generate any income, future editorial personnel would need to similarly self-fund the operation of the journal. In addition, the funding constraints mean that either the journal editor must take all tasks on (e.g. editing, proofing, layout, typesetting, managing reviewing etc), or must use additional research funds to pay staff to support in these areas, or must rely on volunteers. These options are either unsustainable (in the third case) or a drain on the time and/or research funds of the editor (in the first two cases). At present, there is no strategy as to how these challenges can be overcome. It is something the editorial board has considered, but is yet to find a sustainable solution that preserves the fully open access nature of the journal.”

- “The journal needs sponsorship for copy editor and editorial assistants.”
- “The main challenge is the need to attract and retain high-quality authors and reviewers, which can be addressed by offering incentives such as recognition, awards, and other benefits.”
- “The peer review process takes a long time due to the unavailability of incentives and authors end up withdrawing their papers.”
- “The rising costs of typesetting and technical support is becoming tenuous. The time dedicated to editorial duties requires a full-time employee to uphold the standards the journal strives for.”
- “We need additional funds to pay an annual honorarium to our new Editor in Chief. We are seeking support from corporate organizations, but any other sources of support would also be considered.”

Institutional challenges:

- “Actually, the journal is owned by a University; a public and governmental higher learning institute. All infrastructures used by the journal are owned by the University, although the university has limitations in finance, skilled manpower and infrastructures like internet connections, power supply and others. Most of them are associated with the economics of the country at large.”
- “Administrative inflexibility”
- “Competition for available funds within the host organization.”
- “Grant allocation has become unstable and the University Research Council does not allow internal budgeting for the publication/production of a journal. The institutions where Diamond OA journals are housed should take pride in such efforts, and contribute to the sustainable funding.”
- “Inadequate logistical support including funding. Seek institutional budgetary support to meet its cost of operations. Provision of office space and facilities like computers, a printer and internet access. Capacity building to enhance performance of staff (editors, layout and formatting.”
- “Our journal depends on our institution, which ensures the financial viability of the establishment in general, according to its guidelines.”
- “Perhaps the administrative procedures to access institutional finance for the journal and budgeting are the two main challenges.”

- “The Association covers all of the costs. They have been stable, however, it is a risk to the journal if association’s funding decreases. The journal costs are currently covered by advertisements sourced by the association.”
- “The journal is big, but it is treated equally with other small journals by the host institution. The journal now requires at least three full time staff since the submission reached over 2000. But, the host does not want to spend.”
- “The journal is located in the Faculty of the Humanities, and as such is financially maintained by the University. The challenges to our financial sustainability are tied to the general financial challenges of the higher education sector in the country. At present our support from the institution is stable in as far as it provides the necessary IT-support, provides for one full-time appointed editorial staff member, and covers the generation and (limited) printing costs of the journal. This more than adequately facilitates the execution of editorial tasks, the maintenance of quality standards and accessibility of published content. The editorial staff, however, being primarily discipline-specific academically trained, are not necessarily equipped to develop and implement financial strategies.”
- “The journal relies on an NGO for its funding. There are a number of potential solutions: endowments, institutional partnerships, sponsored supplements, advertising agreements; grants from international bodies and scientific writing workshops to mention but a few.”
- “The main challenge is reliance on host institution funding, which is not great at the moment. Though stable, finances are used to support basic elements such as editorial meetings. I think universities should aim to have dedicated staff managing these journals and resources.”
- “The main challenge is to free ourselves financially from the university, by drawing up a financing plan outside this dependence.”
- “There are currently no challenges. Given that the journal is funded by a government organization/parastatal, in future there could be challenges related to cost-cutting that may be required due to a shortage of funds from the Government.”
- “Volunteer work is unreliable and seasonal. More institutional commitment would help, despite its constant clamor that the university has no money. I plan on contacting professors, and my business friends to assist financially.”
- “We need more commitments from corporate donors to fund the basic costs”
- “We only receive an annual budget. A three-year funding period will allow for greater financial stability”

Printing costs, going online only:

- “Cost of printing hard copies.”
- “Making a journal available in electronic format only.”

Strategic and sustainability planning challenges:

- “A permanent plan, editor, staffing and financial/funding plan”
- “Make a journal attractive for sponsors, invest in promotion to attract more sponsors.”

- “Our main challenges are related to funding to get our consultants to meet in order to develop a strategic plan that will facilitate the consistent execution of the journal’s editorial tasks, and to assure adherence to globally recognized quality standards in editorial work and publishing.”

Technical and facility challenges:

- “Basic Infrastructure to run the Editorial Office: Office for Editor-in-Chief with well-equipped state-of-the-art provisions including furniture, chairs, Desktop/Laptop etc.; Office for Managing Editor with well-equipped state-of-the-art provisions; Secretary Office with all the basic provisions of equipment (desktop/photocopy/printers/Wi-Fi) and stationaries; Office for Copy Editor with all the basic provisions; Office for the Proof Reader with all the basic provisions; Office for the Content Manager and Communication with all the basic provisions; Office for Computer & Technical Expert; Meeting Office; Professional Payment for the following Editorial Team: Editor-in-Chief, Managing Editor, Copy Editor, Proofreader, Content and Communication Manager, Technical Expert, Secretary Office;”
- “Funding for editorial tools – AI plagiarism checkers; currently institutional Turnitin but it does not have AI checking capacity”.
- “Funding is needed to cover our annual production and OJS hosting fees. Sadly we cannot currently claim/raise funds from our institution to cover these costs.”
- “Funding for IT.”
- “ICT problem.”
- “Journal management platform.”
- “Lack of infrastructure: maintaining robust editorial and publishing systems can be difficult without adequate resources.”
- “Robust computers are important – acquisition of computers by any possible funder.”
- “Server is always broken down – a new server is needed.”
- “The launch of an OJS platform is an ongoing project. We have engaged a service company specializing in website development. In order to ensure the longevity of the Journal website and maintain free access for readers and authors, we are considering diversifying our income sources by exploring alternative revenue streams, such as sponsorships, partnerships, or hosting events.”
- “To maintain the OA system with high quality publications and reviewing we need more funds to improve the journal online submission system and production and diversify our contributors.”
- “Unreliable internet connectivity.”

Training and support:

- “Training of personnel in order to use the Publication Platform is very important. Consultations from recognized publishers are needed in order to develop policies and regulations and good practices that can help the journal indexed.”
- “Fees to pay to COPE, Crossref, OASPA, and others.”

Volunteer work:

- “Chief editors and a journal manager work solely on a voluntary basis.”
- “Financial constraints make a journal a volunteer work of the Chief Editor and with limited support from the editorial board. The host institution has no budget for the journal currently making it subject to unsustainable publications. The possible corrective measure would be for the Host institution to budget for the journal’s activities.”
- “No funding, personal effort, faculty effort.”
- “Reliance on time inputs from volunteers including the editors in chief, sub-editors, panel members and referees, all of whom are professionals with significant demands on their time and resources.”
- “The editor-in-chief and his team work on a voluntary basis, and we have a shortage of international reviewers, because the rules do not allow us to pay them.”
- “Unsustainable volunteerism: The journal heavily relies on the voluntary work of reviewers and the editorial team, which can become unsustainable in the long run. Therefore, we are exploring incentives for reviewers, seeking funding for editors and associate editors, and promoting the academic value and social responsibility of the journal to attract institutional support.”
- “We do not have a budget, our department provides financial support towards production. This is unreliable.”

3.2.3 Institutional in-kind support

Journal host organizations provide in-kind support either in the form of general IT services, facility costs, publishing platforms, websites and other tools, labour, etc. The most common types of support include general IT services (used by 52.3% respondents), service-specific IT services (45.7%) and the ability to use facilities and premises of the host organization (45.7%). The majority of journals (57.8%) rely on multiple forms of support provided by the host organization, while 7% report no support. If a journal relies on only one form of institutional support, it most commonly belongs to one of these categories.

Table 8. The reliance on institutional in-kind support

Form of support	# journals using this form of support	# journals using only this form of support
Facilities and premises	91	16
Human Resource management	48	1
General IT services	104	27
Service-specific IT services	91	27
Salaries of permanent staff	37	2
Salaries of temporary staff	25	7

Other types of in-kind support include

- Additional pay as incentive for journal chief editor, deputies, editors and associate editors
- Donors, grants, quality management assistance
- Plagiarism checking services
- Stipends

3.2.4 Incentives

Almost one quarter of the respondents have incentives for journal's personnel at their institutions.

Table 9. Incentives for journal's personnel

Incentives for the journal's personnel	# journals	%
No	153	76.9%
Yes	46	23.1%
Total	199	100.0%

Types of incentives in place include (in alphabetical order):

- **Additional points at evaluation/promotion:** "It is an extended professional contribution of the University Regular Staff which will have the weightage for promotion" / "Certificates, which are counted during staff promotion" / "For academic promotion" / "Points for promotion as service" / "It gives the personnel at least 1 point under Academic leadership qualities, for promotion" / "Reviewers and the Editor-in-Chief are awarded scores during the annual personnel evaluation for career progression" / "Incentives in performance evaluation" / "Journal editing seen to contribute to reputation of the institution and counts towards promotion and performance evaluation" / "certificate of completing the required two years' service will be considered for academic promotion" / "the editors' and associates' contributions will be considered for promotion"
- **Allowances:** "An allowance is given after publishing an issue" / "Limited amount as allowance"
- **Bonuses:** "A three-monthly bonus"
- **Collaboration opportunities:** "Collaboration as Editorial Board members"
- **Honoraria:** "Payment of honorarium and special recognition"
- **Internet package, data charges:** "Some amount of money are given to cover data charges"
- **Less other institutional administrative work**
- **Monetary:** "~ 23 USD per month for editors to manage the journal activity by the Ministry of Education" / "up to USD 24 per person per month" / "monthly stipend" / "monthly payment" / "monthly pay" / "small pocket money is paid only for editorial members from university" / "the managing director works for a full-time salary" / "the journal managing editor and secretary is employed and paid a monthly salary" / "there is a small topup for personnels working in the management of the journal"

- **Moral incentives**
- **Recognition/ recommendations**
- **Reduction in regular working hours**
- **Teaching load consideration**
- **Tokens of appreciation:** “A small token of appreciation once an issue of a journal is published”
- **Visibility:** “Both the staff and reviewers are given a chance to publish their profiles on the website. Additionally, authors also have their profiles on the website.”

3.2.5 Collaborations among Diamond OA journals

More than three quarters of the respondents (77.4%) would consider collaborating with other organizations in one or more areas mentioned in the survey. Those who would not collaborate in any of these areas account for 17.1%, while 5.5% said they didn't know.

Figure 5. The willingness of journals to collaborate

Most journals would collaborate on training, support and/or advice on publishing policies and best practice (115; 57.8%); IT services (108; 54.3%), production (103; 51.8%), communication (95; 47.7%) and editorial services (90; 45.2%), while only 20% are interested in collaboration relating to administrative, legal and financial services.

Table 10. Potential collaboration areas

Collaboration areas	# journals ready to collaborate in this area
Editorial services (selection of manuscripts, peer-review, plagiarism checking services, etc.)	90
Production services (copy-editing, proofreading, typesetting, metadata, etc.)	103
IT services (submission system, platform, website, etc.)	108
Communication services (marketing/dissemination, social media, etc.)	95
Administrative, legal and financial services (contracts, accounting, documentation, etc.)	40
Training, support and/or advice on publishing policies and best practice	115

3.3 Editorial quality and research integrity/publication ethics

Vast majority (193; 96.7%) of the respondents have some form of anonymous peer review. Double-anonymized peer review prevails among the respondents (167; 83.9%). Two journals only have editorial peer review and in all other cases it's combined with anonymous peer review. Various forms of open peer review are used only sporadically, in combination with other review types.

Table 11. Peer review types

Peer review type	# journals
Double-anonymized	167
Single-anonymized	37
Editorial review	59
Open identities of the reviewers, authors and editors	2
Open reviewers' reports	3
Open participation in the peer review process	2

Most respondents (171; 85.9%) have specific policies/guidelines/instructions on editorial quality (with definition of quality criteria, compliance, peer review process and editorial independence commitment) and research integrity/publication ethics.

Figure 6. The availability of policies/guidelines/instructions on editorial quality and research integrity / publication ethics

Most respondents (159; 79.9%) have up to 20 members in their editorial boards or other editorial bodies, with almost equal shares of those having up to 10 board members (80; 40.2%) and those with 11–20 members (79; 39.7%). The fact that less than 10% of the respondents have editorial boards with more than 30 members confirms that the vast majority of the surveyed journals has manageable editorial boards.

Size of editorial bodies	# members	%
No editorial board	1	0.5%
1-10	80	40.2%
11-20	79	39.7%
More than 20	36	18.1%
Unclear	3	1.5%
Total	199	100.0%

Figure 7. The size of editorial bodies

Approximately one quarter of the respondents (19; 24.6%) have more than 50% of editorial board members from outside of the journal's country and the share of those with less than 10% of foreign members is almost the same (51; 25.6%).

Editorial board members from outside the country	# members	%
1-10%	51	25.6%
11%-30%	39	19.6%
31-50%	53	26.6%
Over 50%	49	24.6%
No response	7	3.5%
Total	199	100.0%

Figure 8. The percentage of editorial board members from outside the country

At the same time, nearly half (97; 48.7%) of the respondents have more than half of editorial board members from outside their institutions.

Editorial board members from outside the institution	# members	%
1-10%	37	18.6%
11%-30%	20	10.1%
31-50%	41	20.6%
Over 50%	97	48.7%
No response	4	2.0%
Total	199	100.0%

Figure 9. The percentage of editorial board members from outside the institution

Editorial challenges mentioned include:

- The translation of articles into English.
- Financial compensation for the editor-in-chief, editorial board, and reviewers.
- Geographic diversity of authors.
- Motivation for editors and reviewers.
- Participation of the Editorial Board members.

3.4 Technical service efficiency of Diamond OA journals

Nearly half (98; 49.2%) of the respondents rely solely on in-house infrastructure, almost one-third use outsourced services (62; 31.2%), while about 10.1% combine various in-house and outsourced resources.

Technical maintenance	# journals	%
In-house	98	49.2%
In-house and outsourced	20	10.1%
Outsourced	62	31.2%
No response	19	9.5%
Total	199	100.0%

Figure 10. Maintaining and updating a journal’s technical infrastructure

Most journals (138; 69.3%) use only one maintenance option and the survey data reveal a strong reliance on in-house IT services, which are used by almost half of the respondents (95; 47.7%).

Table 12. Provision of technical service maintenance

Technical service maintenance	# journals	# journals using this as the only option
In-house by an IT department/personnel	95	57
In-house by a dedicated publishing department	37	13
In-house across different departments	14	7
Partially outsourced	47	31
Mainly outsourced	16	11
Fully outsourced	23	19

Other responses include:

- AJOL
- Editor-in-chief
- In-house by two volunteers
- Mainly Personal computers are used. No specialized infrastructure is in place
- The Publisher does it, but using OJS
- The technical infrastructure is maintained & updated by volunteers of the journal
- Volunteer personnel
- We use OJS/PKP which we pay on a volunteer base; any other tech infrastructure is done on a volunteer base

For more than half of the respondents (112; 56.3%), the publishing infrastructure supports all publishing workflows online (e.g. a journal's online platform is used to submit manuscripts, review them and make them openly available after approval for publication).

Figure 11. Online publishing workflows in publishing infrastructure

Public Knowledge Project's open-source software Open Journal Systems is by far the most popular publishing software used in the surveyed sample (136³; 68.3%).

³ The numbers include free-text responses. The IMIST platform, which is based on OJS, is included in the OJS category.

Software	# journals	%
Open Journals System (OJS) and OJS-based	136	68.3%
WordPress	14	7.0%
DSpace	2	1.0%
Other	11	5.5%
None or unspecified	9	4.5%
Don't know	27	13.6%
Total	199	100.0%

Figure 12. Software used for the publishing system

Other responses include:

- IMIST platform
- Locally developed, customized software / Our online publishing system
- Manuscript Central
- None
- Our journal is integrated in the Algerian Scientific Journal Platform which is our publishing infrastructure support online
- PUBNiTO
- ScholarOne
- Skin-the-Cat Creative Lab

Almost three quarters (148; 74.4%) of the respondents assign unique persistent identifiers. The majority of journals use only one PID (188; 54.3%) and the most commonly used is Crossref

DOI⁴. More than half of the surveyed journals (113; 56.8%) use Crossref DOI, while for 40.2% it is the only PID used. ORCID is used by 25.6% (51 journals). Other PIDs are used only sporadically.

Table 13. Persistent identifiers used by the surveyed journals

PIDs	# journals	%
Crossref DOI	80	40.2%
Crossref DOI, ORCID	28	14.1%
Other DOI	14	7.0%
ORCID	10	5.0%
Other DOI, ORCID	7	3.5%
DataCite DOI	4	2.0%
Other combinations	7	3.5%
None	49	24.6%

Table 14. The use of persistent identifiers

PID	# journals	# journals using only this PID
Crossref DOI	113	80
DataCiteDOI	7	4
Other DOI	22	14
ORCID	51	10
URN	1	0
ARK	2	0

3.5 Visibility and discoverability (including indexation)

More than half of the respondents (106; 53.3%) have said that their journals are indexed in AJOL and half of them are discoverable via Google Scholar. Those indexed in the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) account for nearly one-third (65; 32.7%), while the share of those indexed in the Web of Science and Scopus is considerably smaller – 10.1% and 13.1%, respectively. The analysis of free-text responses reveals a long tail of indexing venues relevant in the African context and throws light on national (Portail des Revues Scientifiques Marocaines) and continental platforms (e.g. the South African journal platform [Sabinet African Journals](#)). It is reasonable to assume that many more surveyed journals are indexed by these services but did not mention it in the survey. Therefore, the data presented in the table are merely illustrative.

⁴ 'AJOL DOI' mentioned by a number of respondents has been added to the CrossRef DOI group in this analysis.

Table 15. The presence of the surveyed journals in databases / indexing services

Journal	# journals indexed	%
AJOL	106	53.3%
Google Scholar	101	50.8%
DOAJ	65	32.7%
Google	59	29.6%
Scopus	26	13.1%
WorldCat	21	10.6%
Web of Science	20	10.1%
SciELO	12	6.0%
BASE	11	5.5%
PubMedCentral	10	5.0%
OpenAIRE	8	4.0%
EBSCO	7	3.5%
Portail des Revues Scientifiques Marocaines (IMIST-CNRST)	7	3.5%
Algerian Scientific Journal Platform	6	3.0%
CORE	6	3.0%
Medline	4	2.0%
ARCIF	4	2.0%
ProQuest	4	2.0%
Sabinet African Journals	4	2.0%
Mirabel	3	1.5%
Ulrichs Web	3	1.5%
Not indexed	17	8.5%

Note: The percentages in the table are calculated with respect to the total number of respondents. The sum of the numbers in the table is greater than 100% because many journals are indexed in multiple databases/services. The table includes coded free-text responses.

Although the majority of journals are indexed or merely discoverable in multiple databases or services, the number of those indexed with only one indexing service is not insignificant (82; 41.2%; see table below), and in most cases this single service is usually AJOL.

Table 16. Journals indexed in only one database / indexing service

Database / indexing service	# journals
AJOL	38
DOAJ	5
Google Scholar	18
Google	4
WorldCat	17
Total	82

The most common challenges faced by journals when applying for indexing include satisfying the technical criteria and membership fees (42; 21.11%), followed by satisfying the metadata requirements (34; 17.1%) and non-technical participation criteria (30; 15.1%). The language used in the application process does not seem to be a major issue.

Although insufficiently detailed, free-text responses provide more information about the challenging non-technical requirements: some journals are rejected because of their local, i.e. African focus, low citation rates in citation databases, authors coming from limited geographic areas and endogeneity (too many papers authored by editorial board members or the reviewers working for the journal). A few respondents also mentioned the unresponsiveness of the indexing services, who have never provided feedback about their applications.

Table 17. Challenges faced by journals applying for indexing in databases / indexing services

Challenges	# journals	%
Satisfying the non-technical participation criteria	30	15.1%
Satisfying the technical participation criteria	42	21.1%
Satisfying the metadata requirements	34	17.1%
Paying for membership, annual or one time	42	21.1%
Paying for recurring charges, for example, monthly fees	31	15.6%
The language of the communications/requirements/paperwork is only in English	7	3.5%
The language of the communications/requirements/paperwork is another language that is hard to understand	5	2.5%
The service/its requirements/its paperwork are too technical	13	6.5%

3.6 Challenges, funding needs and support required to make Diamond OA journals more sustainable

Financial constraints are by far the most pressing challenge that affects three-quarters (149; 74.87%) of the respondents, while nearly half of them (90; 45.2%) are struggling with the lack of human resources. Infrastructure-related and administrative challenges affect more than 30% of the respondents.

Table 18. Challenges faced by Diamond OA journals

Challenges	# journals	%
Financial constraints	149	74.9%
Administrative constraints	64	32.2%
Lack of human resources	90	45.2%
Lack of expertise	51	25.6%
Technical limitations of existing infrastructure	66	33.2%

Challenges	# journals	%
Providing adequate resources for the infrastructure and services	60	30.2%
Issuing persistent identifiers	35	17.6%
Trying to achieve and maintain interoperability with other services and systems	46	23.1%
Archiving, backing up or preserving content and software	48	24.1%

Note: The percentages in the table are calculated with respect to the total number of respondents. The sum of the numbers in the table is greater than 100% because the respondents could choose multiple options.

Free-text responses highlight additional challenges, such as recruiting reviewers and the slow pace of their work, low submission rates, registration in journal databases, marketing, geographic diversity of authors, but also the fact that African journals are expected to adopt ethical principles and guidelines coming from the West, though these are not necessarily relevant in the African context.

3.6.1 Unmet funding needs

Editorial quality challenges:

- “Additional human resources” / “It would help if we had more help on editing to ensure consistency (e.g. are all the references in the right format). The Editors just don't have time to do all the editing work.”
- “Author development support.”
- “Consistent publication, technical and editorial software acquisition, journal website development and maintenance, acquiring persistent identifiers, indexing”
- “Continuing Editorial Staff Training: Providing ongoing training for editorial staff to stay informed about best editorial practices, technological advancements, and changes in publishing standards.” / “Fund for training on publication and editorial tasks” / “Funds for training for staff, buy license for a robust plagiarism checking software license and for engaging copyediting services” / Funding for training editorial staff. / “Funds to train the editorial team.” / “Training needs for younger editors, and funds for reviewers' compensation.” / “Training and financing.”
- “Copyediting, production” / “Paying for the services of copy-editors and editors at the writing unit” / “Paying services rendered to the journal such as copy editing etc.” / “Copyediting, typesetting and printing costs” / “Funds for proofreading.”
- “Ensure the publication of quality manuscripts from all countries (especially from Africa)”
- “Editorial collaboration.”
- “Financial constraints for peer review process, management and administration of the journal.”
- “Finding reviewers” / “In my country, it is difficult to get reviewers voluntarily. Some kind of monetary incentive is needed” / “Support for Reviewers: Encouraging reviewer participation by offering incentives, training, or compensation for the time dedicated to

evaluations.” / “No remuneration/motivation for reviewers, editorial staff, and board members. Lack of resources/infrastructure for journal-related activities” / “Paying reviewers” / “Funds to cater for reviewers.”

- “Fund for paying incentives for personnel” / “Incentives for editors” / “Incentives for the Editorial team” / “Incentive matters at the current condition.” / “Incentive for Editors. Reviewers. Different trainings.”
- “Labor and facility.”
- “Lack of funds to reward our editors, reviewers and administrators, in the form of honorarium or financial expenses. Lack of funds to organize meetings (i.e., annual editorial board meeting), advertize the journal, and produce hard or print-copies of the journal to increase its readability.” / “Funding to support all aspects of the journal management processes” / “Funding to pay editorial staff who usually work as volunteers. Our current funding only supports the main publishing costs.” / “Employing personnel to assist in the journal's activities.” / “To recruit journal administrators/staff” / “Paying an honorarium to the Editor-in-Chief” / “Honoraria for editorial team” / “Long-term funding for editorial assistant” / “A dedicated Editorial assistant / manager” / “Funding for additional permanent editorial and administration staff” / “Having a part-time administrator who can deal with admin and such matters.” / “Payments for better quality editorial staff” / “Journal administrator; Copy editors and formatter / We are desperate to get funding for our volunteers interns” / “Funds to support editors and journal support teams.” / “The staff (journal manager, copyeditor and typesetter) are underpaid for the service they provide. The goal is to increase their salaries to make the job worthwhile for them.”
- “Need for funding English editing.”
- “Operational Costs: Editorial management: Hiring and supporting qualified editors and editorial staff requires dedicated funding. Production and publishing: Costs associated with typesetting, copyediting, layout, and online platform maintenance can be substantial.”
- “Our journal currently lacks sufficient funding to support various operational aspects, including: Editorial tasks such as manuscript handling, peer review management, and editorial board management. Publication costs including typesetting, copyediting, and proofreading. Development and implementation of initiatives to enhance journal quality and compliance with industry standards.”
- “Software for checking plagiarism.”
- “To hire permanent staff.”
- “We need a dedicated and trained administrative staff.”
- “We do not have funding to publish special editions”

Administrative constraints, funding, collaboration and partnerships:

- “Admin budget.”
- “Administrative constraints leave little room for additional funds.”
- “Donations and support from other national and international institutions”
- “Finding stable funding sources.”
- “Funding for publishing services. Funding for administrative costs. Funding for capacity development and community of practice. Funding for printing and distribution.”

- “Funding to provide space for permanent staff, office equipment, etc.”
- High operating costs (“costs related to editorial management, online publishing, and other operational expenses”).
- “Lack of some core human resources to manage the day-to-day routines of the journal. Currently, all the “staff” are volunteers. We also need funding to subscribe to editorial tools such as AI plagiarism checkers.”
- “Logistical support, incentives for permanent and temporary staff.”
- Long term partnerships: “to find a serious and reliable partner.”
- “More human resources; Dedicated section, Dedicated staff”
- “Our ideal is to have the journal be financially independent from our institution. Since we are a private institution, we are solely funded by tuition fees. This places strain on the entire institution.”
- “Our financing needs are the need to have a sufficient number of employees and an administrative structure with sustainable financing equal to or exceeding \$50,000 annually.”
- “Payments for working staff.”
- “Payment for organizing editorial staff meetings.”
- “Providing OA is expensive, and finding sustainable funding is a real challenge. To address this, we need to seek grants for open access funding, collaborate with institutional partners, and explore mixed models to balance costs.”
- “Research funding is limited on a year by year basis.”
- “The journal hopes for a wide base of supporters who can donate minimal amounts regularly to keep the journal free for all.”
- “The main challenge is to find sources of funding to ensure free submissions and OA: Possible Solutions: Obtain funding from academic institutions, governments, and philanthropic organizations dedicated to supporting OA; use open-source publishing platforms and tools to reduce the costs associated with digital publishing; participate in or initiate collaborative projects with other journals or institutions to develop shared technological solutions.”
- “We need to secure funding to maintain Diamond OA to pay the publisher costs.”
- “We need to streamline business processes, explore more efficient technologies, and negotiate with suppliers to reduce costs.”

Technology challenges:

- “Archiving platforms” / “The journal would benefit from additional funding for external permanent archiving.”
- Back up, PIDs, platform maintenance.
- “Covering annual OJS hosting fees and covering our annual production costs.” / “Financial support to cover our OJS hosting fees -- ideally three to five years -- would be most helpful. In addition, support to cover our journal production costs for three to five years would also ensure the sustainability of the journal.”
- “Infrastructure and human resources.”
- “In-house IT support to automate manual processes not functioning or customizable in open-source systems. More funding for appointing human capacity to keep up with

increasing demands and development needs, especially in non-core areas such as marketing and communication functions and in developmental role journal plays with inexperienced or untrained authors.”

- “Most of our IT equipment (Computers, Printers, Scanners, Copiers, routers, Monitors, Projectors, screens, server systems, Hard disks, ...) are beyond recommended end-of-life cycles, therefore funds are needed for their renewal.”
- “Mostly on technical aspects (expertise).”
- Need for having an online submission system.
- “OJS maintenance, lthenticate.”
- “Payment for construction of a journal website.”
- “Platform subscription, language editing, page production.”
- “Production costs, acquiring requisite infrastructure” / “Production costs of the journal articles. The work is done by librarians.”
- “Publishing software and an expert in the same.”
- “Resources for infrastructure and services”.
- “Salary of the personnel, database hosting, online journal management system fee to get access to more automated systems.”
- Software
- “Subscription fees for a hosting platform. Subscription fee for domain name. Cost of production. Salary for administrative staff.”
- “Technical and aesthetic issues are more dominant which can only be resolved through professional payment.”
- “Technological Development: Investing in modern online platforms, efficient editorial management systems, and technological solutions to enhance the experience of authors, reviewers, and readers.” / “Technical infrastructure for hosting the journal website and managing submissions.”
- “The cost to train the editorial office, purchase Crossref services and engage an OJS specialist.”
- “The journal is hosted by the University Press, to whom we must pay an annual hosting fee. In addition, the administrative burden of running the journal, including language editing and typesetting, is increasing significantly, meaning that more of this work needs to be outsourced, requiring additional funding.”
- “To develop a website that performs most of the editorial functions that are presently being done manually.”
- “We need to obtain funding for hosting and typesetting costs.”
- “We need servers to fully automate our submission system and store files.”
- “We require funding for subscription to host our journal independently. We are hamstrung by the lack of finances for technical support and editorial support as well as for dedicated employed personnel.”
- “Well-functioning online content management systems are too expensive, but reliance on open-source means limited and inadequate functionality, long delays and inadequate support in implementing latest best practice for authors, indexes and journal staff. Meaning tedious manual processes to fill in gaps to compete with well-resourced journals and well-functioning online systems.”

Visibility and indexation challenges:

- “All fees to pay to recognized OA organizations to improve our reputation” / “Membership subscription in some organizations e.g. COPE.”
- “Insufficient citations.”
- “Finding diversified and sustainable sources of funding is often crucial to ensure the long-term financial viability of our journal. Financial needs faced by our scientific journal that may sometimes go unmet include:
 - Promotion and Marketing Expenses: To increase the visibility of the journal, attract authors, and expand the reader base, funds may be required for online promotion activities, advertising campaigns, or participation in academic conferences.
 - Conference and Event Expenses: Organizing conferences, workshops, or other academic events to promote the journal and create networking opportunities.
 - Revenue Diversification: Exploring alternative revenue sources, such as partnerships with institutions, research grants, or journal memberships.
 - Social Responsibility Initiatives: Financing social responsibility projects, such as education programs, awareness initiatives, or the translation of articles for increased international reach.”
- “Get more international visibility”
- Increased competition: “Competition with other journals to attract quality authors can create financial pressures...We must highlight the distinctive advantages of our journal, invest in online visibility, and collaborate with partners to expand our audience.”
- “Marketing and promotion activities to increase visibility and attract submissions.” / “Promotion of the journal” / “additional registrations of the journal to other platforms that facilitate promotion” / “Marketing and promotion: Increasing the journal's visibility and attracting high-quality submissions necessitates promotional efforts that require resources.” / “Funds to market the journal globally.”
- “Indexing in reputable indexers” / “We would like to be indexed in AJOL.” / “Funds to support wide journal indexing”

Interoperability challenges:

- Lack of DOIs: “Our establishment cannot pay in foreign currency for a DOI, and has no right to finance this type of activity, which does not exist in the expense code” / Payments of article identifiers / Funds to support annual subscriptions for DOIs / “Subscription and registration for Persistent identifiers. Inadequate human expertise on indexing, metadata harvesting tools. Inadequate Infrastructure to fully support online accessibility, visibility and findability.”

Printing costs:

- Money for printing in hard copies / Print copies.

Changes in the publishing landscape and the need to stay informed of trends:

- “Rapid changes in publishing trends make it difficult to navigate the research landscape. To do this, we must stay informed of trends, be flexible in our model, and anticipate changes to be able to adapt quickly.”

3.6.2 What kind of support would make Diamond OA journals more sustainable

Human resources support:

- “1–2 Permanent working staff for the journal (1 IT, 1 administrative).”
- “A dedicated Editorial assistant / manager, and a three-year funding cycle”
- “A new crop of young enthusiastic editors and reviewers.”
- “Additional funding for permanent editorial and administration staff, and finding persons with the required skills for the job.”
- “Additional human resources”
- “Administrative support / “Provision of logistical support to facilitate effective operations” / “Support to establish a dedicated secretariat to manage the Journal”
- “An annual fund to contribute to staff costs”
- “Assisting with production costs and incentives for those working with the journal.”
- “Being freed up more from our primary lecturing workloads and postgraduate supervision, to spend more time on the journal in terms of management etc.”
- “Encouraging our editors.”
- “Ensuring that we have teams which can serve at all stages.”
- “Establishing full time editors, such as a managing editor. This will help in the process of getting indexed in renown databases.”
- “Expansion of our editorial board.”
- “Expertise.”
- “Financial, staff, expertise.”
- “Financial, Administrative, Marketing” / “Financial and managerial”
- “Financial support and building office so as to have special office for running journal”
- “Financial support for peer review process, management and administration of the journal”
- “Funding and establishing international linkages with resource persons to serve as reviewers for manuscripts”
- “Having a part-time administrator who can deal with admin and such matters.”
- “Institutional Collaborations: Establishing partnerships with academic institutions, research organizations, or government agencies can provide financial support, human resources, and increased visibility.”
- “Long-term funding for editorial assistant.”
- “Our journal requires expenses to pay the salaries of our staff” / “We need sponsorship or grant to recruit workers” / “Financial compensation for journal bodies” / “Staff support” / “Having more experts as associate editors. This could be possible if they can be compensated.” / “Staffing” / “Professional Payment to the Editor-in-Chief and Editorial Members” / “Honorarium to our editorial staff, cost of advertising and printing the journals

for dissemination. / “Grants to employ people or give allowances personnel the journal engages” / “Qualified journal administrative staff” / “Journal Manager/Publishing Assistant Salaries” / “Dedicated editor.”

- “Proofreading services.”
- “Recruitment of committed editorial board members and peer reviewers.”
- “Remuneration for reviewers”
- “Some additional financial support to hire additional editing and to take some of the burden off of the parent organization.”
- The journal costs include hosting fee and language editing costs. However, the journal “relies on the editor or a volunteer handling the admin of managing the review process. At present, the editor is supported by an admin assistant who supports this. Future editors may not enjoy such support. As such, support with these items (hosting, language editing, typesetting and administration) would contribute to the sustainability of the journal.”
- “The support should be financial in the range of about \$30,000, with administrative, technical, and training support provided.”

Technical support and facilities, ensuring interoperability:

- “A website that performs more editorial functions.”
- “Anti-plagiarism software, employment of permanent technical/office staff, very good laptop and desktop systems” / Funding for plagiarism checking tools (e.g. iThenticate subscription).
- Archiving content.
- “Acquisition of persistent identifiers like DOI” / Funding to cover the costs of DOIs (member fees, content registration fees and similarity checks fees) / “ Support to acquire the DOI” / “Issuing of persistent identifiers” / “Financial support on registration to Persistent Identifiers providers.”
- “Effective online publishing infrastructure.” / “Electronic Publishing system with flows from submission to final decision” / “Funding and technical support for the development of a journal management system.” / “Funding for upgrading the submission and production system” / OJS installation / “Funding in order to implement the OJS platform.” / Software adaptation / “Software (OJS) and technical expert of the same for publishing and management of the Journal.”
- “Improve readability of the journal.”
- “Office and its equipment”, “equipment.”
- “Our print and online journal was unable to publish its print version for the past three years due to the exponentially rising printing costs as a result of the country's rising inflation. At the same, the editorial office lacks logistics like laptops and hard drives that are vital for conducting the day-to-day activities of the journal.”
- Processing cost fund (online submission system, funding language editing, and editorial meeting costs).
- “Providing adequate resources for the infrastructure and services, and capacity building for the editorial mainly support on online publishing workflows, assign unique persistent

identifiers, and journal database indexation; technical support to create specialized series are the supports that would make the journal more sustainable.”

- Stable connectivity / Constant internet access.
- Supporting costs of licenses and journal management software and programs.
- “Supporting the development or adoption of open-source tools for editorial management, plagiarism detection, and other needs.”
- “Technical expert in submission system, assigning DOI and joining WoS and Scopus”
- “Technical support” / “Funds to pay for the technical IT services.”
- Website hosting costs – “to get better in hosting our journal website” / “Support for hosting the journal online” / “We need sponsorship to improve our website” and “to improve the journal.”
- “We need IT facilities like laptops, subsidized internet, DOI, incentive for Editorial Board members.”
- “We need your technical support in developing a good portal infrastructure and of course, we need our portal more discoverable, therefore, we need your support in indexing our portal in more reputable databases.” / “Technical assistance” / “Infrastructural support”. / Technical support on indexing, metadata harvesting tools and communication and marketing.

Visibility and indexation:

- “Advertising fees to promote the journal” / “costs of advertising”.
- “Developing a communication strategy to promote the journal.”
- “We absolutely must give a helping hand to African scientific journals and help them index in major databases to enable African researchers to publish in Africa.” / “securing indexing of the journal” / “Help in preparation for indexation.” / “International indexing with emphasis on Scopus” / “Support for Indexing would go a long way to support sustainability for the Journal” / “Indexing such as with DOAJ and Web of Science/Scopus” / “We would like to be indexed to databases such as AJOL.” / “Further indexing” / “Indexing into more databases.” / “Create an African scientific journal database. Developing an African indexing system” / “International visibility, indexation, manuscript submission system, African indexing, support for authors” / “Quality has been improving steadily, and the major constraint is recognition and wider dissemination rather than finances. The organizations that provide critical evaluation (such as the Web of Science or JPPS) are very slow in evaluating the quality of journals.”
- “More acknowledgment from international organizations to have more visibility and more citations to compete with big publishers.”
- “More visibility of our journal.”

Advocacy for Diamond OA publishing support:

- “A management understanding of the publishing, complexities of managing a journal and an appreciation of the value of an accredited journal” / “Continued institutional support for the public value of academic publishing.” / “Mainstream university funding for ongoing sustainability.”

- “Implementing mechanisms for individual or institutional donations, potentially through targeted campaigns or partnerships with organizations with similar goals.”

Knowledge sharing and support:

- “Access to professional resources.”
- “Capacity building on the journal publishing process, legal administration processes, best practices to the journal staff and editorial teams.”
- “Continuing Education: Supporting ongoing training for editorial staff to stay current on best editorial practices, technological trends, and developments in the publishing field. Promotion of Social Responsibility: Emphasizing social responsibility initiatives, such as promoting diversity and inclusion, educational programs, or actions aimed at making research more accessible to a broader audience. Revenue Diversification Strategies: Exploring additional means of generating income, such as partnerships with businesses, philanthropic donations, or the creation of related services (workshops, training, etc.).”
- “Development of a business model. Collaborative projects” / “Need of Training or guidance to develop a business plan that will work under the constraints of a Diamond OA model.”
- “For the journal to stay abreast of developments in scholarly publishing and be able to adapt and innovate to the changing environments they need to explore new technologies, most of which are situated in Europe or the USA, which in essence makes it impossibly expensive for us to partake of. It would be wonderful if these corporations could account for the exchange rate and adapt their business models for our market. Institutional support from research institutions or funding bodies using grants or subsidies to particularly support the publication of research in Global South OA journals.”
- “Funding to attend workshops and symposia.”
- Training / funds for training workshops / Supporting training / “Training on best practices” / “Training and capacity building for staff to ensure quality publication” / “Training in OJS management” / “Training of journal editorial board.” / “Training and capacity building: Participating in programs or workshops that provide skills and knowledge in OA publishing practices and technologies.” / Ongoing training / “Continuous training of the Editorial Board, Incentives for the Editorial board, and co-hosting host Conferences periodically” / “Training facilities on how to best use the publication Platform OJS. Help on development of journal guides and best practices. Workshops on academic writing and peer review process.”, / training on “Indexing process. Technical training in journal management. Use of electronic journal management systems. Updating editorial policy.” / “Training and retraining, mentoring and collaboration with established journals, indexing support”.

4. Continental, national and institutional platforms for Diamond OA journals

4.1 General features: Scope, disciplines and inclusion criteria

We would like to thank 21 institutional, national and continental platforms that host Diamond OA journals from nine countries: Algeria, Ethiopia, Ghana, Kenya, Nigeria, South Africa, Tunisia, Uganda and Zambia who contributed to the consultations. Most responses came from South Africa.

The survey responses came from continental platforms: African-wide portal for African Scholarship from African universities and AJOL – an African platform for all qualifying, African-published research journals; national platforms – aggregation portal on behalf of South African and African journals, SciELO South Africa and Khulisa Journals that hosts SciELO SA approved journals; institutional journals platforms and a commercial medical publisher that collaborates with scholarly societies and combines its own platform with journal hosting provided by Sabinet. Some individual journals also responded as disciplinary platforms, but these responses were eventually excluded from the analysis. Responses also show that institutional repositories play a role in Diamond OA publishing in Africa, e.g. in University of Zambia.

Table 19. The distribution of the platform survey responses by country

Country	# responses
Ethiopia	1
Kenya	1
Nigeria	1
South Africa	17
Zambia	1
Total	21

Platform scope

The majority of platforms (15 of 21) covered by the survey are institutional in scope, though some also serve as disciplinary and national platforms. Three continental platforms responded to the survey.⁵

Figure 13. The scope of the surveyed platforms

Platforms differ in size measured by the number of hosted journals (ten platforms host one to five journals; seven – 21–30 journals, one – 100–200 journals, while one hosts more than 500 journals)⁷ and the number of published articles (seven have up to 1,000 articles, six – 1,000–5,000, two – 5,000–10,000, two – 10,000–50,000, and two – 100,000–500,000 articles)⁸. While nine platforms host only Diamond OA journals, others also host journals that charge author fees. Altogether, the surveyed platforms host 302 Diamond OA journals.

The largest continental platform and the project partner AJOL currently has 130 Diamond OA journals and there were 4,088 articles added to those journals in 2023 (out of the total number of articles of 17,454 added to the platform last year).

⁵ Free-text data were coded and included in the table. The survey data were cross-checked and aligned with the information from the country report for South Africa.

⁶ The sum is greater than the total number of platforms because some belong to multiple types.

⁷ One response could not be verified.

⁸ Two responses could not be verified.

Disciplines

All platforms, except one, which is dedicated to medical sciences, cover multiple disciplines. One portal focuses on STEM only, while three are oriented solely towards SSH. All the other platforms cover a variety of disciplines, though SSH seems to be better represented.

Table 20. The disciplinary coverage of the surveyed platforms

Disciplines	# or platforms
Multidisciplinary	18
Natural sciences	7
Engineering and technology	6
Medical and health sciences	10
Agricultural sciences	5
Social sciences	11
Humanities	11
Non-academic	3

Inclusion criteria

Platforms have different inclusion criteria. It is noteworthy that none of them use bibliometric criteria.

Table 21. Inclusion criteria used by the surveyed platforms

Inclusion criteria	# platforms
Institutional, national or disciplinary affiliation	12
Compliance with editorial quality criteria	13
Only OA journals are accepted	3
Only Diamond OA journals are accepted	2

Other responses include:

- Compliance with current best practice, e.g. DOIs, ORCIDs, detailed affiliations of authors, etc.
- No
- Only African universities and institutes can publish on APOS.
- Only SciELO SA approved journals are considered for inclusion. All SciELO SA journals were subjected to peer-review evaluation.
- We have a rigorous and very comprehensive assessment process for applicant and ongoing journals.

4.2 Personnel, incentives, funding, institutional support, sustainability and collaborations

Number of people working for a platform

In most cases, platforms are run by fairly small teams: ten platforms have two to five people, five have only one staff member, two five to ten and one has 20 people. Only one platform has more than 30 people, while two have no staff.

How a platform's personnel work

The majority (15) of the respondents have a dedicated unit responsible for the platform with the employed personnel (fully or partially employed to work for the portal). Six platforms do not have a dedicated unit, but the personnel are employed by the institution and are sharing their time between the platform and other tasks. One respondent mentioned using some volunteer work.

Incentives for personnel

In most cases (20) there are no incentives for staff working on the platforms. Only one platform provides some incentives and this is small monetary support for journal editors (~ 23 USD per month for editors to manage the journal activity by the Ministry of Education; and a quarterly bonus).

Funding

Though funding varies, it is noteworthy that the majority (seven out of eight) of those relying on fixed and permanent subsidies from the host institution are institutional platforms. Those relying on periodically negotiated subsidies from the host institution include three institutional and two national platforms.

Table 22. Funding sources

Funding sources	# platforms
Fixed and permanent subsidy from the host organization	8
Periodically negotiated subsidy from the host organization	5
Time-limited grants or subsidies, either private or public from outside the host organization	2
Collective funding (e.g. crowdfunding, membership fees, etc.)	1
Print sales (e.g. print on demand)	1
Other	9

Other responses include:

- All journals pay an annual journal hosting fee; journals budget forms part of the Open Science budget, with Department of Science and Innovation funding;
- Article processing charges (when the portal hosts fee-based journals together with Diamond OA journals);
- It's part of University's operations budget;

- The institution has allocated funds for the annual subscription;
- The portal supports one of the functions of the library (library as publisher). Tasks performed are included in general duties.

Stability of funding sources based on the last three years

Although the stability of these funding sources also varies, the majority of the respondents see their funding sources as either stable or very stable.

Table 23. The stability of funding sources

Funding stability	# platforms
Very stable	6
Stable	7
Neither stable or unstable	2
Unstable	2
Very unstable	3
Don't know	1
Total	21

Annual approved budget

The majority of platforms (13) do not have an annual approved budget. However, two institutional platforms who do not have a budget have also said that the maintenance of the platform is included in the institutional budget and they consider their funding stable.

In-kind support provided by platform's host organizations

Platforms' host organizations provide facilities and premises, salaries, general and service-specific IT services. Most platforms rely on multiple types of support.

Table 24. In-kind support provided by host organizations

Type of support	# platforms
Facilities and premises	12
Human Resource management, general financial and legal services	9
General IT services (email, hardware, Internet, etc)	13
Service-specific IT services (publishing platform/website, tools, etc)	9
Salaries of permanent staff	17
Salaries of temporary staff	1
N/A	2

Sustainability planning

Less than half (ten) respondents have a platform sustainability plan.

Challenges

Financial and human resources are the main challenges faced.

Table 25. Challenges faced by journal platforms

Challenge	# platforms
Financial constraints	10
Administrative constraints	4
Lack of human resources	13
Lack of expertise	4
Technical limitations of existing infrastructure	4
Providing adequate resources for the infrastructure and services	7
Issuing persistent identifiers	1
Trying to achieve and maintain interoperability with other services and systems	4
Archiving, backing up or preserving content and software	6
Keeping up with similar services	2

One respondent mentioned that “AJOL is considered by DOAJ as a permanent archival service. Similar service is Redalyc”.

Collaborations

Platforms are open to different types of collaborations. Training, production services and communication services are most frequently mentioned as areas of potential collaboration.

Table 26. Potential areas of collaboration

Collaboration areas	# platforms
Production services (copy-editing, proofreading, typesetting, metadata, etc.)	10
IT services (submission system, platform, website, etc.)	9
Communication services (marketing/dissemination, social media, etc.)	10
Administrative, legal and financial services (contracts, accounting, documentation, etc.)	4
Training, support and/or advice on publishing policies and best practice	11
None	2
Don't know	1

One respondent wrote that they “already collaborate in order to reduce and absorb costs of DOIs. We are looking into XML.”

4.3 Technical service efficiency

In most cases the platform's technical infrastructure is maintained and updated in-house.

Table 27. Maintaining and updating a platform's technical infrastructure

Infrastructure	# platforms
In-house by an IT department/personnel	12
In-house by a dedicated publishing department (e.g. the library)	5
In-house across different departments	3
Partially outsourced	3
Mainly outsourced	5
Fully outsourced	4

"We have been working with 2 external tech contractors for the past 15 years. Only Free and Open Source software is used." is one of the other responses.

In most cases (16) the platforms support all publishing workflows online. One platform does not support publishing workflows as it is primarily an aggregator. The remaining platforms (three) support some publishing workflows online.

OJS is the most commonly used software. It is used by 18 platforms. One platform uses DSpace. Other solutions include Atypon and theSciELO e-publishing methodology (open source).

Most platforms (20) assign unique persistent identifiers, with Crossref DOI being the most popular. It is used by 18 platforms, 10 of which also use ORCIDs.

Other responses include:

- It is up to individual journals to add other persistent identifiers. ORCID is highly recommended in the assessment framework.
- ROR.

The majority (12) of the platforms provide long term preservation options. Institutional platforms prevail among those who don't.

4.4 Visibility and discoverability, including indexation

Most platforms are indexed in Google Scholar (16).

Table 28. Databases/services indexing journals from the surveyed platforms

Indexing service	# platforms
BASE	3
CORE	2
Google	13

Indexing service	# platforms
Google Scholar	16
OpenAIRE	1
SciELO SA	6
WorldCat	4
Not indexed	1
Other	5

Other responses include:

- DOAJ
- Sabinet
- Scopus
- Sherpa Romeo
- WoS

Most platforms (16) also provide support to journals that would like to get indexed.

It seems that most platforms are able to deal with indexing challenges. Some challenges include satisfying the non-technical (four respondents) and technical (four respondents) participation criteria. No platforms mentioned language issues.

Table 29. Challenges related to indexing in databases / indexing services

Indexing challenges	# platforms
Satisfying the non-technical participation criteria	4
Satisfying the technical participation criteria	4
Satisfying the metadata requirements	1
Paying for membership, annual or one time	2
Paying for recurring charges, for example, monthly fees	1
The language of the communications/requirements/paperwork is only in English	0
The language of the communications/requirements/paperwork is another language that is hard to understand	0
The service/its requirements/its paperwork are too technical	1

Some other responses include:

- It is the responsibility of individual journals to apply for inclusion.
- Minimal number of articles edited per year.

4.5 Financial sustainability challenges and solutions

Respondents listed the following financial sustainability challenges and possible solutions:

- “As mentioned earlier, funding is so unstable. Sometimes we have some little resources other times we have none. Since the host organization is a public entity, if the government doesn't release funds, the functioning of the journal is greatly affected. Lobbying for increased budget from top management.”
- “Buy in from the publisher”
- “Currently, our journals are part of the Open Access Policy of the university and library as publisher is a service that is part of the Libraries service model.”
- “Dedicated funding from the institution.”
- “Different financial administration strategies of each of the participating institutional journals. Lack of standalone budget for the project. Solution: Adequate separate budget and funding should be available to the project either from the institution or funding organizations. This can also help transit the journals to Diamond OA.”
- “Due to the high cost and financial difficulties and inability to get constant support, it is looking difficult. This can be addressed if we have committed and dedicated annual support”
- “Editorial, copy editing, peer reviewing papers.”
- “Fundraising could be increased, focusing on book series for specific funders.”
- “Having the internal skills to manage the portal and to provide training and assistance to a journal editorial team to set-up their journal processes.”
- “In the past, it has been challenging to attract donor support for African research sharing, but the need for this is gaining awareness. We are now in a better funding situation regarding additional donor partners, and an extra strategy for library crowd-funding just starting off, but for long term full financial sustainability, African governments regionally should contribute our core costs, as we are a regional public service and good.”
- “Limitations to the functionality of the platform, not as user friendly and intuitive as one would like.”
- “Our main challenges are related to funding to get our consultants to meet in order to develop a strategic plan that will facilitate the consistent execution of the journal's editorial tasks, and to assure adherence to globally recognized quality standards in editorial work and publishing.”
- “The costs for hosting the platform is increasing annually and we have to ensure that we add more journals or that we charge the current journals more for hosting their journals.”
- “The financial constraints are not portal-related, as the Library funds the portal's hosting as part of our Digital Commons support. The challenges are instead related to OA policy at the journal level. One of the identified challenges is COPE membership funding to strengthen the standing of the journal hosting service.”
- “The launch of an OJS platform is an ongoing project. We have engaged a service company specializing in website development. In order to ensure the longevity of the Journal website and maintain free access for readers and authors, we are considering diversifying our income sources by exploring alternative revenue streams, such as sponsorships, partnerships, or hosting events.”

- “The main challenge is funding. It can be addressed by sourcing additional funding.”
- “The only challenge is funding the DOIs. Thank god, AJOL does it.”
- “The portal's financial sustainability will become a challenge, if it is moved from the university to a neutral space, like one of the Research and Education Networks, as they may want to charge hosting fees. The only way these fees can be paid, i.e., to keep the Diamond OA model, will be for funders to pay these fees. Further, the other challenge for financial sustainability is the ability to maintain the Diamond OA model, as some African institutions insist on paying their peer reviewers a nominal fee and then want to recoup the money through APCs.”
- “The portal is outsourced. Although it's a library project, funding is not guaranteed. It is dependent upon the University budgets and Library subscriptions.”
- “We are a low profile platform. More awareness should be created on the important role it plays in terms of e-workflow.”
- “We are funded with 3-year grants. These grants have been renewed many times. But we never know as we get to the end of the grant whether the grant will be renewed.”
- “We have no dedicated budget for expenditure as costs vary. The software is Open Source.”
- “We lack the ability to create and carry out workable medium-term financial plans that would enable us to support the regular completion of the activities including necessary developmental components for upholding internationally acknowledged publishing quality standards.”
- “We used to be able to sell advertising in the medical field. This is no longer the case.”

4.6 Unmet funding needs

The following unmet funding needs were mentioned:

- “Awareness creation to increase visibility”
- “Digitizing publishing workflows”
- “Extra staff.”
- “Fund for training on publication and editorial tasks”
- “Fund for paying incentives for portal personnel”
- “Funding, poor infrastructure, technical limitation”
- “Lack of funds to reward our editors, reviewers and administrators, in the form of honorarium or financial expenses.”
- “Long-term guarantee of funding. Currently we receive 3 year-funding every 3 years.”
- “OJS plugins to other services are sometimes lacking.”
- “Online hosting cost”
- “Providing layout templates for all the journals.”
- “Publication and online infrastructure cost”
- “Registration of ISSNs”
- “ScriPris, SciProof and OMP.”
- “Securing core organizational funding from 2025 to 2030 (underway). Expansion of staff members to keep up with current journal partner applications, assessments, training and support. Expansion of staff members to meet the demand of various regional and

international project collaborations. Expansion of staff members to meet other service requests, and expand the technical publishing services offered by us, including XML. We also need funding support for the development of an African languages API, and translation of the main website into other languages. Funds for Communications and Marketing in order to publicize our massive achievements (a wealth of statistics and experience that need to be written up and shared) and fully launch a new income strategy.”

- “Skilled human resources to assist editorial teams of Journals. Currently no journal is running its full process on OJS. It is only copies of past issues that are published on the OJS. The OJS responsibility moved to a new section in 2024 and we are in the process of assisting an in-house journal to get DHET accreditation over the next few years and the journal editorial team will use OJS for this purpose.”
- “Some journals on the platform struggle to find funding to make their journals sustainable”
- “Staff recruitment/motivation”
- “Staffing, infrastructure maintenance”
- “Sustainability”
- “There needs to be infrastructural developments like being able to include a search facility across all African universities.”
- “To grow the pool of human capacity to support retrospective digitization processes for journals.”
- “We are a private organization and work with commercial models. But we would also assist publishers/journals to get their archives indexed on our platform but funding is lacking there because we cannot sustain all the costs.”

4.7 What kind of support would make platforms more sustainable

The following support will be appreciated:

- “Centralize and fund editorial processes that provide professional services to all journal editorial boards. This is the main reason journal editors are not wanting to move away from commercial journal publishers. I would rather have all universities provide funding for a centralized service. but this will also require a national mandate on OA publishing from government bodies.”
- “Create more awareness on Diamond OA and maybe provide guidelines on how individual OA journals can become financially independent from APCs.”
- “Financial and technical online expertise”
- “Funding for infrastructure such as DOI, software/server maintenance; editorial support staff and dedicated IT personnel”
- “Funding for infrastructure and development.”
- “In Africa, it does seem that peer reviewers need to be paid a minimal fee. This fee should be allowed and funded centrally and streamlined. Indexing platforms should allow for this model, as it does not hinder the academic integrity of the journal. Templates for layout editing should be available to all journals, which will prevent the need to pay someone on an institutional level, at every institution. Our Libraries has started designing

templates for some journals that ask for it. This means that there won't be a need to recoup the publication fees. Further, a similarity detection service should be available for all African journals, for free, as well as free DOIs.”

- “Increased visibility and access of our journals”
- “Provide funding and collaboration in service provision”
- “Providing funding and technical assistance”
- “Provide help with Metadata and preserving content.”
- “Provide funding models and get political support and commitment in our country.”
- “Providing grants and technical partnership”
- “Provision of Indexing assistance”
- “Should we consider as a country to have a national instance for a platform like PKP OJS and then all universities could utilize this, rather than individual instances at all the universities. Cost, funding, skills, and human resources can then be more streamlined.”
- “Training for editorial teams; portal staff”
- “Toolkits to assist with advocacy.”
- “We need your technical support in developing a good portal infrastructure and of course, we need our portal more discoverable, therefore, we need your support in indexing our portal in more reputable databases.”

5. Country overviews and recommendations

25 country reports (Algeria, Angola, Benin, Botswana, Burkina Faso, Côte d'Ivoire, Democratic Republic of Congo, Ethiopia, Ghana, Kenya, Lesotho, Malawi, Mali, Morocco, Mozambique, Namibia, Nigeria, Senegal, South Africa, Tanzania, Togo, Tunisia, Uganda, Zambia and Zimbabwe) written in English and French outline a diverse Diamond OA publishing landscape with over 1,240 journals. Country snapshots are available below and we would like to thank our experts for their input.

In most cases the country report structure includes the following sections:

- **Landscape and policies** that presents an overview of OA publishing landscape and Diamond OA journal publishing and highlights notable national and institutional OA policy developments.
- **Personnel** that describes how Diamond OA journals personnel works.
- Institutional support that describes support provided to Diamond OA publishing on the institutional level.
- **Collaboration** that presents notable collaborations on Diamond OA publishing.
- **Funding and sustainability** that presents the funding landscape (or lack thereof) for Diamond OA publishing and current sustainability strategies of Diamond OA journals.
- **Technical infrastructure** that presents an overview of publishing platforms for Diamond OA journals.
- **Challenges** faced by Diamond OA journal publishers.
- **Needs and strategies to advance Diamond OA publishing** that outlines possible solutions.

In many countries, registries of Diamond OA journals do not exist and even the data on the number of Diamond OA journals is limited, which speaks to the need for better discovery and indexing services for these types of publications on the national, African and international level.

We were unable to identify Diamond OA journals in some countries: Benin, Burkina Faso, Côte d'Ivoire, Mali and Sierra Leone, but the country reports writing process helped to start Diamond OA publishing conversations in these countries.

Some countries with strong Diamond OA journals (e.g. Egypt and Rwanda) are not covered in this report, as we did not know the experts we could approach for national overviews.

To strengthen Diamond OA publishing and help sustain Diamond OA journals it's important to support journals' institutionally responsible departments, for example libraries, and national platforms for Diamond OA journals enhancing their online publishing workflows and building capacities of editors, reviewers and authors via training.

Detailed recommendations are available in the country overviews below.

5.1 Algeria

Landscape and policies

OA in Algeria

The number of OA journals in Algeria has been increasing. By mid-2024, 1,005 scholarly journals were identified and validated by the Directorate General of Scientific Research and Technological Development (DGRSDT), 868 of which are Diamond OA journals.

A number of factors have contributed to this growth, including the support of government institutions such as the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, the Centre de Recherche sur l'Information Scientifique et Technique (CERIST), the Directorate-General for Scientific Research and Technological Development, and associations and research groups specializing in OA.

Stratégie nationale de la recherche scientifique et du développement technologique (2014-2024) encourages open sharing of research results and stresses the importance of OA.

Diamond OA journal publishing

Algerian OA journals mostly publish research conducted at universities and cover a wide range of disciplines, including sciences, social sciences and humanities. They publish original works (in Arabic, Tamazigh, English, French, German, Spanish, etc.) in both fundamental and applied research.

In terms of the technical infrastructure, there are three types of journals in Algeria:

- journals that have their own website based on OJS,
- journals hosted on the websites of universities, faculties and research laboratories, and
- journals hosted solely on the Algerian national platform.

Diamond OA journals with their own websites based on OJS are often hosted free of charge on the servers of universities and research institutes (e.g. 30 Algerian journals indexed in the DOAJ). They are easy to manage, as maintenance is carried out by the technical staff assigned to these journals or by volunteers. Journals that have their own website based on OJS face fewer obstacles and challenges than other journals.

The Algerian Scientific Journal platform handles online publication workflows. Journals are managed by the editors-in-chief. The platform fully supports editorial and publication workflows.

Personnel

The staff of Algerian OA journals may vary depending on the structure and resources of the journal, but the following roles and responsibilities are generally assumed:

- **Editorial Board** (including the Editor-in-Chief who defines editorial policy, oversees the publication process and makes final decisions on articles; Associate Editors who coordinate the peer review process, select reviewers and contribute to editorial decision-making; and Committee members who contribute their scientific expertise and help select articles for publication),
- **Peer reviewers,**
- **Editorial team** (including a Publication Manager who coordinates the publication process, from article submission to online publication; and an Editorial assistant who helps manage administrative tasks, communicate with authors and reviewers, and format articles) and
- **Other roles** (e.g. a webmaster).

The staff of Diamond OA journals consists of volunteers (academics and researchers) and part-time or full-time employees of the managing institution. The paid staff receive salaries from the institutions that recruit them: universities, faculties, research institutes, research centres, government bodies. Running the staff of an OA journal is a major challenge.

For the time being, editors in Algeria do not have a special status, which would allow them to receive a bonus or an adjustment to their working hours as teachers/researchers. All the editors-in-chief of Algerian OA journals are volunteers. However, some universities have a publishing and scientific coordination department responsible for managing their own journals by hosting them on the university website.

Institutional support

Most Algerian universities and research centres provide Diamond OA journals with premises, specific IT services such as free hosting and permanent staff to manage journal updates.

Collaboration

There is significant collaboration between Diamond OA journals in Algeria through collaborative platforms, between editorial boards and journal editorial teams, and the organization of workshops and training courses on OA and scientific publication. CERIST, in collaboration with the Directorate-General for Scientific Research and Technological Development, regularly organizes workshops and training courses. These workshops and training courses are aimed at researchers, students, librarians and all members of the scientific community involved in the management of Algerian journals.

Funding and sustainability

The funding of OA journals in Algeria depends entirely on institutional subsidies and the support of universities in allocating grants to journals published by their researchers and free hosting on their platforms and servers.

Algerian OA journals rely on various strategies to ensure their sustainability:

- Subsidies and institutional funding: Crucial support from research organizations, universities and governments.
- Publication of early access articles, management of research data, organization of conferences.
- Open source software and tools to facilitate journal management.
- Efficient and automated publication processes.
- Training for volunteers and editors.
- Promotion and awareness of the importance of Diamond OA journals.

Algerian Scientific Journals platform

In 2015, Algeria launched an [Algerian Scientific Journals Platform \(ASJP\)](#). It currently includes 868 Diamond OA journals and 234,076 OA articles, and supports the Arabic, French, English and Kabyle languages.

Not all journals hosted on ASJP have persistent identifiers. CERIST is currently negotiating with Crossref to assign DOIs to articles published by journals hosted on this platform.

Governance and funding

The platform is hosted by CERIST and is managed by a director and permanent technical staff.

It is funded from the public budget, by the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, with a contribution from the Direction Générale de La Recherche Scientifique et Du Développement Technologique (DGRSDT). They cover the costs of installations, maintenance, premises, human resources management, general IT services (e-mail, hardware, internet, etc.), specific IT services such as anti-virus and plagiarism software, and the salaries of permanent staff. Funding is currently very stable and will remain sustainable as long as public funding is provided.

The platform does not have a specific budget, in foreign currencies (Euros, dollars, etc.), to be able to pay recurring costs abroad.

Personnel

The platform is staffed by IT engineers, technicians and developers. Although they receive performance bonuses, they tend to leave their jobs for more attractive job offers in Europe.

Challenges

- The lack of a specific status for editors-in-chief and editorial boards

- The lack of financial resources. Dependence on institutional subsidies can undermine the sustainability of journals.
- The lack of financial and human resources to invest in training the editorial board and staff.
- Language barrier: Most Algerian OA journals that publish articles in French or English cannot afford professional translation services. This has an impact on the quality of the articles published.
- The lack of international visibility of Algerian Diamond OA journals. Few journals are indexed in international databases; as a result, they have limited quality submissions from both international and local researchers.
- Instability of the editorial board and declining motivation of journal staff due to the lack of rewards and incentives, work overload and the lack of clear and transparent communication between staff members.
- Incomplete information on journal pages: the lack of information about the copyright policy and licences and lack of information about the editorial boards, resulting in rejection of journals by DOAJ.
- Creative Commons licences are still not common among Algerian journals.
- The lack of ICT infrastructure, low bandwidth, poor connectivity and workspace for some OA journals.
- Irregularity and delays in journal publication, sometimes as a result of lengthy peer review processes.

Needs and strategies to advance Diamond OA publishing

To overcome these shortcomings and meet the challenges, capacity building is needed to develop training programmes for Algerian authors and publishers on international scientific publication standards.

There is also a need to increase funding for Algerian OA journals to enable them to invest in quality. The establishment of diversified funding models is essential to guarantee the viability and independence of OA journals.

Support for Algerian Diamond OA journals is necessary and can be provided in the form of:

- **Financial:** crucial for sustainability.
- **Technical:** development and maintenance of the platform.
- **Human:** volunteers, editors, editorial board.
- **Promotional:** publicizing the journal and its advantages.

Strategies to advance Diamond OA journal publishing in Algeria

- Funds that are allocated to pay APCs to hybrid journals should be invested in shared infrastructure and platforms that can support Diamond OA journals.
- Long-term preservation of Diamond OA journals (digitize, curate and share all collections in the archive).

- Algerian Diamond OA journals need to raise their quality and elevate their place in research assessment by indexing these journals in the international standard databases such as DOAJ, Scopus and Web of Science.

The project can support Algerian journals in making Diamond OA more sustainable in several ways:

Funding:

- Provision of grants to cover the publication, management and development costs of Diamond OA journals.
- Setting up a national fund for Diamond OA.
- Collaboration with international funding bodies to support Diamond OA journals.

Training and capacity building:

- Organization of workshops and training on business models for Diamond OA journals and on managing publishing platforms.
- Provision of resources and tools to support Diamond OA journals.
- Support for the creation of networks and collaborations between Diamond OA journals.

Infrastructure and technologies:

- Support for a national Diamond OA publishing platform.
- Support for the adoption of open source software and tools for managing Diamond OA journals.
- Setting up a robust IT infrastructure to host Diamond OA journals.

Advocacy and awareness:

- Promoting the importance of Diamond OA publishing to researchers, institutions and policy makers.
- Organization of awareness raising and advocacy campaigns on the benefits of Diamond OA publishing.
- Participation in international conferences and events to promote Diamond OA publishing.

International collaboration:

- Working with international organizations to support Diamond OA journals.
- Establishment of partnerships with Diamond OA journals in the MENA region and European countries.
- Participation in Diamond OA publishing research projects.

In addition to these points, the project can also adapt to the specific needs of Algerian journals by carrying out studies and analyses to identify obstacles to the adoption of Diamond OA publishing and proposing appropriate solutions.

In conclusion, the project can play a crucial role in promoting and supporting sustainable Diamond OA publishing in Algeria by tackling the different aspects of the challenge. It should be emphasized that the success of the project will depend on the collaboration and commitment of all stakeholders, including researchers, institutions, funding bodies and decision-makers.

Author: [Kamel Belhamel](#), University of Bejaia (Algeria)

5.2 Angola

This overview is based on “[OA for Angola Collaborative Project](#)” (2022) results from UNESCO, the Ministério do Ensino Superior, Ciência, Tecnologia e Inovação, Redalyc of the Autonomous University of the State of Mexico, AmeliCA and the Universidade Óscar Ribas.

Landscape and policies

Diamond OA journals are published by universities and scholarly societies (Associations). Diamond OA journals and a national repository contribute to the research progress and benefit the country, according to focus groups participants in “[OA for Angola Collaborative Project](#)”, as they allow publication and access without economic constraints.

Strategies to advance Diamond OA

“[OA for Angola Collaborative Project](#)” provided the following recommendations:

- Continue publishing in Diamond OA journals, which are the main publications channels for Angolan researchers.
- Diamond OA publishing requires joint work of governmental and educational authorities, researchers and students
- Consolidate OA publishing through the development of institutional and national policies (incentivizing publications in Diamond OA journals) and the creation of open knowledge offices.
- Establish collaboration programmes with institutions in Brazil, Cuba and Portugal to strengthen Angolan Diamond OA journals.
- Promote panels, discussions and/or congresses among researchers on issues related to copyright and Diamond OA publishing (such as Creative Commons licenses) to promote better informed publishing choices.
- Request Angolan authors to use author-level identifiers (such as ORCID, Google Scholar, Autores Redalyc), so that their research can be more easily located and its evaluation can be more transparent.

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5.3 Benin

No Diamond OA journals have been identified in Benin.

Needs and strategies to advance Diamond OA publishing

The following needs have been identified:

- Streamline technical support for journals;
- Ensure that journals comply with international standards of practice;
- Strengthen the operational capacities of journals and ensure their recognition by bodies such as Conseil Africain et Malgache pour l'Enseignement Supérieur (CAMES);
- Increase journal efficiency with collaborations, e.g. working in disciplinary consortia;
- Provide financial support for journals and invest in their OA and open science future;
- Ensure the research integrity of publications and the professionalism of journals.

Author: [Joseph Sagbohan](#), Université d'Abomey-Calavi, Ecole Polytechnique d'Abomey-Calavi (Bénin)

5.4 Botswana

The report does not cover the whole country and is based on a survey conducted among the Diamond OA journals hosted on the [University of Botswana journal platform](#). The platform has ten OA journals and is powered by OJS software. This report covers responses from four journals that currently have active editors and other staff.

Personnel

One of the four journals has a dedicated unit responsible for the journal with some personnel employed and some working as volunteers; in two journals the personnel employed by the institution share their time between publishing and other tasks, and in one journal all the work is done on a volunteer basis.

While some journal editors get additional points for performance evaluation, promotion is not based solely on this.

Institutional support

All surveyed journals use the facilities and premises provided by their host organization. One journal uses general IT services (email, hardware, Internet, etc.) and one uses service-specific IT services (publishing platform/website, tools, etc.) provided by the hosting organization.

Collaboration

Two journals mentioned IT (submission system, platform, website, etc.) and production services (copy-editing, proofreading, typesetting, metadata, etc.) as the most likely areas for collaboration. Other areas of collaboration include training, support and/or advice on publishing policies and best practices; communication services (marketing/dissemination, social media, etc.) and editorial services (selection of manuscripts, peer review, plagiarism checking services, etc.).

Funding and sustainability

Funding sources vary and fixed and permanent subsidies from the journal's primary institution's base, periodically negotiated subsidies from the journal's primary institution's base, collective funding and print sales are equally represented. Two journals also have other sources of income (e.g. event organization, commercial revenue, loans, etc.).

The main challenges related to the financial sustainability of Diamond OA journals include the following:

- Online journals do not generate income, and this can only be addressed if the University covers publishing costs;
- The lack of monetary incentives for editors leads to poor commitment and high drop-out;

- Temporary staff are not regularly paid and there are insufficient funds to pay staff for extra time spent working for the journal.
- Providing funds for typesetting and copy editing.
- Institutions are not committed to funding the upgrades: once deployed software and hardware technologies are very rarely updated.

Technical infrastructure

Technical infrastructure is usually provided in-house, either by a dedicated publishing department (three journals) or across different departments (one journal). For two journals publishing workflows are partially carried out online, whereas in one journal all publishing workflows are supported by the online platform.

ORCID is the only unique persistent identifier assigned by the journal portal.

Inadequate provision of resources for the infrastructure and services, the lack of human resources, administrative and financial constraints are identified as the greatest challenges (three journals). Two journals have to cope with the technical limitations of existing infrastructure and the lack of expertise, while achieving interoperability with other services and systems is seen as a challenge by one journal.

The journal portal is indexed by Google. The journals tried to get indexed in journal indexing services, but they failed to meet technical and non-technical inclusion criteria.

Challenges

Other key challenges of Diamond OA publishing in Botswana include:

- **Governance of OA:** Greater involvement of key stakeholders such as research institutes, librarians, educational and political decision makers;
- **Standardization and Interoperability:** There is a need to improve interoperability of open platforms to increase content visibility;
- **Widespread Internet access:** Access to high speed Internet remains a challenge, constraining times and places where researchers and scholars can work, and their access to literature.

Needs and strategies to advance Diamond OA publishing

- OA advocacy workshops for researchers;
- PID registration campaigns;
- Hardware and software;
- Training and capacity building.

Author: [Naniki S Maphakwane](#), Botswana Open University (Botswana)

5.5 Burkina Faso

We were unable to identify Diamond OA journals in Burkina Faso. All journals require a financial contribution from authors. There is an interest in adopting the Diamond OA publishing model, but financial, material and human support is needed. Journals in Burkina Faso face financial constraints and lack qualified staff. They mainly depend on subsidies from the government and financial contributions from authors. It is therefore crucial to identify other sources of funding, apart from the fixed and regular contributions from the ministry or the university.

Current challenges include:

- Instability of funding;
- The lack of sustainability plans;
- The lack of training to support production (e.g. the layout of articles in the journal);
- Articles published in journals do not have a DOI;
- Indexation in international databases;
- The elimination of publication fees for authors;
- The recruitment of qualified staff and the lack of expertise are significant obstacles to the sustainability and improved quality of journals.

Needs and strategies to advance Diamond OA publishing

The journals' needs include financial support for a transition from fee-based journals to Diamond OA, capacity-building for those involved and raising researchers' awareness of the benefits of OA. An immediate priority is to set up training courses to raise awareness among academics and researchers of the benefits of Diamond OA journals.

The adoption of a national and regional strategy aligned with the principles of open science and OA publishing, in line with UNESCO's Recommendation on Open Science, is a political imperative.

There are opportunities for sub-regional cooperation in French-speaking Africa, and support by organizations such as African and Malagasy Council for Higher Education (CAMES), CRUFAOCI, WACREN, AUF, EIFL, and other international organizations such as UNESCO would be beneficial. A fruitful partnership with the DOAJ could also be helpful. CAMES, in collaboration with key organizations such as WACREN, AUF, and EIFL, and with the financial support of UNESCO, should lead advocacy actions in member countries to encourage the adoption of open science principles. Such an approach would not only help increase the visibility and impact of African research, but would also foster a more inclusive and accessible scholarly ecosystem.

Author: [Zoé Aubierge Ouangré](#), Université Norbert Zongo (Burkina Faso)

5.6 Côte d'Ivoire

We were unable to identify any Diamond OA journals in Côte d'Ivoire. Institutional journals do not have sufficient budget to publish without APCs. Although some of the journals would like to flip to Diamond OA publishing, funding is a stumbling block.

Current challenges include:

- The lack of persistent identifiers, which is being addressed by the collaboration between the Université Virtuelle de Côte d'Ivoire and DataCite;
- Insufficient visibility and indexation issues;
- African and Malagasy Council for Higher Education (CAMES) doesn't accept publications in DOAJ-indexed journals when researchers apply for assessment and promotion. AJOL indexed journals aren't considered either.

Needs and strategies to advance Diamond OA publishing

There is a desire to learn about current good practices in Diamond OA publishing and to enhance the quality and the visibility of journals. And there is a need to change regional researcher evaluation and promotion approaches.

Author: [Cécile Outtara-Coulibaly](#), Université Virtuelle de Côte d'Ivoire

5.7 Democratic Republic of Congo

Out of 13 OA journals published in the country, three are Diamond OA journals and the sections below cover Diamond OA journal practices.

Personnel

There are no dedicated units responsible for the journals with employed personnel (fully or partially employed to work for the journals), but personnel employed by the institutions are sharing their time to work for the journal.

Institutional support

All journals use the facilities, premises and general IT services (email, hardware, Internet, etc.) provided by their host organizations. Host organizations also pay salaries of temporary staff. Two journals also use service-specific IT services (publishing platform/website, tools, etc.) provided by the host organization.

Funding and sustainability

Two journals receive periodically negotiated subsidies from the journal's primary institution's base and are also funded by print sales. All journals have financial constraints.

Technical infrastructure

Technical infrastructure is usually provided in-house by an IT department/personnel.

Author: [Eliezer Bisimwa Mwongane](#), Université Libre des Pays des Grands Lacs (Democratic Republic of Congo)

5.8 Ethiopia

Landscape and policies

A national OA policy in Ethiopia requires that all publicly funded research outputs be OA. Institutions also have policies related to OA and data sharing.

[Ethiopian Journals Online \(EJOL\)](#) is a national OA publishing portal built on OJS and managed by Addis Ababa University. It hosts 22 Diamond OA journals, which are described below.

Personnel

Almost all Diamond OA journals have a dedicated unit with staff employed to support publishing. They all have an editor-in-chief, a managing editor and associate editors. The editor-in-chief and associate editors are already employed as faculty members and share their time between the institution and the journal. Journals also employ dedicated staff: managing editors, assistant editors, and secretaries, responsible exclusively for publishing operations. Salaries for the staff working for the journal including the editor-in-chief, managing editor and associate editors, are covered by host institutions.

Institutions usually provide incentives for the journal staff: the editor-in-chief and associate editors receive small monthly payments and the workload of the editor-in-chief is usually reduced (e.g. less teaching duties).

Institutional support

Host organizations provide facilities and services, general IT services and publishing platforms/websites.

Collaboration

Journals have notable collaboration: they use shared hosting provided on the national level and within their institution. They also collaborate on capacity building workshops and other training events for editors, authors and reviewers.

Funding and sustainability

Except for the salaries and incentives, no permanent or temporary funding is allocated for journals, which is a major challenge that affects the quality and publication frequency of journals.

Journals usually request a budget from the institution on a case by case basis. Institutions previously provided some funding for printing, but due to inflation this is not always the case. Selling print versions and special issues are an alternative source of income for some journals.

Technical infrastructure

The technical infrastructure for journals is maintained and updated in-house by IT departments or institutional publishing departments, usually the library. Research offices are sometimes engaged.

In addition to the national portal [Ethiopian Journals Online \(EJOL\)](#), there are also institutional OA journal portals at [Haramaya University](#) with five journals, Hawassa University with four journals and [University of Gondar](#) with six journals.

Most platforms assign unique persistent identifiers in the form of DOI from DataCite.

There is no dedicated unit to run OJS portals, but the staff employed by the institution share their time between the portal and other tasks. Institutions provide support in the form of facilities and premises, staff, general IT services, platforms, websites, and salaries of the staff.

The portals do not have any allocated funding, and therefore do not have dedicated staff. There are no incentives for working on the portals and this affects their quality and sustainability of the portals.

Challenges

- The lack of permanent dedicated funding to run journals;
- The lack of technical skills among authors and journal editors to work with online publishing platforms;
- The lack of adequate infrastructure to host online publishing platforms;
- Service interruption due to power outages and/or network connectivity issues, capacity of ICT infrastructure/servers,
- The lack of expertise for online publishing platforms: the implementation and management of such systems requires the knowledge of academic publishing, while journals usually consider this a duty of ICT departments;
- Finding reviewers for journal articles.

Needs and strategies to advance Diamond OA publishing

Diamond OA journals in Ethiopia need funding and incentives to be able to have dedicated staff. Journals can also be strengthened through capacity building on quality, including how to use the online publishing platforms. The above measures would help journals maintain quality and

become sustainable. In addition journals would greatly improve their response time and frequency of publication.

The portals' funding needs are related to incentives for experts working on the portal: maintaining and updating the systems and also experts to provide capacity building for editors, reviewers and authors.

The project can support Diamond OA journals in Ethiopia through:

- Funding Diamond OA journals;
- Capacity building;
- Supporting institutional departments responsible for publishing to strengthen OA publishing and help sustain journals – e.g. libraries should be strengthened in capacity to guide online publishing;
- Support for the national platform EJOL and building the capacity of editors, reviewers and authors via training.

Author: Getnet Lemma, Addis Ababa University (Ethiopia)

5.9 Ghana

Landscape

Ghana has been making strides in OA publishing and scholarly communication and the Consortium of Academic and Research Libraries (CARLIGH) has been involved in OA journal publishing initiatives. There are at least 30 Diamond OA journals. All journals are from academic and research institutions. Two universities – [University of Cape Coast](#) and [University of Ghana](#) – maintain OJS-based OA publishing platforms for OA journals.

Funding and sustainability

Diamond OA journals are fully funded by their hosting institutions. Many are hosted by the university departments, which primarily provide funding and staffing for journal-related work. The funds are allocated by departments, with some consistent support from the primary institution.

However, there are no formal incentives for journal staff. Some institutions take into consideration journal editing and publishing for evaluation and promotion, though it is not standardized or enshrined in policy. Promotion criteria don't foresee any additional points for the work done for journals.

Challenges

Diamond OA journals face financial sustainability and quality challenges. More reliable financial support from institutions is needed, enshrined in policy, and creation of contingency plans or emergency funds to address sudden financial shortages. Also, establishing partnerships with organizations or entities willing to provide consistent financial backing will be helpful.

Lack of incentives for editorial teams is another challenge. This can be addressed by providing incentives for editorial team members, in the form of honoraria, professional development opportunities, or recognition, and by fostering a supportive and collaborative work environment to enhance team morale and retention.

High reviewer attrition rates is another challenge, and it is necessary to implement measures to recognize and reward reviewers for their contributions. Rewards and recognition could take the form of certificates, acknowledgments, or training opportunities and developing strategies to engage and retain reviewers, by providing clear guidelines, timely feedback, and opportunities for professional growth.

Diamond OA journals also struggle with visibility and attracting submissions, especially if researchers are unaware of their existence or they are not indexed in widely recognized databases. Some institutions face challenges in terms of technological infrastructure for hosting and maintaining online platforms for their Diamond OA journals. There is a need for capacity building in terms of editorial skills, peer-review processes, and overall journal management to enhance the quality and professionalism of Diamond OA journals.

Building and maintaining a supportive community around the journal is crucial for financial sustainability, therefore, fostering community engagement through social media, academic conferences, and networking events could help. Feedback and collaboration from the academic community, and their involvement in decision-making processes, would also help. Addressing these challenges requires a combination of financial planning, strategic partnerships, and community engagement. Collaboration with like-minded institutions and organizations can contribute significantly to the sustainability of Diamond OA journals.

Needs and strategies to advance Diamond OA publishing

Improving the quality of Diamond OA publishing in Ghana requires collaborative efforts at the journal, institutional, and national levels. National support and policies can create an environment conducive to high-quality OA publishing, while institutional and journal-level actions can contribute to the success of individual initiatives.

Journal Level:

- Peer-review enhancement: rigorous and transparent peer-review processes should be implemented,
- Training for editors and reviewers should be provided to ensure consistency and quality and enhance the skills of editorial teams;
- Encouraging diversity in editorial boards to bring various perspectives;
- Guidance and support for authors, especially those new to the publishing process and offering resources on proper research conduct and writing;
- Investing in robust and user-friendly online platforms for journal hosting and ensuring the security and sustainability of technical infrastructure.

Institutional Level:

- Fostering a culture of continuous learning in scholarly publishing: organizing workshops, webinars, and training sessions for researchers and journal editors;
- Allocating institutional funds to support OA publishing initiatives;
- Establishing grants or awards to encourage high-quality research and publications;
- Recognition and Incentives: Acknowledge and reward quality publications through institutional awards or recognition. Considering OA publishing in promotion and tenure criteria in Ghana can help. Ghana Tertiary Education Commissions(GTEC) could enforce that in academic institutions;
- Infrastructure Support: providing technical support for maintaining journal websites and platforms and ensuring access to tools and software for editorial processes.

National Level: GTEC could enforce the development and implementation of national policies that support Diamond OA publishing. Encourage institutions to adopt OA-friendly policies thereby introducing the following:

- **Funding Initiatives:**
 - Establishing national funding programs to support OA journals.
 - Collaborating with international organizations to secure funding for local initiatives.
- **Networking and Collaboration:**
 - Facilitating collaboration between journals, institutions, and publishers.
 - Creation of a national network for sharing resources and best practices.
- **Open Science Advocacy:**
 - Promoting open science practices and advocating for the importance of Diamond OA publishing.
 - Engaging with policymakers (Ministry of Education, GTEC, Science and Technology Policy Research Institute – CSIR etc.) to incorporate OA principles into research and education policies.
- **Research Evaluation:**
 - Encouraging the use of quality metrics and indicators that take into consideration the value of Diamond OA publications.
 - Avoidance of relying solely on traditional or local metrics for research assessment.
- **Education and Awareness:**
 - Conduct awareness campaigns to educate researchers, institutions, and policymakers about the benefits of OA publishing.
 - Provide resources on best practices in scholarly communication.

Author: [Richard Bruce Lamptey](#), College of Science, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology Library (Ghana)

5.10 Kenya

Landscape and policies

Various organizations in Kenya have developed and implemented OA policies. These organizations run OA journals and repositories where research done by the members of the organizations, including students and faculty, is available. Through the Kenya Library and Information Services Consortium (KLISC) libraries are at the forefront of championing OA journal publishing and policies. Many universities have set up OJS-based portals for OA journal publishing. This overview focuses on Diamond OA journals only.

Personnel

In most Diamond OA journals the personnel work voluntarily; these journals do not have a dedicated host department or unit within their parent organizations. In some cases the institution employs the journal personnel, who share their time between journal publishing and their primary role at the parent organization.

Few host organizations provide incentives for the journal staff. Only one journal mentioned that the staff and reviewers could publish their profiles on the website.

Institutional support

Some host organizations provide in-kind support to their journals. All journals use their host organizations' facilities and premises. In addition, most journals are supported with general IT services, including email, hardware, and the Internet. Some journals use service-specific IT services provided by host organizations.

Collaboration

Diamond OA journals are willing to collaborate in many areas, including editorial services; training and support and/or advice on publishing policies and best practices; IT services (submission system, platform, website, etc.); communication services (marketing/dissemination, social media, etc.); and production services (copy-editing, proofreading, typesetting, metadata, etc.).

Funding and sustainability

Diamond OA journals are mostly funded through periodical negotiation subsidies from the journal's primary institution's base.

The main challenges related to the financial sustainability of Diamond OA publishing include a lack of resources and funding for editorial tools such as AI plagiarism checkers. It has also been pointed out that OA journals face a continuous decline in budgetary allocations, which affects their growth and development. Some OA journals also lack hosting platforms and domain subscription fees after the host organizations withdrew their support. They lack financial resources to compensate peer reviewers.

Among proposed sustainability strategies is to use a part of the income from paid short courses, sensitization workshops and training to support the production costs. Another sustainability strategy would be reaching out to African diaspora scholars who could join the editorial board to help with quality control and advise on management decisions. Another strategy would involve securing advertisements.

Needs and strategies to advance Diamond OA publishing

Kenyan Diamond OA journals can benefit from:

- Funding towards supporting the basic costs of journals such as:
 - payments for editors,
 - subscription for PIDs (e.g. Crossref and DataCite DOI),
 - marketing,
 - similarity checking tools (e.g. Ithenticate);
 - honoraria for reviewers,
 - establishment of journal management offices/departments,
 - annual server and web hosting costs,
 - graphic design costs for the OJS interface;
- Training
 - for editorial teams,
 - on how to get indexed on Scopus, WoS, DOAJ, AJOL.

Author: [Arnold Mwanzu](#), Aga Khan University (Kenya)

5.11 Lesotho

Landscape and policies

The National University of Lesotho (NUL) publishes two Diamond OA journals. They are hosted by the Library on the institutional platform [NUL Journals Online](#), powered by OJS. The journals belong to the Faculty of Humanities and Faculty of Agriculture.

NUL has also proposed a policy to establish a journal titled the *NUL Multidisciplinary Journal*. The journal will be a Diamond OA journal hosted on the Library's platform, NUL Journals Online. The approval of the policy is pending. If approved, it could provide an avenue for the Pro Vice Chancellor to mobilize resources to fund the publishing process. Faculties do not have the resources to support publishing.

Personnel

The publication teams process the publication and editorial routines at the faculty level, although there is no full-time staff working for the journals at the faculties. Staff do this as part of their academic citizenship and are employed by the NUL as lecturers. They share their time between journal publishing and other tasks including teaching and research.

There are no incentives for journal's staff at the institutions, but the role is recognized as academic citizenship and additional points for evaluation/promotion are awarded.

Institutional support

The University provides the infrastructure including the Internet connection, pays staff salaries and also provides staff work offices. Each of the two faculties, Agriculture and Humanities select their own journal teams, who develop their own workflows. The Library hosts the OJS platform for the Faculties. The Library has ICT personnel and a scholarly communication librarian to assist the faculties.

Collaboration

There is no visible collaboration between the two journals. They are only hosted on the same platform.

Funding and sustainability

Lesotho does not have a National Research Organisation or other strategic funds for publishing facilities, to support Diamond OA journals. While Diamond OA publishing may be desired, the reality is that it needs financial resources to sustain it.

Challenges

- There is no mechanism to incentivise publication teams;
- No funding to support Diamond OA publishing;
- The frequency of publication of the journals at NUL.

Needs and strategies to advance Diamond OA publishing

Lesotho and NUL need financial and training interventions that will build capacity to develop and implement feasible medium-term financial strategies that facilitate the consistent execution of editorial tasks, incorporating essential developmental elements for adhering to globally recognized quality standards in editorial work and publishing, all while guaranteeing the continuous accessibility of published content.

The Library would like to see more training provided to these faculties to enable the sharing of standards, skills, policies and collaborations among Diamond OA journals (including shared reviewers' databases, training for editors, reviewers and authors, etc.)

The most pressing needs for Diamond OA publishing are:

- Financing the journal publishing process, including editors and editorial teams, typesetting, and other technical matters;
- There is also a need for capacity building in online journal management and OA.
- Strengthening the infrastructure in the library and getting additional staff.

Author: [Buhle Mbambo-Thata](#), National University of Lesotho Libraries (Lesotho)

5.12 Malawi

Landscape and policies

Malawi does not have a national OA policy. However, there have been initiatives or guidelines within academic institutions and research organizations that promote OA (e.g. Mzuzu University). The Malawi Library and Information Consortium (MALICO) has collaborated with universities and research institutions in Malawi to provide insights into efforts towards OA.

There is no national journal quality assessment system in Malawi but individual universities and research institutions have their own processes for evaluating the quality of journals, and this is particularly the case with universities where a faculty is involved in publishing. Where such assessments exist, various criteria are taken into consideration, such as peer review practices, editorial standards, citation metrics and relevance to the academic community. While OA-related criteria may not be explicitly included in assessment, the openness and accessibility of journals indirectly contribute to their perceived quality.

Many universities and research institutions in Malawi host their own journals or have repositories where research outputs, including Diamond OA journals, are archived and made available. Malawi Library and Information Consortium (MALICO) has been advocating for Diamond OA publishing.

This overview covers four Diamond OA journals.

Personnel

Two Diamond OA journals are published by a dedicated unit in the university responsible for a journal and one of them has employed personnel (fully or partially employed to work for the journal), but in two other cases there is no dedicated unit and everyone is working as volunteers.

Institutional support

Journal host organizations provide facilities and premises and general IT services (email, hardware, Internet, etc.) and in some cases Human Resource management, salaries of permanent and/or temporary staff and service-specific IT services (publishing platform/website, tools, etc.).

Collaboration

Diamond OA journals share reviewer and author databases and in some cases use shared hosting and publishing platforms and run joint training for editors, reviewers and authors.

Funding and sustainability

Diamond OA journals are funded by print sales (e.g. print on demand), periodically negotiated subsidy from the journal's primary institution's base and in some cases fixed and permanent subsidy from the journal's primary institution's base.

Most Diamond OA journals (except one) do not have capacity to develop and implement feasible medium-term financial strategies that facilitate the consistent execution of editorial tasks, incorporating essential developmental elements for adhering to globally recognized quality standards in editorial work and publishing, all while guaranteeing the continuous accessibility of published content.

Challenges

Some key challenges of Diamond OA publishing in Malawi include the following:

- **Limited funding** for operating and maintaining OA publishing;
- **Insufficient technical infrastructure and expertise** may hinder the establishment and maintenance of robust OA publishing platforms;
- **Capacity building** to train editors, reviewers, and authors in scholarly publishing practices, including ethical considerations and quality assurance;
- **Visibility and recognition:** Diamond OA journals from Malawi struggle to gain visibility and recognition on a global stage, which can impact their ability to attract submissions and build strong reputation;
- **Ensuring high editorial standards and peer-review processes;**
- **Language Barriers:** English is commonly used in scholarly publishing, but barriers may exist for researchers who are not proficient in English, potentially limiting the diversity of voices represented in Malawian scholarship.

Needs and strategies to advance Diamond OA publishing

Addressing these challenges will require concerted efforts from stakeholders in Malawi, and potentially collaboration with international partners.

Additional funding needs and priorities for sustainable Diamond OA publishing in Malawi include the following:

- **Infrastructure development:** Investing in the development and maintenance of robust technical infrastructure, including hosting platforms and publishing systems, to ensure reliable and efficient dissemination of research outputs.
- **Capacity building:** Providing support for training programmes and workshops aimed at enhancing the capacity of editors, reviewers, authors, and journal managers in scholarly publishing practices, including ethical standards, peer review processes, and editorial management.
- **Promotion and outreach:** Allocating resources for promotional activities to increase awareness and visibility of Malawian Diamond OA journals both locally and internationally, thereby attracting more submissions and readership.
- **Quality assurance:** Implementing mechanisms for quality assurance, such as editorial guidelines, peer review standards, and plagiarism detection tools, to uphold the integrity and credibility of Malawian scholarly publications.
- **Inclusivity and diversity:** Supporting initiatives to promote inclusivity and diversity in scholarly publishing by providing resources for translations, language editing services, and initiatives to encourage submissions from under-represented groups.

To support sustainable Diamond OA publishing in Malawi, the project should consider the following actions:

- **Financial support** through grants or funding opportunities specifically targeting Malawian Diamond OA journals and publishing initiatives;
- **Technical assistance and expertise** to help establish and maintain OA publishing platforms, improve infrastructure, and address technical challenges;
- **Training and capacity building** to enhance the skills and knowledge of stakeholders involved in scholarly publishing, including editors, reviewers, authors, and journal managers;
- **Networking and collaboration:** Facilitating networking opportunities and collaborations between Malawian publishing initiatives and international partners to share best practices, resources, and experiences in OA publishing;
- **Advocacy and awareness:** Supporting advocacy efforts to raise awareness about the importance of OA publishing and its potential benefits for the research community and society at large.

By addressing these funding needs and priorities and providing targeted support, the project can contribute to the sustainability and growth of Diamond OA publishing in Malawi, thereby enhancing the visibility and impact of Malawian research output on a global scale.

Author: [Patrick Mapulanga](#), Kamuzu University of Health Sciences (Malawi)

5.13 Mali

We were unable to identify any Diamond OA journals in Mali. Submission and publication fees are the main sources of OA journal funding now that cover all journal running costs. Covering the production costs, technical support services and motivating volunteers will help to develop the Diamond OA publishing model.

In almost all cases, OA journal teams work on a voluntary basis. If journals are published by research institutions, the journal staff divide their working time between the activities of the journals and other tasks. Learned societies journals are managed on a voluntary basis by the members of the society. Research institutions as well as societies issue certificates to academic staff working for their journals. These certificates of service to the community are attached to promotion applications.

Several journals are housed on the premises of institutions, which provide them with general IT infrastructures (e-mail, hardware, Internet, etc.) and specific infrastructures (publishing platform/website, tools, etc.).

Revue Maliennes <https://www.revues.ml> portal is maintained by a volunteer (a librarian in a research institution passionate about new technologies who works to increase the visibility of national scientific production).

There is a lack of training in scholarly publishing, infrastructure and institutional, national and international support. All the journals operate in isolation and there is no collaboration between

the journal teams. Current research evaluation policies and practices in the country and in the region do not favour Diamond OA publishing practices.

Author: [Abdrahamane Anne](#), DER Santé Publique (Mali)

5.14 Morocco

Landscape and policies

One of the main missions of the CNRST (Centre National pour la Recherche Scientifique et Technique) is to contribute to the promotion of the country's research. One of the dissemination and promotion channels enabled by CNRST is the [Moroccan Scientific Journals Portal \(PRSM\)](#), where the majority of journals seem to be Diamond OA. It was not possible to establish the accurate number of Diamond OA journals in Morocco, but it's estimated that there are at least 75 OA journals that do not charge APCs.

Personnel

The majority of journals run by individuals operate without a dedicated publishing unit, using volunteer staff. For journals run by institutions, there is usually no dedicated unit either, but staff are employed by the institution and divide their time between publishing the journal and other tasks.

Incentives for journal staff may vary, but generally speaking, academic recognition remains the main form of motivation.

Institutional support

Scholarly journals generally benefit from limited institutional support. Host institutions may provide in-kind support such as meeting facilities and basic IT services, but this largely depends on the resources available within each institution. The majority of journals benefit from CNRST, which offers technical support by providing a shared technical platform based on OJS.

Collaboration

Collaborations between Diamond OA journals are very limited. The CNRST offers a range of services to journal publishers, including access to a common publication platform and training sessions on various aspects of the editorial process and indexing. These training sessions offer publishers the opportunity to improve their skills and foster collaboration within the Moroccan scientific journal community

Funding and sustainability

Journals are funded from a variety of sources, including periodic institutional grants, time-limited external grants, donations and crowdfunding, partnerships and collaborations, and print sales. However, financial instability is common, and there is usually no approved annual budget for the

journal. In addition, most journals do not have a sustainable development plan, which makes it difficult to guarantee long-term financial stability.

Challenges and solutions

The main challenges to the financial sustainability of Moroccan journals include the lack of stable funding and dependence on short-term subsidies. Solutions could include diversifying funding sources, strengthening international collaborations and seeking longer-term grants to ensure financial stability. Many journals find it difficult to operate on a day-to-day basis, in particular to cover the costs of publishing and remunerating the staff involved.

In addition to financial challenges, there are other obstacles, such as the need to improve the visibility of journals, and to attract and retain authors, reviewers and readers.

Retaining volunteer reviewers, which can have an impact on the quality and publishing schedules, is also a challenge.

While the submission and publication workflows are usually managed via the publishing platform, some journals still conduct peer review via email. The main reasons for this include:

- Resistance to change, where editorial teams prefer to maintain traditional methods rather than adopt new approaches;
- Insufficient human resources allocated for journal management, which often leads the publisher to take on several editorial roles;
- Lack of specialized training to use the journal management system effectively;
- The instability of the editorial board, requiring ongoing training to ensure effective journal management;
- Financial constraints, particularly with regard to recruiting and maintaining the staff needed to manage the editorial process.

Needs and strategies to advance Diamond OA publishing

As far as funding needs are concerned, various forms of support are required to enhance the sustainability of Diamond OA journals. This could include regular, ongoing grants, as well as awareness-raising initiatives to promote the benefits of OA publishing and encourage financial contributions.

In summary, to make Diamond OA journals more sustainable, it is essential to address the financial and operational challenges they face. This requires the ongoing commitment of various stakeholders, including government institutions, universities, research organizations and foundations, to support these publications and ensure their long-term viability in the Moroccan academic landscape and internationally.

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5.15 Mozambique

Landscape

At least 16 Diamond OA journals are published by Eduardo Mondlane University / Universidade Eduardo Mondlane, National Institute of Health / Instituto Nacional da Saúde, Catholic University of Mozambique / Universidade Católica de Moçambique, Higher Polytechnic Institute of Gaza / Instituto Superior Politécnico de Gaza, University of Lúrio / Universidade Lúrio, Pedagogical University of Maputo / Universidade Pedagógica de Maputo and University of Save / Universidade Save.

Personnel

Some universities have a dedicated unit responsible for scientific publishing activities, directed by a unit director, who also performs the functions of the editor-in-chief and coordinates tasks related to scholarly publishing, with academic and research units, namely, faculties, departments and centres. In other institutions, this role is taken by the unit responsible for Research, Extension and Innovation. In one institution the scholarly journal is under the responsibility of the Training and Communication unit.

Institutions are willing to mobilize funding to support OA journal initiatives, but they face many challenges to ensure investments. The dynamics of scholarly publishing in Mozambique often depends on the enthusiasm and commitment of individual professionals who take the role of the editor-in-chief. They make a tremendous effort to keep the journals running even when facing many structural difficulties.

In journals associated with public higher education and research institutions, the staff members performing editorial tasks are mostly employed by these institutions. In some cases, they are allocated to the unit responsible for publication management, while in others they carry out publication management activities on a voluntary basis, as they have other tasks that consume most of their working time.

For example, in one institution only the editor-in-chief is employed full-time at the unit, along with the administrative staff who do not perform any editorial functions. The remaining members of the editorial board are partially linked to the editorial unit, dedicating the most of their time to other academic activities and research unrelated to editorial processes. The funding, IT infrastructure, human resources management and other facilities for the OA journal are provided by the university and allocated to the editorial unit. All these resources are provided centrally, but there are many challenges to mobilizing funds, maintaining support services and infrastructures, such as higher quality servers and a stable internet connection, IT specialists with knowledge and skills to configure and maintain applications and/or scholarly publishing platforms.

At the moment, there are no incentives for the employees of the editorial units at institutions that have scholarly journals in Mozambique, except for monthly salaries provided by their institutions, which in many cases correspond to their main jobs and not exactly the function of editor and/or member of the scholarly journal's editorial team. Efforts are made to take into consideration a

part of these activities in annual performance evaluations of the employees, which can also be used for professional career promotion purposes.

Institutional support

IT infrastructure, financial resources, human resources and support services are generally provided by the institutions that host OA journals. For example, the editorial unit can be located in the central library and benefit from shared IT infrastructure services, including specific support services for installing, configuring and managing the OJS platform and other applications or IT services.

A similar structure can be found at other institutions: resources are shared between the unit responsible for the journal and the IT department, where the IT department installs, configures and maintains the OJS platform.

Another example of resource-sharing is the editorial team with staff from different departments: the library, IT, and communication services.

Collaboration

Diamond OA journal editors sometimes collaborate on training sessions for editors, reviewers and authors supported by partner-funded projects and these training activities are usually open to all those interested in the institution, as well as to other institutions as a way of maximizing gains in terms of sharing experiences in the Mozambican scholarly community.

Training opportunities for editors, reviewers and authors have been offered by international publishers, notably Elsevier and Springer. It is important to note that similar opportunities have also been offered through initiatives such as Research4Life and other international organizations that work to mobilize resources and support for the development of platforms for accessing information resources and scientific publications. Recently similar workshops were organized in collaboration with partners from Brazil and Portugal through the Lusophone Open Science Conference (ConfOA).

Funding and sustainability

In general, OA journal initiatives are funded entirely by funds from the public budget, in the case of public institutions, while private institutions use funds from the institution's general revenues.

Some specific activities, such as training for staff on academic writing and peer review, have been supported through projects funded by university partners. Although the FNI (National Research Fund) provides support to research projects that include the publication and dissemination of information, OA journals have not had any projects/activities funded by FNI.

Technical infrastructure

Four institutions have implemented the OJS platform to edit and publish Diamond OA journals. Although they have been using the OJS platform for some time, it is not yet used to its fullest. Namely, the OJS platform is used only for online publishing, while practically the entire process

between submission and publication of accepted manuscripts is carried out outside of this. Submissions can be made either by email or via the platform, and the former option is used by younger authors only, who recently graduated from masters or doctoral levels. The peer review process is conducted off-platform.

Some other institutions using OJS are struggling with technical limitations at the editorial level, including technical issues related to the structuring of the platform to host journals and their volumes and issues.

Some institutions do not adopt OJS due to technical limitations and continue to publish journals in the PDF format, through links that are inserted on the institutions' websites, though they seem to have an IT infrastructure (servers, dedicated internet) capable of hosting the platform. These institutions lack support for the training of IT staff and editorial board members.

Challenges

The key challenges include:

- The lack of Diamond OA publication policies;
- Training for editorial teams, reviewers and authors with an emphasis on aspects of Diamond OA publishing;
- Training focusing on good practices in OA scholarly publishing and complying with journal indexing requirements;
- The migration plan for all print journals to the OJS platform.

In general, all institutions publishing scholarly journals in Mozambique face many challenges in ensuring financial sustainability. They mostly depend on government resources, which have been reduced in recent years, as the publishing of scholarly journals does not seem to be a priority when allocating funds from the public budget. In most institutions, initiatives related to journal publishing are at an embryonic stage and they often depend on small projects funded by external partners. When these projects come to an end, funding for the journals established in this context also ceases, leading them to a crisis soon after the publication of the first issues.

For example, a journal was established through a project funded by external partners and its hosting in a cloud is paid with the project funds. The funding is coming to an end and there are no funds to maintain the journal after the end of the project. Another journal is facing financial sustainability challenges regarding the need to improve overall journal quality elements. Namely, the editorial unit has been seeking funding to use DOIs. Unfortunately, it has not been possible to ensure funding from the public budget. Funding through a project has recently been approved for this purpose but it cannot be considered sustainable in the medium and long term, as this project lasts three years.

There are also many challenges related to quality and integrity, including ethical aspects in scholarly publishing as in almost all initiatives the editorial teams lack specific training in editorial matters and processes. Except for the journal team from one university, editorial teams have not participated in any training on editorial processes in scholarly journals and they had to learn independently by dealing with specific situations.

The biggest challenge to the effective and efficient use of the OJS platform in Mozambican institutions is related to the weakness in basic IT skills by authors, members of editorial teams and reviewers.

A major challenge delaying the publication process is peer review. The local academic community is not so well developed and there are many difficulties in identifying appropriate specialists to perform review.

Another major challenge is ensuring that all editorial processes are carried out via the platform. To achieve this, it is necessary to promote workshops to train editorial teams and reviewers to effectively use the OJS platform.

Needs and strategies to advance Diamond OA publishing

In order to ensure the sustainability of Diamond OA journals, investment should be made in shared hosting and infrastructure for journal publishing. Other necessary services could converge to guarantee the quality of publications, including the compliance with the journal indexing requirements and criteria.

Training in academic writing (preparing manuscripts, using reference software), conducting peer review in line with best practice and ethical standards, data preparation, storage and sharing is much needed.

Help to develop good practices and guidelines and preparation for indexation is also important.

Training should also focus on the efficient use of the OJS platform and carrying out all publishing workflows via the platform.

We believe that an investment in the establishment of a shared hosting service for scholarly journals, which could be implemented and managed by the Mozambique Research and Education Network (MoRENet), would improve the sustainability of OA publishing in Mozambique. MoRENet already has a part of connectivity and storage infrastructure that can be used in a shared way by all institutions interested in creating and hosting scholarly journals.

Additionally, it would be necessary to invest in training a service management team, which would be responsible for replicating the training at the local (institutional) level. This will allow the creation of a collaboration network among institutions, ensuring the sustainability of Diamond OA journals.

Author: [Horacio Zimba](#), Eduardo Mondlane University (Mozambique)

5.16 Namibia

Landscape

At least 17 scholarly journals are published in Namibia; 14 are OA and 12 participated in this study as Diamond OA journals. Only nine journals operate through a journal management system and are published entirely online. Due to limited technical support, the other journals publish journal issues in PDF format on the institution's website. Such journals are unsearchable and inaccessible because there is no publicly available metadata description of the journal and its content.

Personnel

Most journals operate on the existing human resources of the institutions, to whom the journal management is an added responsibility without any additional remuneration. Editors and editorial board members are full-time staff members of local and international universities (Kangira, 2019). Along with their job duties, they dedicate some of their time to journal management. It is only at the National Commission on Research, Science and Technology (NCRST) that a journal manager is a full-time position, but in most other institutions, it is an added responsibility to their full-time jobs (e.g. teaching and research). There is no remuneration system for journal editors and peer reviewers.

Regarding incentives, for academic institutions such as The University of Namibia (UNAM), the chief and deputy journal editors get a publication point when applying for promotion. At the same time, at some institutions, the work of an editor is considered community service. At institutions like the Ministry of Environment and the Namibia Scientific Society, the journal is an additional responsibility with no incentives. Also, the need for incentives for reviewers hinders the review turnaround. Some journals opted to provide an appreciation letter to reviewers that they can use when applying for promotion at their institutions. None of the journals have integrated the Publons reviewer system as a way of demonstrating the value of the impact of a reviewer's contribution to scholarship now. The Namibia Institute of Education (NIED) journal has an independent journal editor who is given a token of appreciation for each issue published. The editor is a retired professor and works as a consultant for the NIED to manage the journal as a journal editor.

Institutional support

Diamond OA journals solely depend on their institutional support for sustainability. Generally, there is no direct budget specifically to support the operations journals at Namibia's universities and other research institutions. However, infrastructures and software are run based on the operational budget submitted to each unit.

No public funding is geared towards OA publishing or a national OA mandate. Most journals are only supported at the institutional level with human resources and technical support, and small financial support mainly covers the layout, design, and editing of journals in a few institutes.

UNAM, through UNAM Press and Centre for Research Services, has made recommendations for hiring a journal manager to oversee the university's five journals; however, the position has been put on hold for some time now. The University Library, Research and Scholarly Communication Unit manage the journal platform, providing training to the journal management team, advice on issues of copyright and licensing and assigning DOIs. The UNAM journals are legally part of the university press; however, due to a shortage of staff and limited expertise in journal management at the press, the responsibility has been left to the library and journal editors. The UNAM, through the Library: Research and scholarly communication sections and Centre for Research Services, has established the journal development guidelines, which explain the requirements and standards that journal managers should follow; however, while the guidelines have been accepted by the institutional Research Innovation and Development Committee, it was referred to the committee to draft a policy that will support the guideline. The policy is still in development.

Collaboration

Namibian institutions publishing Diamond OA journals need to collaborate more; despite the initiative to form a community of practice during the Consultative meeting for research output and journal accreditation framework, such an initiative has never materialized.

Namibian universities have not yet opted to share reviewer databases. The issue of identifying potential reviewers has been an emerging question, indicating that there is a need for a collaborative and integrated shared reviewer database for Namibia and Africa.

The University of Cape Town hosts journals of the [UNAM](#), NCRST, and the Namibia University of Science and Technology (NUST) as part of the [Africa Platform for Open Scholarship](#) a continental platform for the publishing of OA journals, monographs and textbooks in Africa developed through its library service. The University of Cape Town provides training for hosted institutions, journal editors, and reviewers, as well as the OJS software and technical support to host institutions, including the migration to the upgraded version of OJS.

UNAM supported NCRST in developing their journals, integrating the DOI assignment in the OJS, and dealing with other technical challenges.

UNAM is working with journal editors to identify compliance issues for journal indexing in DOAJ and supports other institutions in dealing with issues related to ethics, copyright, licensing, indexing, DOI assignment and capacity building. However, there needs to be more collaboration at the institutional level to support open scholarship, collaboration regarding the co-hosting of journals at a country level, facilities and infrastructure like software, sharing of expertise in journal management and reviewing manuscripts. The NCRST, supposed to support these initiatives as part of national R&D development, has opted to publish its journal instead of providing accreditations and financial and infrastructure support to improve the sustainability of OA publishing.

Funding and sustainability

The misconceptions about OA publication contribute to non-funding, as OA publishing is mainly associated with poor quality. In addition, the lack of a national OA publishing mandate and open science policy could be another contributing factor. Another critical factor is the limited funding for research and development at the national level; Namibia relies on international funders to fund research projects, while sufficient national funding for research would be required to fund OA initiatives. In addition, the lack of a national research funding framework and accreditation policy is another hindering factor; institutions must be funded based on research output and innovation development. Funding institutions based on research productivity can help them fund their research initiatives sustainably.

An accreditation framework that assigns equal weight to commercial and OA journals and developing promotion and funding policies that protect and respect OA publications would change the misconception towards OA publishing and encourage local researchers to publish in local Diamond OA journals.

Research institutions and local funding agencies (including the government) should encourage more equitable funding allocations between various OA academic publishing models and improved and more open financial allocation and monitoring. In most cases, priority is given to funding international commercial publishers' OA publishing initiatives; local and African OA journals are abandoned and criticized for poor quality. More investment should be made in these journals.

Challenges

Overall challenges include the following:

- There is limited time devoted to the journal for both editors and reviewers. Most editors and editorial board members are full-time employees at higher education institutions loaded with teaching, postgraduate supervision, and administrative workloads, for whom establishing sound policies for the journal, attending to journal issues, and reviewing manuscripts is an additional responsibility (Kangira, 2019).
- There is no national systemic practice for assessing the quality and standard of journals, and it is up to individual publishers and editors to ensure that journals are of a reasonable quality (Kangira, 2021).
- The lack of national open science and open access policy.
- The poor visibility of local journals also leads to low submission rates and challenges in attracting authors to submit manuscripts. During the stakeholder consultation for the national policy for research outputs and journal accreditation, the need for a rigorous assessment and evaluation procedure was emphasized, which is why the quality and rigour of published papers in some of these journals are of doubtful standard. The assumption is that implementing the research output and journal accreditation framework, as drafted by the Ministry of Higher Education, Technology, and Innovation, will aid in addressing the issue of visibility of the quality of national Diamond OA journals.

- The lack of incentives and reward systems for journals: The publications evaluation strategy at most institutions relies on and favours commercial publishers and sharing research in internationally indexed journals, which are mainly considered for research promotion. Therefore, it ignores that most such publications will only be available to other scholars who can afford university subscriptions to the relevant journals; such publications will remain inaccessible to decision-makers and policymakers in the country whose institutions do not subscribe to significant publications. As a result, researchers tend to submit their manuscripts to platforms where their publications will count for their career development and promotion.
- According to the journal website review, most journals do not have publicly available editorial guidelines describing quality criteria, copyright compliance, ethical compliance, conflict of interest handling, and ethics and research integrity issues.
- While most journals have author's guidelines, which describe the structure of the journal mainly, they still need to address issues of plagiarism, ethical standards, and authorship standards, among others.
- Reviewers' guidelines explaining the structure of the review, what the reviewer should focus on, what should be excluded from the review, and what the attributes of a quality review are not available on journal websites. Interviews with some journal editors showed that they developed a guideline that they sent to the reviewers via email.
- Identifying good reviewers, especially in some specialized topics: If a review is poor, the editor is forced to ensure another review, which results in delays and frustration among authors.

Needs and strategies to advance Diamond OA publishing

- Funding for capacity building and developing a national platform or registry for Diamond OA journals.
- Funding for advocacy and awareness campaigns on the importance of Diamond OA publishing.
- Funding for infrastructures and additional systems for journal operations, such as DOI, ORCID, typeset software, plagiarism software subscriptions, and integration with the open journal system.
- Enhanced collaboration among Namibian institutions and beyond to improve the quality and sharing of resources for the sustainability of OA publishing.
- Develop the national open science and open access policy to govern open science and OA publishing operations and activities.

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5.17 Nigeria

Landscape

There are at least 14 Diamond OA journals in Nigeria published by universities, scholarly societies and a National agency.

Personnel

Some Diamond OA journals have a dedicated unit and team employed by the institution; they have a graphic secretary who does all the work/design internally before sending it to the website manager. Some have the journal domiciled by the faculties/colleges. Two journals reported that there was no dedicated unit, but the institution employed the personnel who shared their time between journal publishing and other tasks.

Institutional support

Most host organizations/institutions provide support in terms of building, furnishing, and salaries for all staff. They also provide computer systems and have an editor-in-chief as part of the permanent staff. Organizations/institutions have made their digital infrastructure available to institutional journals. Virtually all journals were available solely in the print format. However, Nigerian tertiary institutions are taking it upon themselves to create online journal systems and digitize the journals. At some universities, efforts are at advanced stages to digitize all back issues and make them available online.

Funding and sustainability

Diamond OA journals rely heavily on volunteer work; they have some revenue sources, such as grants, collectively-organized funding and donations.

Most Diamond OA journals are funded by the university and the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFUND) that supports the hard copies publishing. In other words, journals are funded by the host institution and TETFUND.

Challenges and solutions

- **Financial sustainability:** In Nigeria, there is scarcity of funds allocated to research and academic publishing, making it challenging to establish and maintain Diamond OA journals. They rely heavily on volunteer work and they have some revenue sources, such as grants, collective funding and donations. Some Diamond OA journals operate at a loss, while the majority do not know their financial status. Lack of funding sources also makes investment in digital infrastructures difficult.
- **Awareness and capacity:** The academic system is not fully aware of the benefits of Diamond OA publishing to their communities. There is a lack of skilled personnel for editorial and publishing tasks and there is resistance to adopting this publishing model.

- **Infrastructure:** Inadequate technological infrastructure and internet accessibility is a contributory factor that hinders the efficient operation and accessibility of Diamond OA journals. Limited access to essential publishing software and platforms and lack of technical expertise for journal management.
- **Capacity and expertise:** The capacity and expertise of researchers, editors, and reviewers in OA publishing needs urgent enhancement to ensure the quality and rigor of the published content. Some journals are not published regularly due to various issues, such as delayed response from reviewers, the lack of funds to engage dedicated IT personnel, etc.
- **Institutional recognition:** Lack of institutional recognition for publications in Diamond OA journals can discourage researchers from actively contributing to such platforms.
- **Global visibility:** Ensuring global visibility, content visibility in major indexing databases like Scopus and the Web of Science and recognition for Diamond OA journals from Nigeria might be challenging, impacting the ability to attract diverse readership and contributors.
- **Competition with subscription-based journals:** Diamond OA journals often face competition from traditional subscription-based journals that have established reputations and financial backing. This makes it challenging for OA journals to attract quality submissions and maintain sustainability.
- **Long-term financial planning** requires careful budgeting, forecasting, and strategic decision-making. Without a solid financial plan, journals struggle to maintain operations and provide quality services to authors and readers.

Obstacles to editorial quality:

- **Defining quality criteria:** It can be difficult to create precise and detailed standards for assessing submissions, to guarantee uniformity in the standards of peer review, and to maintain publication excellence for all articles.
- **Adherence to guidelines:** It can be difficult to make sure that authors, editors, and reviewers follow publication policies, ethical standards, formatting specifications, and editorial guidelines, particularly when handling a variety of submissions from different disciplines.
- **Peer review process:** Difficulties may arise while overseeing the process, making sure reviews are completed on time, obtaining knowledgeable reviewers, protecting reviewer privacy, and striking a balance between author viewpoints and reviewer criticism.
- **Editorial independence commitment:** Maintaining editorial independence and averting conflicts of interest during the decision-making process can be difficult, especially when dealing with institutions, funding sources, authors, and reviewers.

Challenges with publication ethics and research integrity:

- **Criteria for authorship:** It can be difficult to establish precise authorship standards, assign credit correctly, appropriately credit authors, resolve author contributions, and resolve disagreements or issues with authorship attribution.

- **Data reproducibility and sharing:** Because of data sensitivity, confidentiality concerns, availability and resource limitations, promoting data sharing, highlighting reproducibility standards, and putting best practices for data management into practice can be difficult.
- **Plagiarism detection:** Enforcing publication integrity and keeping originality standards can be difficult when self-plagiarism, plagiarism, and duplicate submissions are not detected and addressed through the use of efficient plagiarism detection techniques.

Technical efficiency challenges:

Many ICT technicians in Nigerian tertiary institutions lack proper understanding of the publishing workflow and they often lack training on scholarly communication. As a result, they often face challenges in identifying the right tool and approach to achieve effective scholarly communication. Poor digital skills among journal editors, publishers and reviewers make the situation even more difficult.

Several issues can come up when it comes to the effectiveness of technical services, particularly when it comes to updating and maintaining the technological infrastructure for Diamond OA publications in Nigeria:

- **Limited resources:** One of the main issues are insufficient funds and the lack of financial resources to invest in a strong technical infrastructure. This restriction may make it more difficult to hire qualified IT staff, upgrade systems, or buy the equipment and tools required for effective technical support.
- **Infrastructure maintenance:** Regular maintenance and updates are necessary to guarantee the ongoing functioning and performance of servers, databases, and online platforms. Problems may occur if the staff lacks sufficient skills or experience to carry out maintenance duties.
- **Technical expertise:** Achieving technical service efficiency may be difficult due to a lack of knowledgeable IT specialists who are experienced in server administration, publishing platform management, website upkeep, and technical assistance or due to inadequate training opportunities.
- **Security concerns:** In online publication operations, safeguarding user information, intellectual property, and sensitive data is crucial. While they are necessary, addressing cybersecurity risks, enforcing system permissions, putting data encryption into practice, and upholding safe access rules can be difficult without sufficient funding and knowledge.
- **Integration and compatibility:** Journals may encounter difficulties incorporating new tools, features, or platforms into their current infrastructure as technology advances. It can be difficult and time-consuming to ensure that new technologies function well with existing workflows and that they are properly tested.
- **User experience:** Engagement and workflow efficiency depend on offering authors, reviewers, editors, and readers a user-friendly experience. To improve the entire user experience, there may be difficulties in speeding submission procedures, guaranteeing smooth communication within the online platform, and optimizing user interfaces.
- **Compliance and regulations:** Technical service operations become more complex when data protection laws, copyright laws, accessibility standards, and publishing rules

are followed. It can be difficult to ensure compliance with changing industry standards and legal requirements if there are no formal monitoring or implementation procedures in place.

Potential solutions to address these challenges:

- **Diversification of revenue streams:** This can include seeking institutional support, grant funding, sponsorship, memberships, or partnerships with research funders or institutions to supplement operating costs.
- **Collaborative funding models:** Collaboration among OA journals to pool resources, share costs, or establish consortia can help distribute financial burdens and promote sustainability. Joint initiatives for fundraising, infrastructure sharing, or technology development can be beneficial.
- **Transparency and cost-effectiveness:** Maintaining transparency in financial practices, cost-effectiveness in operations, and efficient resource management can enhance trust among stakeholders and demonstrate commitment to financial sustainability.
- **Community engagement and support:** Building a strong community of authors, reviewers, editors, and readers who advocate for OA principles and support OA initiatives can bolster financial sustainability. Engaging with stakeholders and communicating the value of OA can attract both financial and non-financial support.
- **Expertise:** Building the capacity of journal editors, reviewers, and support staff is crucial for maintaining high editorial standards. However, this requires investment in training and development.

Needs and strategies to advance Diamond OA publishing

To maintain the publication of excellent research that is publicly available and to meet other operating costs, Diamond OA publications need steady financing. Among the financial requirements of Diamond OA journals are:

- **Publication costs** must be funded in order to pay for the expenses related to processing manuscripts, peer review, editing, typesetting, and online publication of articles.
- **Editing and staff support:** Financial support (staff salaries) for editorial processes, including hiring and retaining qualified editors, managing peer review, and ensuring rigorous quality control, copyediting and production ensuring high-quality content formatting and publication.
- **Infrastructure:** In order to improve the journal's online visibility and performance, resources are required for the upkeep of digital platforms, hosting services, website maintenance, online submission methods, archive systems, and technical assistance.
- **Indexing and DOI registration:** In order to improve Diamond OA journals' discoverability, impact, and visibility through the registration of DOIs and their inclusion in reliable databases and directories and other strategies that enhance the visibility and credibility of the journal.
- **Dedicated fund for Initial Setup:** Funding is required for the initial establishment of the Diamond OA journal, including website development, platform infrastructure, and editorial management systems.

- **Marketing and Promotion:** Funding is needed for marketing and promotional activities to increase awareness of the Diamond OA journal within the academic community and beyond and promote the journal to attract high-quality submissions and increase readership.
- **Training Programs:** Financial support for organizing training programs and workshops to enhance the capacity of editors, reviewers, and authors in OA publishing practices.
- **Accessibility and Equity:** Translation and language support to facilitate access for readers with different language backgrounds.

Potential support mechanisms:

- **Policy advocacy/reforms:**
 - **Enabling policies and incentives: Government policies:** Policies encouraging Diamond OA publishing through accreditation systems, research evaluation metrics, or tax breaks. Developing national open access strategies: Collaborative efforts to create a sustainable national OA ecosystem and support infrastructure.
 - **Advocating and reformation for institutional policies** that recognize and incentivize publications in Diamond OA journals for career advancement and promotions.
- **Government support:** Advocacy for government support in the form of research grants and funding for OA initiatives to promote the development of Diamond OA journals.
- **Institutional partnerships:** Collaboration with universities, research institutions, and libraries for financial and infrastructural support.
- **Capacity building and collaboration:**
 - Training workshops and resources for editors, reviewers, and publishers in best practices of Diamond OA publishing.
 - Participating in national and international Diamond OA publishing networks: Sharing best practices, resources, and expertise with other OA stakeholders.
 - Partnerships with technology providers: Negotiating affordable access to essential publishing software and platforms.
- **Awareness campaigns:** Educating researchers, institutions, and policymakers about the benefits and quality standards of Diamond OA journals.
- **Community engagement:**
 - Engaging the academic community through awareness campaigns, seminars, and workshops to promote the benefits of Diamond OA publishing and encourage contributions.
 - Collaboration with professional associations and scholarly societies to garner support, promote Diamond OA publishing practices, and create a sense of community around OA publishing.
- **Innovation and quality assurance:**
 - **Funding for Innovation:** Support for implementing innovative features that enhance the scholarly communication experience, making Diamond OA journals more attractive.
- **Quality control measures:** Resources for maintaining rigorous quality control, including investments in indexing services and DOI registration. **International collaboration:**

- **Global networking:** Building partnerships with international Diamond OA journals and organizations for knowledge exchange, mentorship, and potential joint funding opportunities.
- **Partnerships with funding agencies:** Collaborating with international funding agencies that support OA initiatives to secure grants and financial assistance.
- **Philanthropic support:** Seeking support from philanthropic organizations interested in promoting OA, research, and education.
- **Endowments:** Establishing endowment funds to ensure long-term financial sustainability.

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5.18 Senegal

At least two Diamond OA journals are published in Senegal. Some institutional repositories provide access to the full text of institutional journals (e.g. Bibliothèque Numérique Université Cheikh Anta DIOP).

Revue africaine de santé et de productions animales ([RASPA](#)) launched in 2004 and supported by the École inter-États des sciences et médecine vétérinaires in Dakar collaborates with Episciences – a Diamond OA scientific publishing platform developed by the [Centre for Direct Scientific Communication](#) (CCSD) in France, a [CNRS/INRAE/Inria](#) support and research unit (UAR3668).

Global Africa is a pan-African interdisciplinary and multilingual journal available in four languages: French, English, Arabic and Swahili. This journal was created by four institutions (LASPAD of [Gaston Berger University of Saint Louis](#) (Senegal), the [French Institute for Research and Development](#) (France), the [International University of Rabat](#) (Morocco) and [LASDEL](#) of Niamey-Parakou (Niger-Benin)) and is co-managed collectively within the framework of a consortium. Nine other partners support this journal: the African Studies Association for Africa ([ASAA](#)) in Ghana, the Council for the Development of Social Science Research in Africa ([CODESRIA](#)) in Senegal, the National Institute of Statistics and Economic Studies ([INSEE](#)) in France, the University of Manouba ([ULM](#)) in Tunisia, Les Afriques dans le monde ([AML](#)) in France, the African Worlds Institute ([IMAF](#)) in France, [The Conversation](#) in France, the Virtual University of Senegal ([UVS](#)) in Senegal and the Network of Science Journalists of French-speaking Africa ([RJSFA](#)) from West Africa.

5.19 South Africa

Landscape and policies

The South African Open Science Policy is yet to be approved by the South African Parliament. Advocacy efforts and supportive policies at institutional and governmental levels are essential for promoting and sustaining Diamond Open Access (OA) publishing in South Africa. This includes advocating for funding support, providing the necessary infrastructure, establishing institutional repositories, and implementing open access mandates.

South Africa publishes 322 scholarly journals, all of which are DHET accredited; 192 are OA, with 81 Diamond OA journals and 111 openly available via repositories. The remainder of the journals (130) are subscription-based journals. Many traditional subscription-based journals in South Africa are considering transitioning to OA models, including Diamond OA publishing. However, this transition requires careful planning and consideration of financial implications, as well as the need to maintain editorial quality and integrity.

25 portals have been established in South Africa hosting OA journals, although not exclusively Diamond OA journals.

A number of shared services are provided through the Academy of Science of South Africa (ASSAf) Scholarly Publishing Programme (SPP) to support scholarly publishing in South Africa:

Hosting Platform: *SciELO SA and Khulisa Journals*⁹ provide a robust hosting platform for scholarly journals, allowing them to publish their content in OA. This platform includes tools and resources for managing the editorial process, peer review, and publication workflows.

Indexing and Visibility: Journals hosted on the SciELO SA and Khulisa Journals platforms benefit from increased visibility and discoverability through inclusion in the SciELO Citation Index. This indexing service enhances the visibility of journals within the global scholarly community and helps increase their impact and citation metrics.

Quality Control: SciELO SA and Khulisa journals implement rigorous quality control measures to ensure the integrity and credibility of the journals hosted on its platform. This includes adherence to international publishing standards, peer review processes, and editorial oversight.

Technical Support: The SciELO Network and Khulisa Journals offer technical support and assistance to journals and publishers using its platform. This includes training and guidance on using the two publishing systems, troubleshooting technical issues, and optimizing journal websites for usability and accessibility.

Capacity Building: ASSAf SPP provides training and capacity-building initiatives for editors, reviewers, authors, and other stakeholders in scholarly publishing. This includes workshops, webinars, and resources aimed at improving publishing practices, enhancing editorial skills, and promoting best practices in open-access publishing.

Research Metrics: ASSAf SPP offers tools and resources for tracking and analyzing research metrics, including citation counts, usage statistics, alternative metrics, and impact factors. This

⁹ Khulisa Journals utilize the Public Knowledge Project (PKP) Open Journal Systems (OJS) software

helps journals and publishers assess the reach and influence of their publications and identify areas for improvement.

It must be acknowledged that Portals hosted by Universities and other institutions also offer some of the following services i.e. hosting, technical support and capacity development.

Overall, the ASSAf SPP plays a critical role in supporting OA scholarly publishing, offering a comprehensive suite of services to journals and publishers to enhance the visibility, quality, and impact of their research output.

Journals

This report about Diamond OA journals in South Africa is based on the survey of selected 17 Diamond OA journals.¹⁰ The majority of the surveyed journals (16) have demonstrated a commitment to uphold editorial quality, research integrity, and publication ethics through the implementation of comprehensive policies, guidelines, and instructions.

Personnel

Most journals (9 out of 17), maintain a staffing range of two to five individuals. Such a staffing configuration typically includes key roles such as editors, assistant editors, and administrative support staff. This size range allows for relatively efficient management and coordination of editorial processes while ensuring a dedicated focus on maintaining high-quality standards. Four journals have up to two staff members, three have 11-20, while one has 6-10 people.

In the majority of cases (8 out of 17 journals), there is a dedicated unit overseeing the operations conducted by the teams responsible for publishing the journal. These units, comprising both employed personnel and volunteers, play a pivotal role in streamlining and optimizing the various facets of the editorial process. The amalgamation of professional expertise with the commitment of volunteers, fosters a dynamic synergy, enhancing the overall efficiency and effectiveness of the journal's operations.

None of the surveyed journals reported incentives for editorial team members, such as a reduction in other institutional administrative responsibilities or additional points during evaluation/promotion processes, as recognition for their dedicated work in managing the respective journals. This observation raises important questions about the broader institutional acknowledgment of the crucial role played by these journals in advancing scholarly communication. Recognizing and incentivizing editorial board members and staff can be pivotal in fostering a positive and sustainable publishing environment. Institutions may consider revisiting their policies to ensure that those contributing to the success of academic journals receive due recognition and support.

Institutional support

Facilities and premises are generously provided in-kind to a significant portion of the surveyed journals (9 out of 17). This provision not only underscores the collaborative nature of scholarly

¹⁰ Out of 81 Diamond OA journals 26 indexed by DHET, DOAJ, SciELO SA, Scopus and/or WoS were selected to be surveyed; 17 responded.

publishing but also alleviates potential financial burdens on the journals, allowing them to allocate resources to other critical aspects of their operations. Moreover, the commitment to supporting these journals extends beyond physical infrastructure (7 out of 17 journals). Eight journals have indicated that essential service-specific IT services, including the development and maintenance of publishing platforms/websites and publication tools, are also covered by the hosting organizations. They also provide HR management, general financial and legal services (6 journals), as well as the salaries of permanent (5) and temporary staff (4).

Collaboration

The survey findings highlight a commendable trend of collaboration among the surveyed journals across various operational aspects. Communication services emerged as a focal point for collaboration, with a significant majority (7 journals) indicating partnerships in areas such as marketing, dissemination, and social media management. They are followed by organizational IT services, where six journals reported engaging in collaborative efforts. These partnerships extend to critical components such as submission systems, platform development, and website management. By sharing technological infrastructure and expertise, journals can optimize their digital presence and ensure a seamless and efficient online experience for authors, reviewers, and readers alike.

Collaboration extends into the core editorial functions, with three journals reporting collaboration in editorial services. This includes joint efforts in the selection of manuscripts, peer-review processes, and plagiarism checking services.

The survey also reveals collaborative initiatives in production services, with five journals engaging in joint efforts related to copy-editing, proofreading, typesetting, and metadata management, ensuring a standardized presentation of scholarly works, enhancing the overall quality and professionalism of the publications.

Lastly, the collaborative ideas extend to training, support, and advice, with five journals reporting partnerships in navigating publishing policies and best practices. This collaborative exchange of knowledge reflects a collective commitment to continuous improvement and adherence to industry standards, ultimately benefiting the scholarly community as a whole.

Funding and sustainability

The study reveals diverse funding models among the surveyed journals. Five journals reported being sustained by a fixed and permanent subsidy from their primary institution's base, indicating a stable and consistent financial backing. Similarly, five other journals indicated a reliance on funding through a partially negotiated subsidy from their primary institution, reflecting a more dynamic financial arrangement. None of the journals reported generating funds collectively.

Alternative funding sources have also been identified. Some journals diversify their revenue streams through advertising, with industry advertisements strategically placed on their websites. Page charges and donations from professional bodies were also highlighted as sources of income, with the latter showcasing a collaborative approach involving stakeholders invested in

the journal's mission. Additionally, a few journals mentioned receiving one-off grants through their publishers, underscoring the importance of forging partnerships and seeking external financial support to sustain and enhance their scholarly endeavors. This array of funding strategies not only reflects the adaptability of journals but also emphasizes the need for a multifaceted approach to financial sustainability in the ever-evolving landscape of academic publishing.

The financial health of the surveyed journals appears robust, with a majority indicating a state of stability. Specifically, seven journals reported being financially stable, while six expressed a high level of financial robustness, categorizing themselves as "very stable." This collective affirmation of financial well-being underscores the effective management and strategic planning implemented by these journals, ensuring a secure foundation for their continued operation.

Notably, none of the surveyed journals reported any signs of financial instability, reflecting a positive and optimistic outlook within the academic publishing landscape. This lack of instability signals a successful alignment between the operational needs of the journals and the available financial resources, contributing to a sense of confidence in their sustainability. As financial stability is a key determinant of a journal's ability to fulfill its scholarly mission, these findings suggest that the surveyed journals are well-positioned to continue contributing meaningfully to academic discourse and knowledge dissemination in the foreseeable future.

Among the surveyed journals, a clear financial planning structure is evident, with 15 out of the total having established an annual approved budget. The existence of an approved budget serves as a strategic tool, enabling journals to manage expenses, plan for contingencies, and make informed decisions in alignment with their overarching goals, as far as possible.

Two journals within the study sample reported not having an annual approved budget. While the reasons for this variation are not explicitly outlined, it could suggest differing financial management approaches or perhaps a reliance on alternative funding models.

Despite their overall financial stability, it is noteworthy that a significant portion of the surveyed journals, specifically 11 out of the total, do not currently have a journal sustainability plan in place. This finding raises pertinent questions about the long-term strategic vision and preparedness of these journals to navigate potential challenges or changes in the scholarly publishing landscape. A journal sustainability plan is crucial for ensuring the continued success and impact of academic publications. The absence of such plans among the majority of the surveyed journals may indicate an opportunity for further exploration and development within the academic publishing community.

Technical infrastructure

A significant portion of the surveyed journals (8 out of 17) fully outsource technical maintenance and upgrades. This reflects a reliance on external expertise, allowing these journals to benefit from specialized technical support while potentially streamlining their operational workflows.

Four journals have indicated that technical maintenance and upgrades are primarily outsourced, suggesting a partial reliance on external technical support. This approach may involve a

combination of outsourcing for specialized tasks and utilizing in-house capabilities for specific aspects of technical infrastructure management.

Four other journals reveal that technical support for maintenance and upgrades is provided in-house by an IT department or in-house IT personnel. This self-sufficiency approach indicates a preference for leveraging internal resources and expertise to handle the intricacies of maintaining and updating the technical infrastructure.

The outsourcing model allows for access to specialized skills, while the in-house approach reflects a commitment to leveraging internal capabilities. Each strategy has its own merits, and the diversity observed within the surveyed journals reflects the nuanced decision-making involved in managing the technical aspects of Diamond OA publications.

The predominant trend among the surveyed journals is the support for online publishing workflows, with twelve out of the total indicating a seamless integration of digital platforms throughout the entire publication process (from submission, through peer review, to the subsequent dissemination of approved content to the public). All of them use the Public Knowledge Project (PKP) Open Journal Systems (OJS).

In five journals, only some workflows are conducted online. Despite the prevalent trend towards comprehensive online platforms, some journals may still retain elements of traditional practices, perhaps relying on conventional communication channels such as emails for specific stages of the publication process. This dual approach may be attributed to various factors, including the comfort level of stakeholders with established practices, the nature of specific editorial tasks, or the need for a gradual transition to fully digital workflows. The persistence of email as a potential means of communication underscores the importance of understanding the diverse strategies employed by journals to navigate the evolving landscape of scholarly publishing.

The survey findings reveal a widespread adoption of Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) among the surveyed journals, with a notable emphasis on Crossref DOIs. A substantial majority of 15 journals have implemented Crossref DOIs, recognizing and accepting Crossref as a key infrastructure provider for scholarly content. The use of Crossref DOIs not only enhances the discoverability and citability of published works but also aligns with industry standards, promoting interoperability across various scholarly platforms and databases.

Moreover, the integration of Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID) is another trend among the surveyed journals, with 15 indicating that they have embraced this unique identifier system.

The fact that no major challenges related to technical service efficiency among the surveyed journals have been reported indicates a level of operational smoothness and effectiveness in the implementation of technical services within these scholarly outlets. Despite the current positive outlook, it remains crucial for journals to continue monitoring and evaluating their technical service efficiency regularly. Ongoing investments in staff training, infrastructure, and technology updates will be essential to ensure that technical services remain robust and aligned with the evolving needs of authors, reviewers, and readers. Regular feedback mechanisms and a

commitment to continuous improvement will further contribute to sustaining the efficiency of technical services within the surveyed journals.

Challenges

The predominant challenge faced by the surveyed journals, highlighted by seven of them, revolves around **securing guaranteed, long-term financial support**. This recurring theme emphasizes the critical role that sustained funding plays in maintaining the operational continuity and impact of academic publications. A number of responses illustrate the intricate relationship between financial sustainability and the operational efficiency of the journal. For example, a journal that currently has a secure financial situation conveyed a sense of caution regarding the stability of the situation in the long term. Other journals indicated that their Diamond OA status could be jeopardized unless they secured long-term funding, highlighting the possibility of having to resort to Article Processing Charges (APCs) or the adoption of the "subscribe to open" model to navigate financial challenges. The Diamond OA model could be difficult to sustain as some African institutions prefer compensating peer reviewers with nominal fees, potentially offsetting costs through APCs.

The **financial dependency on host organizations or professional bodies** emerges as another challenge, with funding directly contingent on the financial health of these entities. This interdependence introduces a level of vulnerability for journals, as fluctuations in the financial status of the host organization or professional body can directly impact the journal's financial stability. For seven journals guaranteed financial support is the main challenge for financial sustainability, while financial illiteracy, the number of papers to publish and limited sponsorship/advertising are mentioned by one journal each.

Among the surveyed Diamond OA journals, a predominant challenge are **financial constraints** (reported by 12 journals). This underscores a critical issue faced by many scholarly outlets operating under the Diamond OA model, where funding sources are often limited or unpredictable. Financial challenges can encompass various aspects, including covering operational costs, managing publication expenses (including copyediting and layout editing), and ensuring sustainable long-term viability. The impact of financial constraints extends beyond the immediate fiscal concerns, affecting the overall health and growth potential of these journals.

Simultaneously, nine journals identified a **lack of human capacity** as a significant challenge. This human resource constraint can manifest in various ways, such as insufficient staffing to handle the increasing volume of submissions along with other full-time, non-journal related responsibilities, limited editorial support, or a shortage of skilled professionals with expertise in scholarly publishing (e.g. reviewers). The interconnection between financial constraints and human capacity becomes evident in scholarly publishing, where personnel play a crucial role in editorial processes, peer review coordination, and overall journal management. Without adequate funding, journals may struggle to attract and retain qualified personnel, exacerbating the challenges posed by a shortage of human capacity.

Six journals mentioned **administrative constraints**. Technical limitations of the existing infrastructure and archiving, backing up and preservation are challenges for four journals each.

Interestingly, no journals mentioned reported the lack of expertise, issuing PIDs and efforts to maintain interoperability as challenges.

As already mentioned, no major challenges related to technical service efficiency were reported. Still, one journal articulated dissatisfaction with open-source software, illuminating the complexities associated with technology adoption in the scholarly publishing domain. The challenges cited include the perceived high cost of well-functioning online content management systems and, conversely, the limitations and delays associated with relying on open-source solutions. The dissatisfaction extends to concerns about inadequate functionality and support, hindering the journal's ability to implement the latest best practices for authors, indexes, and journal staff. This candid assessment highlights the nuanced considerations involved in technological choices, with journals navigating a delicate balance between functionality, cost, and the imperative to stay competitive in the scholarly publishing landscape. These specific challenges underscore the need for tailored and flexible solutions to address the unique circumstances faced by individual journals, contributing to a more nuanced understanding of the diverse needs within the academic publishing community. It is noteworthy that many Diamond OA journals apart from the surveyed ones lack the necessary technical infrastructure and expertise to manage the publishing process effectively. This includes issues with website hosting, manuscript submission systems, and metadata management, which can hinder the quality and efficiency of publishing workflows.

Needs and strategies to advance Diamond OA

The survey responses highlight the important role of long-term financial support, rather than short-term injections, to expand the journals' capacity, particularly in terms of personnel (e.g. covering salaries for additional staff), as a key factor that could enhance their sustainability. A strategic allocation of resources, especially in terms of human capital, could alleviate the workload on existing staff, fostering more efficient editorial processes and improving overall publication quality. Long-term funding not only provides a sense of security for the journals but also enables them to make technological improvements and plan and implement initiatives that contribute to their continued growth and impact within the academic community. This insight sheds light on the nuanced financial requirements of academic journals and highlights the potential benefits of establishing enduring funding models that align with the long-term goals of scholarly publications and the importance of a comprehensive and strategic approach to support the continued growth and impact of academic journals.

The desire to stay abreast of developments in scholarly publishing and adapt to changing environments also emerged as a common theme. One journal expressed a keen interest in exploring new technologies, often situated in Europe or the USA. However, the prohibitive costs associated with adopting these technologies pose a significant challenge, particularly for South African journals. Another journal highlighted the need for additional time and freedom from primary lecturing workloads and postgraduate supervision responsibilities. This request emphasizes the importance of allocating dedicated resources, including time and personnel, to the management and development of scholarly journals.

Institutional and/or national OA journal portals

The report is based on the responses received from 18 portals out of 25 identified. These include two portals with a disciplinary focus on medical and health sciences, 11 institutional portals, and three national portals with a mainly multidisciplinary focus followed by a focus on Social Sciences, Humanities, Engineering, Natural sciences and Agricultural sciences. The national portals, namely the commercial SABINET African Journals and the government-supported SciELO SA, are portals that aggregate journals. In SciELO SA, journals are free-to-read and free-to-publish, whilst in SABINET Africa Journals indexing is free of charge for subscription-based journals, while open access ones must pay a subscription fee to SABINET.

Two portals (SciELO SA and Khulisa journals) apply very strict criteria in order to accept journals for indexing. Journals must be evaluated and recommended by the ASSAf Peer Review Panels before they are considered for hosting and/or aggregation through these portals. All the other portals index journals as per request from the journal editors or institutions.

There are 12 portals hosted by national universities; one portal is hosted by the Medical Association, one by a commercial organization, and two are hosted by a government (Department of Science and Innovation).

Portal name	Journals indexed
Sabinet African Journals	630
SciELO SA	111
Unisa Press Journals	31
SUNJournals	26
UJ Press Journals	17
Khulisa Journals	17
MedPharm Publications	13
UWC Scholar – Online Publishing Support Service	12
African Platform for Open Scholarship (APOS)	10
Kovisejournals	9
SAMA	8
UCT Open Access Journals	7
Open Journals	6
Rhodes Hosted Journals	5
PULP Pretoria University Law Press	4
CPUT Open Journal System	3
Durban University of Technology	1
Total	923

Sabinet African Journals and SciELO SA index a significantly greater number of Diamond OA journals than other portals.

Collaboration

Portals expressed their interest in collaborating with other organizations to reduce costs in several areas: eight portals mentioned a desire to collaborate on production services such as copy-editing, proofreading, typesetting, and metadata management; nine expressed interest in collaborating on IT services including submission systems, platforms, and websites; six indicated an interest in collaborating on communication services such as marketing, dissemination, and social media management; four mentioned interest in collaborating on administrative, legal, and financial services including contracts, accounting, and documentation; and nine expressed interest in collaborating on training, support, and advice regarding publishing policies and best practices.

Challenges

The following main challenges to the sustainability of portals have been identified:

- Financial
 - Financial constraints pose significant challenges, particularly in covering editorial costs for new journals. This may hinder the expansion of the portal's offerings and services.
 - Funding isn't guaranteed and the portal relies on university budgets and library subscriptions. Dedicated institutional funding is essential for the portal's sustainability.
 - Due to fluctuating costs, there's no dedicated budget for expenditures and the portals rely on Open Source software to manage expenses.
 - If a portal is migrated from the university hosting to a different hosting scheme (e.g. RRENS), this may challenge financial sustainability due to potential hosting fees. Funders should cover these expenses to maintain the Diamond OA model.
 - Rising hosting costs necessitate either adding more journals or adjusting fees for current journals hosted.
 - Previous revenue streams (e.g. advertising in the medical field) are no longer viable.
 - Exploring fundraising opportunities, particularly focusing on book series for specific funders, could alleviate financial strains.
 - The lack of long-term funding guarantees beyond the current cycle raises concerns about the sustainability of portal operations. This uncertainty may affect long-term planning and strategic initiatives.
 - Securing funding for COPE membership is identified as crucial for enhancing the journal hosting service's credibility.
- Limited utilization of OJS (using only a part of the online workflows) may indicate potential inefficiencies in workflow management and publication processes.
- Technical challenges, such as the absence of layout templates for all journals and the lack of plugins for integrating with other services, may hinder user experience and functionality.

- Funding limitations also impact indexing archives on the platform and achieving accreditation from regulatory bodies like DHET. This could affect the visibility and credibility of the journals hosted.

Addressing these challenges requires collaborative efforts from various stakeholders, including publishers, universities, funding agencies, and government bodies, to build a robust and sustainable Diamond OA publishing infrastructure in South Africa.

Needs and strategies to advance Diamond OA portals

The following steps can be taken to advance Diamond OA portals:

Infrastructure Enhancement: There's a pressing need for infrastructural improvements, such as implementing a comprehensive search facility across all African universities. This is crucial for improving accessibility to scholarly content.

Skilled Human Resources: Adequate human resources are essential to support the editorial teams of journals hosted by the portals. A lack of skilled personnel may hinder the quality and efficiency of publishing processes.

Long-term funding guarantees beyond the current cycle are necessary to ensure the sustainability of portal operations. Additional funding is crucial for infrastructure development, metadata assistance, and content preservation. Centralizing and funding editorial processes can professionalize services for journal editorial boards, potentially reducing reliance on commercial publishers like T&F. However, this would require a national mandate on OA publishing from government bodies.

Compensation for peer review: In Africa, there is a growing recognition that peer reviewers need to be compensated with a minimal fee. Centralized funding for this purpose could streamline the process and ensure consistency across journals.

Providing templates for layout editing to all journals, as initiated by UCT Libraries, can alleviate the need for institutions to cover publication fees.

Offering free access to services like similarity detection and DOIs for African journals can enhance accessibility and scholarly integrity.

The establishment of a national instance for platforms like PKP OJS could centralize resources, skills, and funding, leading to more efficient operations across universities.

Raising awareness about Diamond OA publishing and providing guidelines for financial independence from APCs can empower individual OA journals.

Political support and commitment are essential for implementing funding models and promoting OA in South Africa.

Toolkits for advocacy and initiatives to increase the visibility and accessibility of journals can further support the growth of OA publishing in Africa. Overall, addressing these challenges

requires concerted efforts from stakeholders across academia, government, and funding agencies

Capacity Building: There is a need for capacity building initiatives to support new and emerging editors, reviewers, portal administrators\managers and authors involved in Diamond OA publishing.

Setting up a SciELO Africa portal with the necessary services (e.g. PKP OJS) can contribute to sustainable Diamond OA journals.

Conclusions

Considering that OA diamond journals do not charge publication or subscription fees, they must rely on scholarly community support, library and institutional funding, or volunteer labour to cover their expenses.

Government, national-and institutionally backed journals show higher sustainability, indicating the importance of stable, national-level support.

Ultimately, we would like to emphasize the need for national and international support to enhance the sustainability of OA diamond journals and propose that a collective approach involving policymakers, funding agencies, and journal administrators is crucial for fostering a sustainable open access ecosystem.

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5.20 Tanzania

The report provides general insights about Diamond OA journal publishing at the University of Dar es Salaam (UDSM). It doesn't use a scientific methodology and conclusions don't reflect the situation on the national level. Diamond OA journals are also published by other universities – e.g. Muhimbili University of Health and Allied Sciences, Mzumbe University, Open University of Tanzania and Sokoine University of Agriculture but their publishing practices are not covered in this overview.

UDSM has a journals policy, which periodically undergoes review, and all journals published by the university comply with the policy. All journals published by the UDSM are evaluated for quality every two years and they are ranked based on the adherence to a set of standards defined in the policy. The quality criteria include the peer-review process, indexing, the international character of editorial and advisory boards, timely publication of the journal, etc. OA-related criteria are taken into consideration to avoid being categorized as predatory journals, e.g. whether the publisher is a member of OASPA, or the journal is registered in DOAJ, a declaration of the journals' business model (closed vs open access), etc.

Personnel

Although there are no dedicated institutional units that would work for journals, publishing operations are usually the responsibility of the coordinators of research and publications at academic units. The office is usually headed by an individual who oversees all matters related to research and publication in a particular unit.

No employees are assigned to work specifically for the journal as they also have other academic responsibilities such as teaching, research and consultancy. Most activities performed by journal staff, including the editor-in-chief, are voluntary and are regarded as part of their academic responsibilities. No direct payment is provided for the editors-in-chief and their associates.

The University provides incentives for various activities including editorial work, typesetting, prepress and technical meetings to discuss critical issues about the journal. The technical committees of the journals are also incentivized for conducting their technical meetings that are aimed at discussing some issues to improve the journal.

Institutional support

The University provides ICT facilities such as desktop computers, printers, the Internet network and working space. All journals acquire legal and ICT services from the centralized legal and ICT departments of the university.

Funding and sustainability

Diamond OA journals are directly or indirectly supported financially by their host institution. For example four journals are supported by the UDSM, which provides funds for various activities including editorial work, typesetting, and prepress. The University sustains Diamond OA journals by providing a minimum amount of funds for specific activities. Currently, the burden of sustaining the journals is largely borne by the respective academic units.

Collaboration

The only notable collaboration which is evident and which has worked successfully for decades is between AJOL and the Tanzania journals.

Technical infrastructure

The OA journals at the University of Dar es Salaam are hosted on a centralized system managed by the Director of the research office. The system is based on the open-source software OJS and is updated from time to time. The journal system is maintained by the IT personnel from the University's ICT department. There are one or two IT staff members who are familiar with the system and they are entrusted with the management of the journal system.

The portal maintained under the Director of Research's office the portal will continue existing to serve the purpose it was created for. The progress of the publishing portal is being reported in senate meetings on quarterly basis.

Challenges

The major challenges related to the financial sustainability of the journals are:

- Financial support for running critical activities such as editorial work, typesetting, and technical meetings.
- The lack of incentives for journal's routine functions.
- The slow Internet connection may hinder the publication process and journal workflows.
- The lack of technical know-how among authors; this can be mitigated by conducting technical workshops.
- Non-compliance with the accepted criteria for inclusion in DOAJ

Needs and strategies to advance Diamond OA publishing

Funding is needed to support the following activities:

- Flipping journals charging publication fees and subscription-based journals to Diamond OA publishing;
- Training for journal editors on some OA publishing;
- Training for authors on topics related to Diamond OA publishing techniques;
- Establishing a portal for Diamond OA journals;
- Providing incentives to the personnel of OA journals;
- Establishing an office which will coordinate and oversee Diamond OA publishing activities;
- Reinforcing Diamond OA publishing through the development of publishing workflows.

5.21 Togo

Two Diamond OA journals have been identified in Togo.

Personnel

Publishers have to mobilize their community (from lecturers-researchers to PhD students) to manage journals. They do not have "professional" teams employed to perform editorial tasks. In Togo, journals are most often created on the personal initiative of the lecturers with a view to disseminate and promote research.

As the management of the journal is not an administrative task at the university, it is not deducted from the statutory hours to be devoted to teaching and research. Accordingly, the periodicity of a journal often depends on the availability of volunteers dedicated to get involved in the publishing process. Similarly, journal editing and publishing is not among the CAMES criteria for career promotion.

Funding and sustainability

Although journals are sometimes funded solely by the hosting organization, research institutes do not always receive public funding.

Apart from institutional support, sources of income can include consultancy and service partnerships, project funding (supported by the European Union, the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), the World Bank and the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)) and membership fees.

According to the editors of the two Diamond OA journals, the decision to opt for OA publishing at no cost to authors is motivated, according to the journal's editors, by a need to promote the publication culture. This challenges the almost systematic introduction of APCs (ranging from €50 to €80 depending on the journal) in OA journals in Togo. For some researchers these amounts are beyond the reach, and early career researchers (master's and doctoral students) are particularly affected, among other things they are in a position to make choices based on the APC amount rather than quality, e.g. choose journals with the lowest possible fees, which may have less rigorous evaluation process.

Challenges

Some of the current challenges are, the lack of financial resources, technical expertise and institutional support are some of the challenges, as well as cooperation at local, national and international levels, the pooling of resources and the sharing of good practices, in particular training.

Needs and strategies to advance Diamond OA publishing

Raising awareness of the benefits of Diamond OA, increasing the commitment of stakeholders and exploring sustainable economic models are essential to overcome current obstacles and effectively promote Diamond OA publishing in Togo.

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5.22 Tunisia

Landscape

There are no clear institutional and/or national policies that cover OA publishing in Tunisia. This means that there is no official guidance or support for researchers who want to manage an OA journal, except for the support provided by the National University Centre of Scientific and Technical Documentation – CNUDST.

There is a registry of scholarly journals in Tunisia maintained by the Scientific Research Department and curated by CNEAR (Tunisian National Commission for the Evaluation of Research Activities), which also includes Diamond OA journals, but it is not publicly available. The CNUDST maintains a list of Tunisian scientific journals on its portal: <https://www.pist.tn/>.

Moreover, there are no institutional and/or national OA journal portals showcasing the Tunisian scientific journal output and increasing its visibility and impact. Therefore, OA publishing in Tunisia is mainly driven by the individual choices and initiatives of researchers who seek more impact from their work by taking advantage of the increased accessibility and citation that the

open access movement offers. However, some decision-makers also have a stake in OA publishing as they aim to enhance the reputation and recognition of their institution's research activities, which are partly reflected by their journal publications.

Some journals have a long history of publication in print format and have successfully transitioned to digital platforms while adhering to the principles of OA, despite the limited financial resources available. Other journals have emerged more recently, driven by the needs and interests of specific disciplines or research groups, and have adopted peer review processes, international collaborations, and open science practices to enhance their visibility and quality. However, these journals also face the pressure of competing with prestigious international journals, especially in fields where Tunisian researchers excel, and where the evaluation of research is highly dependent on publication metrics and rankings.

Tunisian Diamond OA journals rely mainly on the voluntary work of research groups or on the support of their research organizations, such as their research unit or laboratories or from non-governmental scientific associations. However, these journals face many challenges, such as maintaining a high-quality peer review, ensuring the visibility and impact of their articles, and managing their operational costs sustainably. One of the main difficulties is to deal with a restrictive budget that limits their resources and opportunities for development.

Personnel

One way to understand the work of the Tunisian Diamond OA journal's personnel is to look at the type of institutions that publish the journals. Most of the journals are published by government academic institutions, which do not have a specific unit for journal publishing. Instead, they use their existing staff, who have to divide their time between journal publishing and other tasks related to the institution. Only a few journals are edited by non-profit scientific organizations, which have some personnel dedicated to journal publishing, but not enough to cover all the work. Therefore, they rely on volunteers to help with the journal publishing process.

There is no formal policy or mechanism to reward the personnel supporting journals. However, the host organization does support and encourage research and publication in the journal as part of its mission. Moreover, being a journal staff member is recognized and valued in the researchers' assessments and CVs, as it shows their contribution to the field.

Institutional support

Journals published by government academic organizations enjoy several benefits from their host institutions. These include:

- **IT Support:** Host organizations typically provide general IT services such as email, hardware, and internet access. Some may even offer specialized services specific to publishing needs, such as developing and maintaining dedicated platforms or websites.
- **Financial Support:** Host organizations often cover a portion of publishing costs, particularly those related to printing, web hosting, and journal-related events.
- **Administrative Support:** Administrative tasks such as personnel management, budgeting, and legal compliance are often handled by the host organization. In addition,

host organizations can utilize their expertise in legal matters, library science, graphic design, and outreach activities to support their journals.

Funding and sustainability

Tunisian Diamond OA journals are funded by the institutions that host them, such as universities or research centers. However, these institutions often face challenges in managing and sustaining their journals, as they have to balance the quality, integrity, visibility and accessibility of their publications with the financial pressures and budgetary constraints faced by their host organization. Moreover, the decision-makers and administrative staff who are responsible for allocating funds to the journals may not have a clear vision or strategy for their development and improvement. On the other hand, some Diamond OA journals are published by scientific associations that rely on other sources of income, such as donations, membership fees, print sales or event organization. These associations may have more flexibility and autonomy in running their journals, but they also need to ensure their financial stability and sustainability.

Collaboration

Some journals benefit from collaboration with AJOL and are indexed by AJOL.

The majority of Diamond OA journals are supported by a program led by the CNUDST that assists in enhancing the visibility of the journal through adopting best practices for scholarly publishing and OA/open science principles (COPE, OASPA, etc). This program includes training, personalized assistance and support for the editorial board.

Funding and sustainability

Tunisian Diamond OA journals' resources are often scarce, unstable, or insufficient to cover the costs of quality peer review, editing, production, dissemination, and preservation of scholarly content. Therefore, there is a need to identify and prioritize the funding needs and opportunities for sustainable Diamond OA publishing in Tunisia.

The current policy landscape may not sustain Diamond OA journals and may threaten these initiatives if it is not supported by a clear strategy in this area from which budgetary funding allocations result.

Technical infrastructure

The technical infrastructure of Diamond OA journals is an important aspect of their publishing quality and sustainability. Different journals may adopt different approaches to maintain and update their systems, depending on their resources, expertise and needs. For example, some Tunisian Diamond OA journals outsource their technical infrastructure to external providers, who are responsible for ensuring the security, functionality and accessibility of their platforms. Other journals host their publishing systems on public hosting or ISP services, which are free of charge, and rely on in-house staff, such as a technical agent from the IT department, to perform the maintenance and updates. These choices may have implications for the journals' autonomy, costs and performance.

Challenges and solutions

One of the main challenges related to the financial sustainability of Diamond OA journals is the cost of maintaining a publishing platform that meets the technical and ethical standards of OA. This includes covering the related costs of membership to adopt persistent identifiers (PIDs such as DOIs, ORCIDs, RORs, etc.) which are necessary for tracking and linking the publications and their authors, funders, and institutions. Moreover, journals also cover the cost of enhancing scholarly integrity by complying with its plagiarism policy, which requires checking the originality and similarity of the submitted manuscripts using specialized software.

Another challenge is the lack of permanent assistants dedicated to editorial tasks such as publishing in various formats, copyediting, and ensuring compliance with the journal's policies and guidelines. These assistants are vital for producing high-quality and accessible publications, but they often work voluntarily or share their time with the journal's host organization.

One of the major challenges related to technical service efficiency is finding qualified personnel who can perform the digital transition in the case of print journals and tasks of maintenance, updating, and backup of the platform of e-journals. These tasks are essential for the security and reliability of the service, especially since the hosting aspects have to be done in Tunisia through a public or private provider. Another challenge is securing the necessary budget to hire a third-party service provider who can cover these tasks in case of a shortage of internal resources.

Some services that a third party can offer to Tunisian Diamond OA journals are assisting journal staff via performing periodic audits, providing assistance and advice to help solve issues, hosting training sessions to fill their needs, and ensuring continuous empowerment. These services can help Tunisian Diamond OA journals maintain and improve their editorial standards, comply with good practices, and enhance their reputation and impact.

Moreover, this service provider can help Tunisian Diamond OA journals set up infrastructures that enable them to integrate and adhere to international open science initiatives/infrastructures, such as PIDs (DOI, ORCID, ROR, etc.) and facilitate their indexing and referencing on search engines, journal databases and other platforms.

A subsidized or free publication system, powered and maintained by the service provider, offering online submission, peer review workflows, a shared pool of reviewers or editors, and a centralized marketing strategy can help the editorial team to ensure the quality, accessibility, and discoverability of the published content.

These benefits can help them to reduce their financial challenges by saving money, time, and effort. They will have access to more resources and services that can lower their expenses, improve their efficiency and allow them to focus more on their core mission of producing and disseminating high-quality OA research and better serve the needs and interests of their communities.

Another challenge facing Tunisian Diamond OA journals, in addition to the lack of adequate funding to support their publishing activities, is maintaining a publishing platform compliant with the publishing standards and quality and technical requirements.

One possible way to address this challenge is to develop a national OA journal portal that could provide a platform for showcasing and promoting Tunisian Diamond OA journals, as well as facilitating their access and visibility. Such a portal could also facilitate the adoption of clear national policies that support and incentivize OA publishing, such as mandating OA for publicly funded research, providing subsidies or tax incentives for OA journals, or establishing quality standards and accreditation mechanisms for OA publications. Moreover, national Diamond OA journal portals could be supported by a public organization that has the expertise and resources to maintain and update the portal's technical infrastructure, as well as to provide training and guidance to the editorial board members of the journals. Such organization could also help the journals meet the technical and bibliographic requirements for inclusion in international indexes and databases, by ensuring compliance with metadata standards, interoperability protocols, and participation criteria. Additionally, this portal can index or host scientific journals, assist with PIDs and offer mechanisms to support membership fees required by registry agencies, which can enhance their discoverability and sustainability. Furthermore, this portal can enable the optimization and rationalization of expenses through a shared and centrally funded/managed model that can reduce the financial burden on individual journals and institutions.

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5.23 Uganda

Landscape

Diamond OA journals are published by Universities (e.g. Islamic University in Uganda; Kampala International University; Makerere University, Uganda Christian University and Uganda Martyrs University), research organizations (e.g. National Agricultural Research Organization (NARO)) and not-for-profit organizations (e.g. African Field Epidemiology Network (AFENET)). These journals are supported by institutional funds. Universities provide OJS-based journal publishing platforms. One of the journals: African Health Sciences, acknowledges support provided by the African Health Journals Partnership Project that is funded by the US National Institutes of Health (through the National Library of Medicine and the Fogarty International Center) and facilitated by the Council of Science Editors.

5.24 Zambia

Landscape and policies

At the moment there are no OA policies that back OA publishing at either national or institutional levels, but some institutions such as the University of Zambia (UNZA) have related policies such as the Scholarly Communications and Publications Policy that is meant to guide and regulate scholarly publishing activities in the University. UNZA also has developed an Institutional Repository policy meant to guide and regulate publishing in the repository. There is also the

Zambia Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative Open data Policy that was developed in 2016 available at https://eiti.org/sites/default/files/attachments/zambia_open_data_policy.pdf.

There are at least 23 Diamond OA journals in Zambia published by UNZA departments, Zambia Medical Association, Kwame Nkrumah University, Southern African Institute for Policy and Research and Mulungushi University.

Personnel

Other than a team of editors, almost all Diamond OA journals but one do not have a dedicated team of staff or organ either on full-time or part-time to manage the journal publications. Editors manage publications as well as day-to-day activities of the journals. In the case of UNZA Journals, very few of them have engaged the University Press to help with typesetting though at a fee. The rest of the work editors do on a voluntary basis. The chief editor for one journal for instance indicated that he does most of the work towards the journal publications because if he doesn't do it, no one will and the journal production would suffer.

To the contrary, another journal is run by the Association, which is responsible for engaging companies to host and manage both the Association and the journal. Once the company has been engaged, their roles include the provision of IT services to the Association, websites hosting and management, websites backups and offsite storage, websites integrity and core structure updates, websites content upload updates and basic search engine optimization, website hosting including the provision of SSL certificates for both websites and creating and maintaining corporate emails. The company also represents a journal in web infrastructure technical meetings upon request, manages hosting and publication of the journal, generates and deposits DOIs, designs manuscripts for publications according to the journal standards, designs and creates html galleys and abstracts for the journal, provides the journal with web-hosting reports annually and upon request, as well as graphic design of flyers and artwork for posters, public health holidays, webinar meetings and national events.

There are no direct incentives for the journal personnel per se. However, one can use their involvement in journal publications (either as an editor of a journal or any other role they assume) as a gradable achievement during staff annual appraisal as well as for promotions purposes. For instance, UNZA staff involved in journal editing or in an editorial board scores 4-6 points in the Academic Promotions Tool. This implies that the staff can use their accumulated points for promotions to a higher rank. The unfortunate part is just that despite this involvement in journal management (editing, editorial boards), workload for substantive activities remains the same. So working towards journal production highly remains voluntary hence less attractive to some people.

Institutional support

Most journals receive support from the hosting institution in the form of IT infrastructure such as hosting space, the Internet, and hardware, while there is not much provided in terms of financial support. For example, the three UNZA journals that are managed by the Directorate of Research and Graduate Studies (DRGS) only receive handling/typesetting fees from the

Directorate, which is paid directly to the University Press. The hosting institutions also provide the publishing platforms and email.

Funding and sustainability

Very few journals receive some form of funding such as for typesetting services. Even then, such funding may not be consistent. There is also some indirect funding where the hosting institution pays the internet service provider for its staff to use and in some cases provides hosting space and publishing platform for the journals. Meanwhile, there is no single journal that receives funding outside its institution so far. It is further worthy noting that without proper or consistent funding for the journal publishing, it is very difficult to operate on hybrid basis either (online and print), considering the associated high printing costs for publications. Many times, print sales also may not attract adequate turnover to sustain the journal production. This therefore leaves Diamond OA journals with no choice but to operate online, an avenue that looks manageable once all IT-related requirements have been met by respective institutions.

Meanwhile, the Medical Journal of Zambia is run and funded by the Zambia Medical Association/SIDA and engages hosting companies to run all its affairs. The Journal of Science and Technology is run and funded by UNZA but the aspect of having full-time staff to manage the journal is not clear.

Sustainability planning includes the use of cloud and or Zambia Research and Education Network (ZAMREN) content hosting space that is potentially huge and can allow much more data hosting and processing power storage facility. Building a national portal for all Diamond OA journals in the country is another sustainability measure.

Collaboration

Apparently, there are fewer journals that have gone online in Zambia to necessitate much collaboration. However, among those that are online, there is no recorded collaboration going on at national level. At institutional level, UNZA journals share the hosting and publishing platforms as well as training of editors and reviewers of its journals. UNZA through DRGS has previously organized workshops for journal editors and reviewers to standardize journal layout, presentation and quality among all journals as well as to encourage print-only journals to go online. Other journals in the country exist independently and are hosted by their respective institutions while one journal is hosted by ZAMREN.

Challenges and funding needs

Issues related to never existing financial strategies for these journals and a combination of poor grant-writing skills to secure funding from the global communities for journal management are among the current challenges.

There is also lack of orientation for new editorial board members, which requires funding for training workshops. You find that many editorial board members incorporated on respective editorial boards lack journal management knowledge, thereby, taking long to make and

implement decisions, which consequently affect the output and frequency of the journal production. Relatedly, funding is needed to support capacity building through exchange programmes for journal editors, reviewers, authors and affiliated staff to conduct training visits to other universities to learn key techniques of running a successful journal.

Infrastructure funding is another big issue: funding towards hosting space, engagement of trained IT personnel to handle platform technical issues, and or incentives to encourage editors to do their editorial work efficiently as well as payments to UNZA Press staff that help with typesetting. Sometimes responses from the technical team to resolve outstanding issues take long, to the disadvantage of progress and the readers.

Other challenges include the lack of publishing policies in universities and at national level to regulate publishing matters. This makes it easy for journals to operate as they deem appropriate, which may have a negative bearing on the quality of the journal publications across journals.

Technical infrastructure

Diamond OA journals' technical infrastructure is largely managed by IT departments in the involved institutions. UNZA for instance has more than ten OA journals and 90% of these are hosted by the institutional IT department known as the Centre for Information and Communication Technology (CICT). CICT hosts the content and is also responsible for the maintenance of the technical infrastructure for these journals. However, where the IT department is not existing, the internet service providers come in to help such as ZAMREN for those that are hosted by ZAMREN such as the Zambia Journal of Library and Information Science (ZJLIS). Basically, most of the online journals in Zambia are owned and hosted by academic institutions or associations that produce them. This is how the MJZ hires competent companies to take care of all their issues including technical infrastructure.

Most journals use OJS, which provides a researcher-to-reader workflow for authors to submit their manuscripts, journal editors to perform peer-review, manuscript acceptance and then the production and availability of the article or content to the research community. Unfortunately though, some journals have given instructions to authors to send their submissions via email despite their journal using the OJS. This could be another area of training needed among editors.

UNZA Press Publications are available in the repository (at <https://tinyurl.com/369nd3we> – two journal articles), UNZA journals at <https://www.unza.zm/units/journals> (six journals) and at <https://journals.unza.zm> (14 journals although two journals are also listed in the earlier list).

Further reading

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5.25 Zimbabwe

Landscape and policies

At least five universities (i.e. Bindura University of Science Education, Lupane State University, Midlands State University, University of Zimbabwe and Zimbabwe Ezekiel Guti University) have OA policies. These policies have been instrumental in promoting OA publishing including the shift by some journals from the closed to OA model. There is no national policy framework guiding OA in the country. And the country is yet to establish a portal for OA journals.

Zimbabwe Council for Higher Education has begun a process of assessing all journals published in Zimbabwe; those that meet set criteria will be accredited. The Council is in the final stages of implementing a registry of accredited journals. The list will include Diamond OA journals meeting their set criteria that replicate the African Journals Online (AJOL) Journal Publishing Practices and Standards (JPPS) framework.

17 Diamond OA journals were selected for this study as they were considered to be adhering to the basic quality publishing standards. Of note, nearly all the journals identified are owned or managed by universities except a few.

Personnel

For most of the journals, editorial work, peer review, typesetting and related responsibilities are done as either voluntary duties or part of university committee work. At some universities personnel responsible for journals conduct the work as part of committees set up by the University Senate. Other universities have the journals housed in academic departments. The academic departments assign staff on rotational basis or depending on expertise and passion to run the journals. Journals that are not affiliated to universities are run by teams on a voluntary basis. Some institutions assigned their research offices to coordinate the publication processes; the research offices provide secretarial duties as well as identification and appointment of

editorial boards and peer reviewers. This is the case at two universities whereby duties and responsibilities of their directors for research include management of institutional journals.

Universities regard journal publishing work as an important pillar in advancing research and scholarly communications. Staff members responsible for journals are recognized through various ways, namely:

- Their contributions are considered as community engagement, an important portfolio in universities. Academic staff promotion and tenure considerations therefore include such contributions.
- Journals advance research; those involved in journal publishing as editors or peer reviewers are rewarded for their work during staff promotions and tenure considerations.
- Diamond OA publishing enhances institutional visibility. As such, recognition and rewards are granted accordingly.

Institutional support

The hosting organizations consider Diamond OA publishing as part of the normal work undertaken by staff responsible. Resources such as ICT infrastructure, offices and stationery available at these institutions are made available for journal publishing at no cost. In instances where there are additional requirements that outside the available resources, institutions provide these. As an example, one university provided online journal system services so that the university could professionally manage its journals. Similarly, two other universities had to register additional IP addresses to enable their journals to be available online. In all instances the host institutions provide the web domains and email addresses for journals.

Funding and sustainability

Diamond OA journals do not have clear budget lines. However, most of the work is done by volunteers. There have been cases where small grants have been accessed to support Diamond OA publishing. The Research Council of Zimbabwe has, in the past, provided small grants to facilitate introduction of OA journals. Universities have also reached out to organizations such as AJOL for support. AJOL has helped by providing hosting services at no charge and providing training to editorial staff.

Collaboration

Notable collaborations for Diamond OA journal publishing have been spearheaded by AJOL, who have provided a platform for Africa to host its journals. AJOL has been providing training (in person and online) to journal editors on how to effectively use online journal systems and related issues.

Another notable collaboration is led by the University of Cape Town (UCT) Libraries who have been coordinating the hosting of Diamond OA journals on the African Continental platform. UCT Libraries also provides training.

The Zimbabwe University Libraries Consortium has planned a training on the use of PIDs, an aspect which also benefits Diamond OA journals publishing.

Challenges and solutions

The biggest challenge relates to ICT infrastructure for those institutions using their own facilities to host the journals. University budgets have been dwindling thereby risking discontinuation of online journal hosting especially those that depend on cloud facilities. For journals hosted by other institutions, universities feel insecure that such facilities may be discontinued, or some levies may be charged thereby presenting an unbudgeted financial obligation.

Another challenge faced relates to authorship / coverage of the published content. Some of the journals fail to attract submissions from other institutions and countries for the journals to have a proper international flare. For better credibility journal coverage should not be limited to manuscripts emanating from the host institution only. Newly established journals find it to be more challenging because prospects of getting manuscripts from renowned authors are relatively low until the journals have stood the test of time.

Other challenges include the following:

- Perceptions towards OA publishing are, to a greater extent, negative. Many researchers, administrators and policy makers perceive all OA publishing as predatory; this is a misconstrued view that must be addressed. Prevalence of predatory publishing makes the situation delicate to address considering that there is also a misconception that publishing in OA journals is inferior to publishing in closed access journals.
- Staff responsible for Diamond OA publishing lament lack of proper recognition and rewards for the work they do. They also feel that time and resources allocated for Diamond OA publishing is woefully, a situation that compromises on quality, consistency in publications.
- Staff attrition has significantly contributed towards the unintended break, disrupted frequency and discontinuity of Diamond OA journals. Departure of the experts, some of whom are mere volunteers and passionate advocates of Diamond OA journals, has impacted on Diamond OA journals' consistency, quality and existence.

The following solutions were proffered:

- AJOL and related platforms require long term funding so that Diamond OA publishing becomes sustainable in Africa.
- There is a need to raise awareness and get buy-in of leadership at institutions of higher learning so that they do not underplay the value of Diamond OA publishing.
- Clarification is also required on the importance of Diamond OA. Many institutions of higher learning tend to place more value on commercialization of research and innovation; a position that conflicts with Diamond OApublishing.

Technical infrastructure

IT departments mostly provide technical support for running the journals. Academic departments are also assigned the responsibility of managing the journals. Libraries have taken up the 'library-as-a-publisher' concept and have created portfolios of scholarly communications librarians. The scholarly communications librarians are responsible for managing Diamond OA journals as well. In some cases, universities' research offices are also responsible for managing technical issues relating to Diamond OA journal management.

Some of the institutions are still using manual systems in the production of their journals. In such instances ordinary word processing and typesetting software are used. After doing the process outside the OJS' workflow system, the final versions of the manuscripts are uploaded manually onto the system. Other journals have infrastructure allowing online publishing workflows but the infrastructure is partially used. Editorial staff for these journals express lack of skills and confidence in using online publishing workflows. However other journals are gradually moving towards using the online workflows to manage the entire journal publishing process.

Technical challenges include:

- Limited use of the OJS for managing the workflows is the biggest challenge. Producing the journal issues outside the system compromises on quality, has risks of losing some manuscripts in emails, and increases chances of inconsistency.
- Editorial staff cite lack of technical know-how hence they prefer to continue using manual systems or they partly use the OJS especially right at the end for purposes of making accepted manuscripts publicly available online.
- Journal managers for some journals express limited knowledge on how to acquire and assign DOIs for their articles.
- Generally, expertise about journal publishing is low. Special skills relating to the publishing workflow using OJS are very limited.

The following challenges also require attention:

- Training on installation and management of OJS.
- Provision of cloud services for hosting Diamond OA journals.

There is a need to build a huge skills base on Diamond OA publishing, especially use of OJS. Trainees can be librarians, academics, ICT personnel and research office staff.

Data were collected using two methods namely, interviews with scholarly communications librarians and web content analysis. Findings from the study show that publishing journals using the Diamond OA model exists though there is a need to equip institutions with skills to improve it.

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Appendix 1. “Collaboration for sustainable open access publishing in Africa” journals survey

“Collaboration for sustainable open access publishing in Africa” project aims to **develop and deliver a participatory funding approach that will enhance quality and sustainability of African diamond open access** (OA) publishing initiatives while maintaining their diversity. Diamond OA means that no fees to authors and readers are charged. **Two open grant funding calls for proposals** co-designed with the diamond OA community will be issued and the funds provided will strengthen quality Diamond OA publishing across Africa. The project is implemented by EIFL, AJOL and WACREN.

If you are publishing a Diamond OA journal in Africa we invite you to fill in this survey. Your participation in the survey will help us better understand challenges that the Diamond OA community is facing and plan the grant funding calls for proposals to support the community.

The survey is divided into six sections:

1. General journal features
2. Funding, incentives, institutional support, sustainability and collaborations
3. Editorial quality and research integrity/publication ethics
4. Technical service efficiency
5. Visibility and discoverability (including indexation)
6. Challenges, funding needs and support required to make a Diamond OA journal more sustainable

The survey has a total of 37 questions and takes approximately 30 minutes to complete.

The survey closes on February 29, 2024.

Please find a printable PDF version of the survey for you to review before you fill in the survey online. Please note that only the online version can be used to submit your final answers.

The survey should be answered, preferably, on a computer. The survey saves answers per page as you click the “Next Page” button and move to the following page. You can exit the survey if you wish and re-enter by copying the link in the same device and browser from which you first accessed it. The pages you have filled in up to that point will be saved. Please note that you will also be able to go back and make changes to your answers before submitting them.

Please press the “Submit” button at the end of the survey. Otherwise, your answers will not be recorded. Please note, that after pressing the submit button, you won't be able to make any changes to your answers.

If you encounter technical issues while filling in the survey please contact the project manager Iryna Kuchma at iryna.kuchma@eifl.net.

By default, the responses provided in this survey will be anonymised. Neither you nor your affiliation (institution/organization/journal, etc.) will be identified in any future project outputs. Your participation in this study is confidential. Personal data collected throughout the survey (an email if you choose to provide it) will be handled in accordance with the [EIFL's privacy policy](#).

Do you agree with the Privacy Policy?

Yes

Survey questions, mandatory questions are marked with an asterisk

General journal features

1. Country, where your diamond open access journal is registered/based*
2. Your diamond open access journal title*
3. Your diamond open access journal website (URL)*
4. Your diamond open access journal ISSN/eISSN number*
5. Name of the host organization/s of your diamond open access journal (please include the name/s of your journal owner/s – University/Research institute/Professional association or other entity. If there is no host organization, please write so).*
6. Language/s in which you publish your journal articles*
7. How many journal articles did you publish in 2023?*
8. What disciplines does your journal mainly cover? (Please select all that apply)*
 - Multidisciplinary
 - Natural sciences
 - Engineering and technology
 - Medical and health sciences
 - Agricultural sciences
 - Social sciences
 - Humanities
 - Non-academic
 - Other (please specify)
9. How many people work for your journal in any capacity?*

- None
- Less than 2
- 2–5
- 6–10
- 11–20
- 21–30
- More than 30

Funding, incentives, institutional support, sustainability and collaborations

10. How does your journal's personnel work?*
- There is a dedicated unit responsible for the journal with employed personnel (fully or partially employed to work for the journal)
 - There is no dedicated unit and everyone is working as volunteers
 - There is a dedicated unit responsible for the journal with some personnel employed and some working as volunteers
 - There is no dedicated unit but the personnel is employed by the institution and is sharing their time between journal publishing and other tasks

11. Are there any incentives for your journal's personnel at your institution (e.g. less other institutional administrative work, additional points at evaluation/promotion, etc.)?*
- Yes
 - No
12. If yes, please describe the incentives in place.
13. How is your diamond open access journal funded? (Please select all that apply)*
- Fixed and permanent subsidy from your journal's primary institution's base
 - Periodically negotiated subsidy from your journal's primary institution's base
 - Time-limited grants or subsidies, either private or public from outside your journal's primary institution's base
 - Permanent public/government funding (international, national, local)
 - Collective funding (e.g. crowdfunding, membership fees, etc.)
 - Print sales (e.g. print on demand)
 - Any other income (event organization, commercial revenue, loans, etc.)
 - Other (please specify)
14. How stable are these funding sources based on the last three years?*
- Very unstable
 - Unstable
 - Neither stable or unstable
 - Stable
 - Very stable
 - Don't know
15. Do you have an annual approved budget for the journal?*
- Yes
 - No
16. Does your journal host organization provide you with in-kind support either in the form of labour, facility costs or other (excluding peer review)? (Please select all that apply)*
- Facilities and premises
 - Human Resource management, general financial and legal services
 - General IT services (email, hardware, Internet, etc)
 - Service-specific IT services (publishing platform/website, tools, etc)
 - Salaries of permanent staff
 - Salaries of temporary staff
 - Other (please specify)
17. To save costs, do you collaborate/would consider collaborating with other organizations in any of the following areas? (Please select all that apply)*
- Editorial services (selection of manuscripts, peer-review, plagiarism checking services, etc.)
 - Production services (copy-editing, proofreading, typesetting, metadata, etc.)

- IT services (submission system, platform, website, etc.)
- Communication services (marketing/dissemination, social media, etc.)
- Administrative, legal and financial services (contracts, accounting, documentation, etc.)
- Training, support and/or advice on publishing policies and best practice
- Other (please specify)
- None
- Don't know

18. Do you have a journal sustainability plan?*

- Yes
- No

19. What are the main challenges related to the financial sustainability of your journal and how could they be addressed?

*By financial sustainability we mean the capacity to develop and implement feasible medium-term financial strategies that facilitate the consistent execution of editorial tasks, incorporating essential developmental elements for adhering to globally recognized quality standards in editorial work and publishing, all while guaranteeing the continuous accessibility of published content.**

Editorial quality and research integrity/publication ethics

Peer review

20. What type/s of peer review is/are in use in your journal? (Please select all that apply)*

- Single-anonymised peer review (authors do not know who the reviewers are)
- Double-anonymised peer review (both authors and reviewers are anonymous to each other)
- Open peer review – Open identities of the reviewers, authors and editors
- Open peer review – Open reviewers' reports
- Open peer review – Open participation in the peer review process (community)
- Editorial review
- Other (please specify)

Policies/guidelines/instructions

21. Do you have specific policies/guidelines/instructions on editorial quality (definition of quality criteria, compliance, peer review process and editorial independence commitment) and research integrity/publication ethics (authorship criteria, data sharing and reproducibility statements)?*

- Yes
- No

22. If you answered yes, please provide a URL/s of your journal's editorial, research integrity/publication ethics policy/guidelines/instructions.

Editorial Board

23. How many editorial board members does your journal have, NOT including editors or editorial staff? Include all board types if your journal has more than one type of board, such as editorial, international, advisory?

- 1-10
- 11-20
- Other (please specify)

24. Approximately what percentage of your editorial board members are from outside your country

- 1-10%
- 11%-30%
- 31-50%
- Over 50%

25. Approximately what percentage of your editorial board members are from outside your institution

- 1-10%
- 11%-30%
- 31-50%
- Over 50%

Technical service efficiency

26. How is your journal's technical infrastructure maintained and updated? (Please select all that apply)*

- In-house by an IT department/personnel
- In-house by a dedicated publishing department (e.g. the library)
- In-house across different departments
- Partially outsourced
- Mainly outsourced
- Fully outsourced
- Other (please specify)

27. Does your publishing infrastructure support online publishing workflows (e.g. a journal's online platform is used to submit manuscripts, review them and make them openly available after approval for publication)? If your online platform performs some of the online publishing actions only, please indicate which ones.*

- Yes – all publishing workflows are online
- Some publishing workflows are online
- No

28. What software do you use for your publishing system?*

- Open Journals System (OJS)
- Janeway
- Lodel
- DSpace
- WordPress
- Drupal
- Don't know
- Other (please specify)

Other: Customisation or own development (please specify), Other open source software (please specify), Other commercial software (please specify)

29. Do you assign unique persistent identifiers to published content (e.g. DOIs, URNs, ORCIDs, Handles, ARKs)?*

- Yes
- No

30. If you answered yes, please select the persistent identifiers you use:

- Crossref-DOI
- Datacite-DOI
- Other DOI
- ORCID
- URN
- Handle
- ARK
- Other (please specify)

Visibility and discoverability (including indexation)

31. Where is your journal indexed? (Please select all that apply)*

- AJOL
- BASE
- CORE
- DOAJ
- Google
- Google Scholar
- Medline
- OpenAIRE
- PubMed Central
- Scopus
- Web of Science
- WorldCat
- National portal (please include a website (URL))
- Other (please specify)
- My journal isn't indexed anywhere

32. If you tried to get indexed by some indexes/databases listed above and failed, please describe your challenges. (Please select all that apply)

- Satisfying the non-technical participation criteria
- Satisfying the technical participation criteria
- Satisfying the metadata requirements
- Paying for membership, annual or one time
- Paying for recurring charges, for example, monthly fees
- The language of the communications/requirements/paperwork is only in English

- The language of the communications/requirements/paperwork is another language that is hard to understand
- The service/its requirements/its paperwork are too technical
- Other (please specify)

Challenges, funding needs and support required to make a Diamond OA journal more sustainable

33. Which challenges do you face? (Please select all that apply)*

- Financial constraints
- Administrative constraints
- Lack of human resources
- Lack of expertise
- Technical limitations of existing infrastructure
- Providing adequate resources for the infrastructure and services
- Issuing persistent identifiers
- Trying to achieve and maintain interoperability with other services and systems
- Archiving, backing up or preserving content and software
- Other (please specify)

34. What are your unmet funding needs?*

35. What kind of support would make your journal more sustainable?*

36. Your contact email if you would like to receive our call for proposals for grant funding:

Please verify that you have entered a valid email address above, so we can contact you.

37. If you provided your email above, would you also like to receive other updates on the “Collaboration for sustainable open access publishing in Africa” project?

- Yes

End of the survey

Is there any feedback you would like to provide on the survey?

A thank you text that appears when the survey is submitted: Thank you for your participation in this survey! We appreciate the time you have spent answering the questions – this work is vital for our project to understand and support the Diamond OA community in Africa.

Appendix 2. Enquête: Aidez-nous à comprendre l'accès ouvert selon la voie diamant en Afrique

Le projet "Collaboration pour une publication durable en accès ouvert selon le modèle diamant en Afrique" vise à développer et à mettre en œuvre une approche de financement participatif qui améliorera la qualité et la durabilité des initiatives africaines de publication en accès ouvert (AO) tout en préservant leur diversité. L'accès ouvert diamant signifie qu'aucun frais n'est demandé aux auteurs et aux lecteurs. Deux appels à propositions pour des subventions ouvertes, conçus en collaboration avec la communauté AO selon la voie diamant, seront lancés et les subventions accordées permettront de renforcer la qualité de l'édition scientifique en AO dans toute l'Afrique. Le projet est mis en œuvre par EIFL, AJOL et le WACREN.

Si vous publiez une revue en AO selon le modèle diamant en Afrique, nous vous invitons à participer à cette enquête. Votre participation à l'enquête nous aidera à mieux comprendre les défis auxquels la communauté AO est confrontée et à planifier les appels à propositions pour des subventions destinées à soutenir cette communauté.

L'enquête est divisée en six parties:

1. Informations générales
2. Financement, incitations, soutien institutionnel, durabilité et collaborations
3. Qualité éditoriale et intégrité de la recherche
4. Qualité du service technique
5. Visibilité (dont indexation)
6. Défis, besoins de financement et soutien nécessaires pour assurer la pérennité d'une revue en AO selon la voie diamant

Cette enquête comprend 37 questions au total et il faut compter environ 30 minutes pour y répondre.

L'enquête est ouverte jusqu'au 29 février 2024.

Pour préparer vos réponses et y travailler hors-ligne, vous pouvez télécharger une version Word du questionnaire en français.

Il est préférable de répondre à cette enquête depuis un ordinateur. Les réponses sont enregistrées pour chaque page lorsque vous cliquez sur le bouton «Next Page » et que vous passez à la page suivante. Si vous le souhaitez, vous pouvez quitter l'enquête et y revenir plus tard en copiant le lien que vous avez reçu sur le même poste, dans le même navigateur et dans le même environnement à partir duquel vous y avez accédé pour la première fois. Les pages que vous avez remplies auparavant seront enregistrées. Il vous sera également possible de revenir en arrière et de modifier vos réponses avant de les soumettre.

À la fin de l'enquête, cliquez sur le bouton «Submit». Sinon vos réponses ne seront pas enregistrées.

Si vous rencontrez des problèmes techniques en répondant à cette enquête, vous pouvez contacter Iryna Kuchma à l'adresse courriel ci-après : iryna.kuchma@eifl.net.

Les réponses fournies dans cette enquête seront anonymisées. Ni vous ni votre affiliation (institution/organisation/revue, etc.) ne seront identifiés dans les résultats du projet qui seront diffusés. Votre participation à cette étude est confidentielle. Les données personnelles collectées tout au long de l'enquête seront traitées conformément à [la politique de confidentialité de EIFL](#).

Confirmez-vous votre accord avec la politique de confidentialité ?*

Oui

Questions de l'enquête, les questions obligatoires sont marquées d'un astérisque.

Informations générales

1. Pays où votre revue en AO diamant est enregistrée*
2. Le titre de votre revue *
3. Le site web de votre revue revue (URL)*
4. Numéro ISSN/eISSN de votre revue*
5. Nom de l'organisation hôte de votre revue (veuillez inclure le nom du propriétaire de la revue – université/institut de recherche/association professionnelle ou autre entité. S'il n'y a pas d'organisation hôte, veuillez l'indiquer)*
6. Langue(s) dans laquelle/lesquelles vous publiez vos articles*
7. Combien d'articles de revues avez-vous publiés en 2023 ?*
8. Quelles sont les principales disciplines couvertes par votre revue ? Sélectionnez tout ce qui s'applique*
 - Multidisciplinaire
 - Sciences naturelles
 - Ingénierie et technologie
 - Sciences médicales et de la santé
 - Sciences agronomiques
 - Sciences sociales
 - Sciences humaines
 - Non académique
 - Autre (veuillez préciser)
9. Combien de personnes travaillent pour votre revue ?*
 - Aucun
 - Moins de 2
 - 2–5
 - 6–10
 - 11–20
 - 21–30
 - Plus de 30

Financement, incitations, soutien institutionnel, durabilité et collaborations

10. Comment fonctionne le personnel de votre revue ?*
 - Il existe une unité spécialisée responsable du revue avec du personnel salarié (entièrement ou partiellement employé pour travailler pour le revue).
 - Il n'y a pas d'unité spécialisée et tout le monde travaille bénévolement.

- Il existe une unité spécialisée responsable de la revue, dont une partie du personnel est employée et l'autre travaille bénévolement.
 - Il n'y a pas d'unité spécialisée, mais le personnel est employé par l'institution et partage son temps entre la publication de la revue et d'autres tâches.
11. Existe-t-il des incitations pour le personnel de votre revue au sein de votre institution (par exemple, moins de travail administratif au sein de l'institution, des points supplémentaires lors de l'évaluation/promotion, etc.) ?*
- Oui
 - Non
12. Dans l'affirmative, veuillez décrire les mesures d'incitation mises en place.
13. Comment votre revue en AO diamant est-elle financée ? (Veuillez sélectionner toutes les réponses qui s'appliquent)*
- Financement fixe et régulier de votre organisation de tutelle
 - Financement négocié périodiquement avec votre organisation de tutelle
 - Financements ou subventions ponctuelles, privées ou publiques, et extérieures à votre organisation
 - Financement permanent public ou gouvernemental (international, national, régional)
 - Systèmes de financement collectif (ex. Crowdfunding = financement participatif, frais d'adhésion)
 - Vente de documents imprimés (par exemple, impression à la demande)
 - Tout autre source de revenu (organisation d'événements, revenus commerciaux, emprunts)
 - Autre (veuillez préciser)
14. Dans l'ensemble, quelle est la stabilité de vos sources de financement sur les trois dernières années ?*
- Très instable
 - Instable
 - Ni stable ni instable
 - Stable
 - Très stable
 - Je ne sais pas
15. Disposez-vous d'un budget annuel approuvé pour la revue ?*
- Oui
 - Non
16. Votre organisation de tutelle fournit-elle un soutien en nature sous forme de main-d'œuvre, de coûts de maintenance et d'équipements, ou autres (à l'exclusion de l'évaluation par les pairs) ? (Veuillez sélectionner toutes les réponses applicables)*
- Équipements et locaux
 - Gestion des ressources humaines, services généraux financiers et juridiques
 - Services informatiques généraux (messagerie, matériel informatique, Internet, etc.)

- Services informatiques spécifiques au service (plateformes de publication, sites web, outils numériques, etc.)
 - Salaires du personnel permanent
 - Salaires des personnels contractuels
 - Autre (veuillez préciser)
17. Pour réduire les coûts, collaborez-vous ou envisagez-vous de collaborer avec d'autres organisations dans l'un des domaines suivants ? (Veuillez sélectionner toutes les réponses qui s'appliquent)*
- Services éditoriaux (sélection de manuscrits, gestion de l'évaluation par les pairs, services de vérification anti-plagiat, etc.)
 - Services de production (révision, relecture, composition, métadonnées, etc.)
 - Services informatiques (système de gestion des soumissions, plateformes, sites web, etc.)
 - Services de communication (marketing, diffusion, médias sociaux, etc.)
 - Services administratifs, juridiques et financiers (contrats, comptabilité, documentation, etc.)
 - Formation, accompagnement ou conseils sur les politiques de publication et les bonnes pratiques
 - Autre (veuillez préciser)
 - Aucun
 - Je ne sais pas
18. Disposez-vous d'un plan de développement durable de votre revue ?*
- Oui
 - Non
19. Quels sont les principaux défis liés à la viabilité financière de votre revue et comment pourraient-ils être relevés ? *

Qualité éditoriale et intégrité de la recherche

L'évaluation par les pairs

20. Quelles formes d'évaluation par les pairs sont pratiquées dans votre revue (Veuillez sélectionner toutes les réponses qui s'appliquent) ? *
- Évaluation en simple aveugle (les auteurs et autrices ne savent pas qui fait l'évaluation)
 - Évaluation en double aveugle (les auteurs et autrices sont évalué-es de manière anonyme par des relecteur-rices anonymes)
 - Évaluation ouverte par les pairs – Les identités de chaque protagoniste sont connues : relecteurs/relectrices, auteurs/autrices, rédacteurs/rédactrices
 - Évaluation ouverte par les pairs – Les rapports d'expertise sont publiés en regard de l'article évalué
 - Évaluation ouverte par les pairs – participation ouverte au processus d'évaluation (commentaires ouverts à la communauté)
 - Évaluation par le comité éditorial

Autre (veuillez préciser)

Politiques/directives/instructions

21. Disposez-vous de politiques, de lignes directrices ou d'instructions spécifiques sur la qualité éditoriale et sur l'intégrité de la recherche (partage des données et déclarations de reproductibilité) ?*

Oui

Non

22. Si vous avez répondu par l'affirmative, veuillez fournir une adresse URL de la politique, des lignes directrices et des instructions de votre revue.

Comité éditorial

23. Combien de membres le comité éditorial de votre revue compte-t-il, sans compter les rédacteurs en chef ou le personnel éditorial ? Inclure tous les types de comités si votre revue a plus d'un type de comité, comme le comité éditorial, le comité international, le comité consultatif ?*

1-10

11-20

Autre (veuillez préciser)

24. Quel est le pourcentage approximatif des membres de votre comité éditorial qui ne sont pas originaires de votre pays ?*

1-10%

11%-30%

31-50%

Plus de 50%

25. Quel est le pourcentage approximatif des membres de votre comité éditorial qui ne font pas partie de votre institution ?*

1-10%

11%-30%

31-50%

Plus de 50%

Qualité du service technique

26. Comment les services ou l'infrastructure technique sont-ils maintenus et mis à jour ? (Veuillez sélectionner toutes les options qui s'appliquent)*

En interne par un service / du personnel informatique

En interne par un service éditorial dédié (par exemple la bibliothèque)

En interne de manière transversale à plusieurs services

Partiellement externalisé

Principalement externalisé

Entièrement externalisé

Autre (veuillez préciser)

27. Votre infrastructure de publication prend-elle en charge les flux de travail de publication en ligne (par exemple, la plateforme en ligne d'un journal est utilisée pour soumettre des manuscrits, les évaluer et les mettre en accès ouvert après approbation de la publication) ? Si votre plateforme en ligne n'effectue que certaines des actions de publication en ligne, veuillez indiquer lesquelles*.

- Oui – tous les processus de publication sont en ligne
- Certains processus de publication sont en ligne
- Non

28. Quel logiciel utilisez-vous pour votre système de publication ?*

- Open Journals System (OJS)
- Janeway
- Lodel
- DSpace
- WordPress
- Drupal
- Je ne sais pas
- Autre (veuillez préciser)

Autre: Logiciel sur mesure ou développement maison (veuillez préciser); Autre logiciel open source (veuillez préciser); Autre logiciel commercial (veuillez préciser)

29. Attribuez-vous des identifiants uniques et pérennes (PIDs) au contenus publiés (e.g. DOIs, URNs, ORCIDs, Handles, ARKs)?*

- Oui
- Non

30. Si vous avez répondu oui, veuillez sélectionner les PIDs que vous utilisez (Veuillez sélectionner tout ceux qui s'appliquent)

- Crossref-DOI
- Datacite-DOI
- Other DOI
- ORCID
- URN
- Handle
- ARK
- Autre (veuillez préciser)

Visibilité (dont indexation)

31. Où votre revue est-elle indexée ? (Veuillez sélectionner toutes les réponses qui s'appliquent)*

- AJOL
- BASE
- CORE
- DOAJ
- Google
- Google Scholar

- Medline
- OpenAIRE
- PubMed Central
- Scopus
- Web of Science
- WorldCat
- Portail national (veuillez inclure un site web (URL))
- Autre (veuillez préciser)
- Mon journal n'est indexé nulle part

32. Si vous avez essayé de faire indexer votre revue par certains index/bases de données énumérés ci-dessus et que vous avez échoué, veuillez décrire les difficultés rencontrées. (Veuillez sélectionner toutes les réponses qui s'appliquent)

- Satisfaire aux critères non techniques d'inclusion
- Satisfaire aux critères techniques d'inclusion
- Satisfaire aux exigences en matière de métadonnées
- Payer les frais d'adhésion (paiement annuel ou unique)
- Payer des frais périodiques, par exemple mensuels
- La seule langue utilisée pour communiquer, pour les critères et pour toute la documentation est l'anglais
- La langue utilisée pour communiquer, pour les critères et pour toute la documentation est une autre langue difficile à comprendre
- Le service, ses critères et toute sa documentation sont trop techniques
- Autre (veuillez préciser)

Défis, besoins de financement et de soutien nécessaires pour assurer la pérennité d'une revue en AO diamant

33. Quels sont les défis auxquels vous êtes confronté(e) (Veuillez sélectionner toutes les réponses applicables) ? *

- Contraintes financières
- Contraintes administratives
- Manque de ressources humaines
- Manque d'expertise
- Limites techniques de l'infrastructure existante
- Allocation des ressources suffisantes pour l'infrastructure et les services
- Attribution des PID, fournir et enrichir des métadonnées, ou mettre à disposition les métadonnées pour leur utilisation
- Mise en place et maintenance de l'interopérabilité avec d'autres services
- Archivage, sauvegarde ou préservation des contenus et des logiciels
- Autre (veuillez préciser)

34. Quels sont vos besoins de financement non satisfaits ?*

35. Quel type de soutien permettrait à votre revue d'être plus durable ?*

36. Adresse e-mail si vous souhaitez recevoir notre appel à propositions de financement :

Merci de vérifier que vous avez renseigné une adresse e-mail valide, afin que nous puissions vous envoyer des informations sur les actualités du projet.

37. Souhaitez-vous recevoir des informations sur les actualités du projet ?

Oui

Souhaitez-vous ajouter des commentaires sur cette enquête ?

Merci d'avoir participé à cette enquête ! Nous apprécions le temps que vous avez passé à répondre aux questions – ce travail est vital pour notre projet visant à comprendre et à soutenir la communauté de l'AO diamant en Afrique.

Appendix 3. “Collaboration for sustainable open access publishing in Africa” portals survey

“Collaboration for sustainable open access publishing in Africa” project aims to **develop and deliver a participatory funding approach that will enhance quality and sustainability of African diamond open access** (OA) publishing initiatives while maintaining their diversity. Diamond OA means that no fees to authors and readers are charged. **Two open grant funding calls for proposals** co-designed with the Diamond OA community will be issued and the funds provided will strengthen quality Diamond OA publishing across Africa. The project is implemented by EIFL, AJOL and WACREN.

If you are based in Africa and manage an institutional, national, regional and/or discipline specific portal/website that hosts/indexes/aggregates African Diamond OA journals we invite you to fill in this survey. Your participation in the survey will help us better understand challenges that the Diamond OA community is facing and plan the grant funding calls for proposals to support the community.

The survey is divided into six sections:

1. General portal features
2. Funding, incentives, institutional support, sustainability and collaborations
3. Editorial quality and research integrity/publication ethics
4. Technical service efficiency
5. Visibility and discoverability (including indexation)
6. Challenges, funding needs and support required to make Diamond OA publishing more sustainable

The survey has a total of 39 questions and takes approximately 30 minutes to complete.

The survey closes on February 29, 2024.

Please find a printable PDF version of the survey for you to review before you fill in the survey online. Please note that only the online version can be used to submit your final answers.

The survey should be answered, preferably, on a computer. The survey saves answers per page as you click the “Next Page” button and move to the following page. You can exit the survey if you wish and re-enter by copying the link in the same device and browser from which you first accessed it. The pages you have filled in up to that point will be saved. Please note that you will also be able to go back and make changes to your answers before submitting them.

Please press the “Submit” button at the end of the survey. Otherwise, your answers will not be recorded. Please note, that after pressing the submit button, you won't be able to make any changes to your answers.

If you encounter technical issues while filling in the survey please contact the project manager Iryna Kuchma at iryna.kuchma@eifl.net.

By default, the responses provided in this survey will be anonymised. Neither you nor your affiliation (institution/organization/journal, etc.) will be identified in any future project outputs. Your participation in this study is confidential. Personal data collected throughout the survey (an email if you choose to provide it) will be handled in accordance with the [EIFL's privacy policy](#).

- Do you agree with the Privacy Policy?
- Yes

Survey questions, mandatory questions are marked with an asterisk

General portal features

1. Country, where your portal that includes African Diamond OA journals is based*
2. Your portal title*
3. Your portal website (URL)*
4. Your portal scope (Please select all that apply)*
 - Disciplinary portal
 - Institutional portal
 - National portal
 - Other (please specify)
5. Name/s of the host organization/s of your portal (please include the name/s of your host institution/s – University/Research institute/Professional association or other entity).*
6. Language/s in which you publish journal articles on your portal*
7. Languages of the interface and information and support pages (About, Help sections and other guidelines)*
8. How many journals does your portal include?*
9. How many articles does your portal include?*
10. How many articles were added in 2023?*
11. How many journals are Diamond OA?
12. What disciplines does your portal mainly cover? (Please select all that apply)*
 - Multidisciplinary
 - Natural sciences
 - Engineering and technology
 - Medical and health sciences
 - Agricultural sciences
 - Social sciences
 - Humanities
 - Non-academic
 - Other (please specify)
13. How many people work for your portal?*
- None
- Less than 2
- 2–5
- 6–10
- More than 10

Funding, incentives, institutional support, sustainability and collaborations

14. How does your portal's personnel work?*
- There is a dedicated unit responsible for the portal with employed personnel (fully or partially employed to work for the portal)

- There is no dedicated unit and everyone is working as volunteers
 - There is a dedicated unit responsible for the portal with some personnel employed and some working as volunteers
 - There is no dedicated unit but the personnel is employed by the institution and is sharing their time between the portal and other tasks
15. Are there any incentives for your portal's personnel at your institution (e.g. less other institutional administrative work, additional points at evaluation/promotion, etc.)?*
- Yes
 - No
16. If yes, please describe the incentives in place.
17. How is your portal funded? (Please select all that apply)*
- Fixed and permanent subsidy from your host organization
 - Periodically negotiated subsidy from your host organization
 - Time-limited grants or subsidies, either private or public from outside your host organization
 - Permanent public/government funding (international, national, local)
 - Collective funding (e.g. crowdfunding, membership fees, etc.)
 - Print sales (e.g. print on demand)
 - Any other income (event organization, commercial revenue, loans, etc.)
 - Other (please specify)
18. How stable are these funding sources based on the last three years?*
- Very unstable
 - Unstable
 - Neither stable or unstable
 - Stable
 - Very stable
 - Don't know
19. Do you have an annual approved budget for the portal?*
- Yes
 - No
20. Does your host organization provide you with in-kind support either in the form of labour, facility costs or other? (Please select all that apply)*
- Facilities and premises
 - Human Resource management, general financial and legal services
 - General IT services (email, hardware, Internet, etc)
 - Service-specific IT services (publishing platform/website, tools, etc)
 - Salaries of permanent staff
 - Salaries of temporary staff
 - Other (please specify)

21. To save costs, do you collaborate/would consider collaborating with other organizations in any of the following areas? (Please select all that apply)*

- Production services (copy-editing, proofreading, typesetting, metadata, etc.)
- IT services (submission system, platform, website, etc.)
- Communication services (marketing/dissemination, social media, etc.)
- Administrative, legal and financial services (contracts, accounting, documentation, etc.)
- Training, support and/or advice on publishing policies and best practice
- Other (please specify)
- None
- Don't know

22. Do you have a portal sustainability plan?*

- Yes
- No

23. What are the main challenges related to the financial sustainability of your portal and how could they be addressed?

*By financial sustainability we mean the capacity to develop and implement feasible medium-term financial strategies that facilitate the consistent execution of tasks, incorporating essential developmental elements for adhering to globally recognized quality standards in publishing, all while guaranteeing the continuous accessibility of published content.**

Editorial quality and research integrity/publication ethics

24. Do you have any inclusion, revision and exclusion criteria that apply to hosted/indexed journals? (Please select all that apply)*

- Institutional, national or disciplinary affiliation
- Compliance with editorial quality criteria
- Only OA journals are accepted
- Only Diamond OA journals are accepted
- Bibliometric criteria (e.g. publication counts, citation counts, impact scores, etc.)
- Other (please specify)

25. If you have any inclusion, revision and exclusion criteria related to editorial quality and research integrity/publication ethics, please provide the URL where these criteria are published.

Technical service efficiency

26. How is your portal's technical infrastructure maintained and updated? (Please select all that apply)*

- In-house by an IT department/personnel
- In-house by a dedicated publishing department (e.g. the library)
- In-house across different departments
- Partially outsourced
- Mainly outsourced
- Fully outsourced

Other (please specify)

27. Does your publishing infrastructure support online publishing workflows (e.g. a journal's online platform is used to submit manuscripts, review them and make them openly available after approval for publication)? If your online platform performs some of the online publishing actions only, please indicate which ones.*

Yes – all publishing workflows are online

Some publishing workflows are online

No

28. What software do you use for your publishing system?*

Open Journals System (OJS)

Janeway

Lodel

DSpace

WordPress

Drupal

Don't know

Other (please specify)

Other: Customisation or own development (please specify), Other open source software (please specify), Other commercial software (please specify)

29. Do you assign unique persistent identifiers to published content (e.g. DOIs, ORCIDs, URNs, Handles, ARKs)?*

Yes

No

30. If you answered yes, please select the persistent identifiers you use:

Crossref-DOI

Datacite-DOI

Other DOI

ORCID

URN

Handle

ARK

Other (please specify)

31. Do you provide long term preservation options for the journals you host (e.g. via CLOCKSS, LOCKSS, the PKP Preservation Network (PKP PN), Portico, a national library/repository, etc.)?*

Yes

No

Visibility and discoverability (including indexation)

32. Where is your portal indexed? (Please select all that apply)*

- BASE
- CORE
- Google
- Google Scholar
- OpenAIRE
- SciELO SA
- WorldCat
- My portal isn't indexed anywhere
- Other (please include the URLs of all relevant portals)
If indexed in National databases, indicate that under Other and please include URLs

33. Do you provide support to journals that want to get indexed by AJOL, DOAJ, Medline, PubMed Central, Scopus, Web of Science, etc?

- Yes
- No

34. If you tried to get indexed by some indexes/databases listed above (or others) and failed, please describe your challenges. (Please select all that apply)

- Satisfying the non-technical participation criteria
- Satisfying the technical participation criteria
- Satisfying the metadata requirements
- Paying for membership, annual or one time
- Paying for recurring charges, for example, monthly fees
- The language of the communications/requirements/paperwork is only in English
- The language of the communications/requirements/paperwork is another language that is hard to understand
- The service/its requirements/its paperwork are too technical
- Other (please specify)

Challenges, funding needs and support required to make Diamond OA publishing more sustainable

35. Which challenges do you face? (Please select all that apply)*

- Financial constraints
- Administrative constraints
- Lack of human resources
- Lack of expertise
- Technical limitations of existing infrastructure
- Providing adequate resources for the infrastructure and services
- Issuing persistent identifiers
- Trying to achieve and maintain interoperability with other services and systems
- Archiving, backing up or preserving content and software
- Keeping up with similar services
- Other (please specify)

36. What are your unmet funding needs?*

37. How could we support your work to make Diamond OA publishing more sustainable?*

38. Your contact email if you would like to receive our call for proposals for grant funding:

Please verify that you have entered a valid email address above, so we can contact you.

39. If you provided your email above, would you also like to receive other updates on the “Collaboration for sustainable open access publishing in Africa” project?

Yes

End of the survey

Is there any feedback you would like to provide on the survey?

A thank you text that appears when the survey is submitted: Thank you for your participation in this survey! We appreciate the time you have spent answering the questions – this work is vital for our project to understand and support the Diamond OA community in Africa.